

Enhancing entrepreneurial ecosystems for education

REPORT ON MENTORING ACTIVITIES - FINAL RELEASE

14/08/2024

Grant Agreement No.: 101100507
 Call: HORIZON-EIE-2022-SCALEUP-01
 Topic: HORIZON-EIE-2022-SCALEUP-01-01
 Type of action: CSA

D4.5 REPORT ON MENTORING ACTIVITIES - FINAL RELEASE

MENTORING PROGRAMME REPORT

WORK PACKAGE	WP4
TASK	T4.5
DUE DATE	14/08/2024
SUBMISSION DATE	14/08/2024
DELIVERABLE LEAD	FRAUNHOFER IPK
VERSION	3.0
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ABSTRACT	THIS REPORT PROVIDES AN OVERVIEW OF THE ENTREPRENEDEDU MENTORING PROGRAMME'S FINAL RELEASE, DETAILING ITS CREATION, STRUCTURE, EXECUTION, AND RESULTS OF ALL THREE COHORTS. IT INCLUDES FEEDBACK COLLECTED FROM PARTICIPANTS AND MENTORING PARTNERS TO ENHANCE FUTURE ITERATIONS OF SUCH A MENTORING PROGRAMME. THE PROGRAMME, FEATURING SIX MODULES BLENDING E-LEARNING AND INTERACTIVE MENTORSHIP, DEMONSTRATED HIGH PARTICIPANT SATISFACTION, WITH AREAS FOR IMPROVEMENT IDENTIFIED AND ADDRESSED.
KEYWORDS	MENTORING, PLATFORM, PROGRAMME, FEEDBACK, COHORT

Document Revision History

VERSION	DATE	DESCRIPTION OF CHANGE	LIST OF CONTRIBUTOR(S)
V1	01.07.2024	FIRST VERSION SHARED	FRAUNHOFER IPK
V2	14.08.2024	FINAL VERSION	FRAUNHOFER IPK, FEA, CORALLIA, CTBG, EBAN, LUISS
V3	20.09.2024	FINAL VERSION AFTER ADJUSTMENT TO PROJECT COORDINATION REQUEST	FRAUNHOFER IPK, FEA, CORALLIA, CTBG, EBAN, LUISS

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report outlines the creation, structure, execution and results of the ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring Programme including all three Cohorts. Further, it entails and derives actions of a feedback collection from participants of the ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring Programme Cohorts.

The mentoring programme has been carefully structured into six modules, providing a comprehensive journey from ideation to execution for the entrepreneurial teams. Further, derived from the feedback of the participants, a seventh module on Human Resource Management and Leadership for Founders has been developed and is illustrated in Deliverable 4.4. Mentoring Modules - Final Release. However, this module was not part of the executed mentoring programme presented in this report. For the mentoring programme, we have integrated a blend of e-learning with interactive mentorship to offer a dynamic, tailored learning experience. The programme's first implementation took place during the Kick-Off Meeting on the 17th of October 2023.

The execution of the programme followed three distinct phases. In the first phase, the mentees were provided with three training videos for each module and had the opportunity to test their understanding of the content through quizzes. In the second phase, an online workshop, Q&A session and individual mentoring sessions were provided to the mentees. Lastly, in the third phase, a reflection session was held in all modules with the mentees. The structure, goal, content and results for each of these phases are provided in this report for all mentoring modules.

During the reflection session for Cohort 1, Fraunhofer IPK collected the feedback from the mentees to derive measures to improve the programme. The feedback collection covered the following topics: Reflection on the Mentoring Journey, Overcoming Obstacles and Developing Skills, Business Model Evaluation, Progress and Future Goals, Learning from the Community, Overall Satisfaction with the Mentoring Programme and Modules and Technical, Organisational Feedback and Closing thoughts. For Cohort 2 & 3 a questionnaire was used to gather feedback. Across all mentoring modules, the participants indicate a high level of satisfaction. However, some measures were derived to improve the mentoring experience for future cohorts. These measures include: Develop clearer guidelines on the sequence and interplay of different module, Tailor Modules to the participants' readiness level, implement a streamlined unified scheduling process, expand the curriculum to include modules on HR Management and Leadership, explore opportunities to enhance user interaction and ease of accessing materials on the mentoring platform. If possible, extend the time between modules to accommodate the participant's schedule and make as much material available to the participants to review it on their own time.

The second Cohort, consisting of four teams from the Greek Hackathon and one team from the previous Hackathon in Rimini, Italy, convened for its Kick-off meeting on January 23, 2024. Further, the third Cohort consisting of five teams from the Bulgarian Hackathon kicked-off on the 22nd of April 2024. The mentoring programme for Cohort 2 & 3 closely follows the

structure of the first cohort, with adjustments made based on the feedback from Cohort 1. Thus, this deliverable 4.5 illustrates the mentoring process for all three Cohorts and highlights the feedback from mentoring programme participants and derived measurements and therefore represents the continuation of the deliverable 4.2. Hence, the result of the mentoring programme are expressed leading the following KPIs: (1) 12 teams defined their business model during the mentoring programme (2) 9 teams developed a business plan at the European level (3) 10 teams applied to one or more Regional initiatives and/or European financial support instruments (4) 12 teams defined a pitch presentation and identified investor events (5) 7 teams identified and enrolled in further acceleration programmes at regional, national or European level

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1 INTRODUCTION OF THE MENTORING PROGRAMME REPORT

This section introduces the ENTREPRENEDU Project and its objectives. Further, the structure and the purpose of this report are highlighted.

The concept of ENTREPRENEDU is focused on closing the innovation and educational gap between different regions of the EU. One important tool to do so is the creation of a highly replicable and scalable Venture Building Programme, an educational model for the European entrepreneurial ecosystems that will be validated at the end of the project in 3 different educational entities.

The foundation for the Venture Building Programme will be laid by a mentoring programme that takes in the 12 teams and start-ups selected during three Hackathons in low to medium innovation countries of Greece, Italy and Bulgaria. At each Hackathon, different teams and start-ups compete to deliver solutions for pressing issues in the European Union. The four most promising ideas at each Hackathon will be selected and take part in the ENTREPRENEDU mentoring programme as a cohort.

This report aims to highlight the structure and implementation of the ENTREPRENEDU mentoring programme. Further, it is reported on the mentoring activities and the mentee participation in detail. Additionally, feedback from mentees and mentors is processed and actions for improvement are derived. The report fully covers the execution of the mentoring programme for Cohort 1, 2 & 3. This report is structured as follows: Subsequently to this introduction, chapter 2 provides an overview of the structure of the mentoring programme. Chapter 3 describes how the mentoring programme was executed. In chapter 4, an overview of the mentoring activities and results of Cohort 1, 2 & 3 is provided. Further, the feedback of the mentees and mentors is discussed and suggestions for improvement are provided. Chapter 5 illustrates the results and KPIs of the mentoring programme. Moreover, chapter 6 concludes this report. Lastly, the appendix provides a detailed overview of the scheduled mentoring slots and the survey which was conducted to gather feedback from Cohorts 2 and 3.

2 STRUCTURE OF THE MENTORING PROGRAMME

This section describes the nature and overall structure of the mentoring programme and discusses its distinct phases. The programme follows a blended learning approach that combines live mentoring and interaction with E-Learning to create a transformative educational journey for its participants.

Figure 1 illustrates the various stages, depth of learning, and content framework of the mentoring programme. This structure was crafted based on insights derived from a demand analysis which was executed with the mentees of cohort 1. Findings revealed that teams and startups are dispersed across different regions in Italy, with varying levels of expertise. As a

result, a blended learning approach allows participants to engage from their respective locations and accommodate their diverse skill sets.

The initial phase, characterised by systematic preparation, involves standardised content delivery aimed at imparting fundamental knowledge through online mediums such as webinars and training videos. This content remains consistent across all participants in the inaugural cohort and includes rudimentary assessment measures, potentially in the form of quizzes.

Moving to the second phase, emphasis shifts towards tailored development, offering more advanced learning opportunities that cater to individual needs. This stage unfolds in a live mentoring environment, fostering interaction between mentors and participants. Workshops, Q&A sessions, and one-on-one mentorship are all viable formats during this phase.

Lastly, the closing phase centres on reflection and feedback. Participants connect with their mentor for a final evaluation of their progress, development, and goal achievements.

FIGURE 1: Blended Learning Structure

Table 1 offers a detailed overview of the mentoring programme's three distinct phases, outlining their respective mentoring units, components, objectives, as well as the duration and planned implementation dates, exemplary for Cohort 1. Phase one kicked off in October 2023, marking the programme's initiation. It spans four hours, providing participants with essential guidance and support to establish a robust foundation for their entrepreneurial endeavours.

Phase two, spanning from October 2023 to February 2024, constitutes the most extensive segment of the mentoring programme. Participants will engage in five hours of mentoring,

aimed at delving deeper into various aspects of their startup ventures, fostering comprehensive skill development and knowledge enhancement.

The final phase, slated for March 2024, encompasses a one-hour mentoring reflection session, representing the shortest duration among the three phases. In total, the mentoring programme will offer ten hours of valuable mentorship to each participant, aiming to maximise the potential of the first cohort of teams and startups and contribute to their long-term success.

Considering the involvement of six mentoring organisations, each startup within the first cohort is poised to benefit from a total of 60 hours of mentoring.

TABLE 1: Detailed view of the mentoring programme structure for Cohort 1

Phase	Mentoring Unit	Mentoring Element	Mentoring Objective	Duration	Dates (for Cohort 1)
Phase 1: Methodical preparation	Webinar / Training-Videos	Three consecutive webinar / training videos (Level 1-3)	Teaching the methodological basis	3h (1h each)	October 2023
	Learning success control	Quiz via online tool	Reflection and deepening of the acquired knowledge	1h	
Phase 2: Development phase	Workshop with guided Exercises (small group)	Interactive Workshop e.g. with whiteboard	Guided Peer learning (start-ups give each other feedback)	2h	October 2023 – February 2024
	Meet-the-Mentor / Q&A Session (small group)	Live session (small group)	Clarification of questions from the guided exercise	1h	
	Individual Mentoring Session	Live session (One-to-One)	Mentor supports identification of obstacles and in developing strategies to overcome them.	2h (2 Sessions à 1h)	
Phase 3: Closing phase	Reflection session (individual)	Live session (One-to-One)	Reflection on the development and progress of the mentee and the achievement of the goals.	1h	March 2024
				Total: 10h	

3 EXECUTION OF MENTORING PROGRAMME

This section outlines the implementation of the mentoring programme exemplary for Cohort 1, detailing the execution process of its various phases.

Based on a demand analysis, which was conducted with the participating mentees, the following mentoring modules have been defined for the mentoring programme:

- Mentoring Module 1: Business Model Development (Expert: Fraunhofer IPK)
- Mentoring Module 2: Crafting a Unique and Competitive Value Proposition (Expert: LUISS)

- Mentoring Module 3: Your Idea Pitch: from Tech Feasibility to Product Development (Expert: FEA)
- Mentoring Module 4: Investment Pitch and Quantifying Your Funding Needs (Expert: EBAN)
- Mentoring Module 5: Entrepreneurial Business Planning (Expert: Corallia)
- Mentoring Module 6: Access to Finance and Related Funding (Expert: Cleantech Bulgaria)

The mentoring programme for Cohort 1 commenced on October 17, 2023, for Cohort 2 on the 23rd of January 2024 and for Cohort 3 on the 22nd of April 2024 with a two-hour session attended by all mentors and representatives of the mentored teams. During these sessions, the mentoring programme was thoroughly explained, and each mentor provided an overview of their specific mentoring module's structure, goals, and requirements. Additionally, mentees were given the opportunity to ask questions and address any pressing issues. A Screenshot of the event for Cohort 1 is provided below.

FIGURE 2: Screenshot of the Kick-Off Meeting for Cohort 1

Subsequently, Cohort 1, 2 and 3 participants registered their startups on the F6S platform to access the dedicated mentoring pages per module. These pages contained “private groups” which served as hubs for sharing links to training videos and quizzes, as well as enabling mentors to post announcements and communicate with mentees. These private groups were based to mentoring modules: [Business Model Development](#), [Crafting a Unique and Competitive Value Proposition](#), [Your Idea Pitch: from Tech Feasibility to Product Development](#),

[Investment Pitch and Quantifying Your Funding Needs](#), [Entrepreneurial Business Planning](#) and [Access to Finance and Related Funding](#). Further, a description of the overall module was highlighted on each individual mentoring page. The F6S platform also hosted the quiz formulas used by mentees to assess their understanding of the mentoring modules: Workshops, Q&A sessions, individual mentorship, and reflection sessions were conducted by mentors using their preferred online meeting tool for Cohort 1. For Cohort 2 and 3 the mentoring was facilitated on the same meeting tool for all sessions, which was a derived measure from the feedback of Cohort 1 participants. The coordination of these sessions was primarily facilitated by Fraunhofer IPK. Further, the publicly available mentoring videos were also uploaded on the European commission financed platform [Zenodo](#). The videos are there listed under the subject Mentoring Videos. However, the videos of the mentoring partner Corallia could not be shared, since they belong to their core entrepreneurial toolkit used for several services falling such as mentoring, consulting, and business acceleration programmes.

4 MENTORING ACTIVITIES FOR COHORT 1, 2 & 3

This section will provide detailed descriptions of various mentoring modules, focusing on the phases within each module. This will include discussions on training videos, quizzes, workshops, Q&A sessions, individual mentorship, and reflection sessions. The illustration will follow a logical sequence. Firstly, the structure of each mentoring element will be described. Secondly, the overarching goals of these elements will be explained. Thirdly, the actual mentoring content provided will be illustrated. Finally, the outcomes of the mentoring elements and the participation of the mentees will be described. The detailed time-schedule for the mentoring is provided in the Appendix. This information will be provided for all three Cohorts of the mentoring programme. Hereby, Cohort 1 consist of the teams A, B, C, D Cohort 2 of team E, F, G, H, I, and Cohort 3 of team J, K, L, M, N, O, P and Q. Unfortunately, in Cohort 1 the teams A and D did not complete the full mentoring programme due to overlaps of the programme with their current job for team A and team D's decision to no longer continue with the business in its current form. However, the teams completed the training session videos and partially the other stages of the programme. Therefore, teams B and C of Cohort 1 completed the whole mentoring programme.

To reach the KPI of 12 teams completing the mentoring programme, the decision was made by the consortium to commit a fifth team consisting of former members of the team D into Cohort 2. This was the team I, which completed the training session videos but unfortunately not the whole mentoring programme due to overlaps of the programme with their current job. Therefore, four teams of Cohort 2 namely E, F, G and H completed the whole mentoring programme.

To reach the KPI of 12 teams completing the mentoring programme, the decision was made by the consortium to select five teams for Cohort 3 from the Hackathon in Sofia. Unfortunately, team Q did not begin with the mentoring programme, since they conveyed to the consortium that they are too occupied with running their respective business. Moreover, Cleantech Bulgaria initiated on numerous occasions contact with team P, but despite the efforts to

motivate them, they decided to not continue with the programme after the training video sessions. Further, the team M did not complete the mentoring programme, since the team was resolved during the run time of the mentoring programme and dropped out after the workshop sessions. The teams J and K completed the programme. To replace the teams that did not finish the mentoring programme, the partner Cleantech Bulgaria contacted the runner-ups of the Hackathon in Sofia. Three of the runner-ups were subsequently onboarded to the mentoring programme, namely team L, N and O. Unfortunately, team O was not able to complete the programme due to overlaps of the programme with their current occupation. However, the team took part in some individual mentoring sessions. Therefore, four teams of Cohort 3 namely J, K, L and N completed the whole mentoring programme. Leading to ten teams completing the full mentoring programme. To combat the exit of some of the teams, the consortium decided to offer additional mentoring sessions to the teams still active in the programme. If a team decided, more mentoring is feasible, they were able to contact the mentor and set up future sessions.

4.1 FRAUNHOFER IPK – BUSINESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT

TRAINING VIDEOS

STRUCTURE	THE TRAINING VIDEOS SERVE AS THE INITIAL MENTORING ELEMENT, WITH EACH OF THE THREE VIDEOS LASTING ABOUT ONE HOUR, A TOTAL OF APPROXIMATELY THREE HOURS OF VIDEO MATERIAL IS PROVIDED. THE MENTORS PRE-RECORD THE VIDEOS, WHICH ARE THEN LINKED TO ON THE F6S PLATFORM.
GOAL	THE TRAINING VIDEOS AIM TO INTRODUCE THE MENTEES INTO THE TOPIC OF THE MODULE AND PROVIDE THEM WITH A BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF THE ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF THE MODULE. THE FIRST VIDEO SERVES AS AN INTRODUCTORY SESSION TO THE TOPIC OF THE MENTORING MODULE. THE SECOND VIDEO DELVES DEEPER INTO THE MODULE'S TOPICS, WHILE THE FINAL VIDEO FOCUSES ON THE MOST COMPLEX ASPECTS COVERED IN THE MENTORING MODULE.
CONTENT	VIDEO 1: IN THE VIDEO, A FUNDAMENTAL UNDERSTANDING OF BUSINESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT IS PROVIDED. IT IS EXPLAINED THAT IT'S NOT JUST ABOUT UNDERSTANDING ONE'S PRODUCT OR SERVICE, BUT ALSO ABOUT UNDERSTANDING THE ECOSYSTEM IN WHICH THE FUTURE BUSINESS OPERATES. THE CHALLENGES FACED BY BUDDING ENTREPRENEURS AND THE IMPORTANCE OF FEEDBACK AND MENTORSHIP IN DEFINING A ROBUST BUSINESS MODEL ARE HIGHLIGHTED. BY THE END OF THE VIDEO, VIEWERS ARE SAID TO BE EQUIPPED WITH THE KNOWLEDGE TO START, REDEFINE, OR PIVOT THEIR CURRENT OR FUTURE BUSINESS MODEL TO BETTER ALIGN WITH THEIR BUSINESS GOALS.

FIGURE 3: Screenshot of the first training video by Fraunhofer IPK

VIDEO 2: THE VIDEO PROVIDES A DETAILED EXPLANATION OF THE BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS (BMC), AIMING TO OFFER AN ADVANCED UNDERSTANDING OF ITS ELEMENTS AND APPLICATION AS A TOOL. IT COVERS THE DEFINITION AND HISTORY OF THE BMC, INTRODUCES VARIOUS ADAPTATIONS, DISCUSSES ITS ELEMENTS IN DETAIL, AND PROVIDES EXAMPLES OF BMC APPLICATIONS

FIGURE 4: Screenshot of the second training video by Fraunhofer IPK

VIDEO 3: IN THE VIDEO, AN OVERVIEW IS GIVEN OF AN APPROACH TO CONTINUOUSLY ADAPT, DEVELOP, AND CHANGE A BUSINESS MODEL ACCORDING TO EXTERNAL AND INTERNAL DRIVERS. FOR THIS PURPOSE, A FRAMEWORK FOR STRATEGIC BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT IS INTRODUCED AND FILLED WITH PRACTICAL TOOLS AND TECHNIQUES TO ANALYSE INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL FACTORS AFFECTING THE BUSINESS MODEL, AS WELL AS TO DERIVE RELEVANT

ACTIONS TO SYSTEMATICALLY DEVELOP THE BUSINESS MODEL IN ORDER TO GROW AND SURVIVE AS A SUCCESSFUL COMPANY ON THE MARKET.

FIGURE 5: Screenshot of the third training video by Fraunhofer IPK

FOR **COHORT 1, 2 & 3** ALL THREE TRAINING VIDEOS HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTORING ORGANISATION AND HAVE BEEN CONSUMED BY THE MENTEES.

RESULTS

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 3H

QUIZ

STRUCTURE

ON THE F6S PLATFORM, A MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUIZ WAS IMPLEMENTED FOR EVERY MENTORING MODULE. THE AMOUNT OF QUESTIONS RANGED BETWEEN 24 AND 30. THE QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE THREE MENTORING VIDEOS. IT WAS ESTIMATED THAT THE COMPLETION OF ONE QUIZ TAKES ONE HOUR.

GOAL

THE QUIZ IS NON-MANDATORY BUT AIMS TO TEST THE MENTEES UNDERSTANDING OF MENTORING VIDEOS TO THEN FOCUS IN THE FOLLOWING MENTORING PROCESS ON AREAS WHERE THE PERFORMANCE IN THE QUIZ WAS LACKING.

CONTENT

THE QUIZ INCLUDES BOTH THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE CONTENT PRESENTED IN THE 3 VIDEOS OF THE MODULE. THE QUESTIONS ARE FORMED IN A WAY THAT MAKES IT EASY TO VERIFY WHETHER THE MENTEES HAVE INDEED WATCHED THE VIDEOS, AND TO IDENTIFY SPECIFIC AREAS ON WHICH THE TEAMS MAY NEED EXTRA CLARIFICATIONS.

RESULTS

FOR **COHORT 1** UNFORTUNATELY, NONE OF THE TEAMS COMPLETED THE QUIZ.

FOR **COHORT 2** THE QUIZ WAS COMPLETED BY TEAMS E, G, H.

FOR **COHORT 3** THE QUIZ WAS COMPLETED BY TEAMS J, K & M

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

WORKSHOP

STRUCTURE

THE WORKSHOP SESSION IS THE FIRST LIVE INTERACTION OF THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEES. THE SESSION IS HELD ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE WORKSHOP SESSION HAS A DURATION OF 2 HOURS AND IS OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES.

GOAL

IN THE WORKSHOP, THE DIFFERENT MENTEES CAN APPLY THE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS LEARNED IN THE TRAINING VIDEOS TO THEIR OWN BUSINESS ENDEAVOURS.

CONTENT

IN THIS SESSION, THE WHITEBOARD TOOL "CONCEPTBOARD" WAS USED TO SUPPORT THE MENTEES IN DEVELOPING THEIR OWN BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS (BMC). EACH TEAM HAD THEIR INDIVIDUAL VIRTUAL ROOM IN WHICH THE MENTORS PROVIDED SUPPORT. LATER ON, THE TEAMS PRESENTED THEIR STATUS OF THE BMC AND RECEIVED FEEDBACK FROM THE MENTORS AND THEIR PEERS. THIS PROCESS WAS CONDUCTED FOR COHORT 1, 2 & 3.

FOR **COHORT 1** ALL FOUR TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP AND A BMC HAS BEEN JOINTLY DEVELOPED WITH ALL TEAMS.

THE WORKSHOP FOR **COHORT 1** HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 01/12/2024.

FOR **COHORT 2** THE TEAMS E, F AND G PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP AND DEVELOPED THEIR BMC. TO PROVIDE THE OTHER TEAMS WITH THE CONTENT DISCUSSED IN THE WORKSHOP, THE SESSIONS WERE RECORDED AND SHARED ON THE F6S PLATFORM.

THE WORKSHOP FOR **COHORT 2** HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 13/02/2024.

FOR **COHORT 3** THE TEAMS J, K AND M PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP AND DEVELOPED THEIR BMC. TO PROVIDE THE OTHER TEAMS WITH THE CONTENT DISCUSSED IN THE WORKSHOP, THE RECORDED SESSIONS SESSION WAS SHARED ON THE F6S PLATFORM.

RESULTS

THE WORKSHOP FOR **COHORT 3** HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 27/05/2024.

FIGURE 6: Screenshot of the Results of the BMC Workshop

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

Q&A SESSION

STRUCTURE

THE Q&A SESSION WAS FACILITATED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE DURATION OF THE SESSION WAS 1 HOUR AND OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES TO ENTER AND ASK QUESTIONS ABOUT MENTORING RELATED TOPICS.

GOAL

THE Q&A SESSION AIMS TO PROVIDE THE MENTEES WITH AN OPPORTUNITY TO ASK QUESTIONS AND TO SOLVE DOUBTS RAISED FROM THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP.

CONTENT

DURING THE SESSION, A PARTICULAR FOCUS WAS PUT ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE BMC OF THE TEAMS. THE MENTORS PROVIDED SUGGESTIONS ON HOW TO OVERCOME SPECIFIC CHALLENGES. ALL MENTEES RECEIVED GUIDANCE TAILORED TO THEIR UNIQUE NEEDS. THIS PROCESS WAS CONDUCTED FOR COHORT 1, 2 & 3.

FOR **COHORT 1** ALL FOUR TEAMS ACTIVELY ENGAGED IN THE Q&A SESSION AND ASKED QUESTIONS.

THE SESSION HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 04/12/2024.

FOR **COHORT 2** ONLY THE TEAM F PARTICIPATED IN THE Q&A SESSION.

RESULTS

THE SESSION HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 04/12/2024.

FOR **COHORT 3** UNFORTUNATELY NONE OF THE TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE Q&A SESSION.

THE SESSION HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 04/06/2024.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

TWO INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR EACH TEAM, EACH WITH A DURATION OF ONE HOUR, WERE OFFERED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR, LEADING TO A TOTAL OF TWO HOURS OF MENTORING PER TEAM. IN THESE SESSIONS ONLY, THE MENTORS AND ONE TEAM ARE PRESENT TO FOCUS ON THEIR SPECIFIC NEEDS AND ISSUES.

GOAL

THE INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS PROVIDE PERSONALISED GUIDANCE TO EACH TEAM, HELPING THEM OVERCOME SPECIFIC OBSTACLES ENCOUNTERED DURING CRITICAL PHASES OF THEIR COMPANIES. THIS ASSISTANCE AIDS IN DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR THE FUTURE.

CONTENT

IN THE INDIVIDUAL SESSION, THE **BMC** OF THE TEAMS WAS REVIEWED AND COMPLETED. THE SESSIONS BEGAN WITH A THOROUGH REVIEW OF THE STARTUP'S CURRENT **BMC**. MENTORS AND MENTEES COLLABORATIVELY EXAMINED EACH COMPONENT OF THE CANVAS, FROM THE VALUE PROPOSITION TO CUSTOMER SEGMENTS, CHANNELS, REVENUE STREAMS, AND KEY ACTIVITIES. FURTHER, THE FOCUS WAS PLACED ON PROVIDING AND DISCUSSING FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PARTNERS THAT THE TEAM CAN APPLY TO THEIR **BMC**. WHERE GAPS WERE IDENTIFIED, MENTORS PROVIDED TARGETED ADVICE ON HOW TO ADDRESS THEM, ENSURING THAT BY THE END OF THE SESSION, EACH STARTUP HAD A COMPLETED **BMC** THAT WAS BOTH REALISTIC AND AMBITIOUS. A SIGNIFICANT PORTION OF THESE SESSIONS WAS DEDICATED TO EXPLORING AND SELECTING FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS THAT STARTUPS COULD INTEGRATE INTO THEIR **BMC**. THIS EXPLORATION WAS GUIDED BY THE MENTOR'S EXPERTISE IN IDENTIFYING PATTERNS THAT HAVE PROVEN SUCCESSFUL ACROSS VARIOUS INDUSTRIES AND HOW THEY COULD BE TAILORED TO THE TEAMS' SPECIFIC CONTEXT. DISCUSSIONS REVOLVED AROUND A RANGE OF INNOVATIVE BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS. THIS PROCESS WAS CONDUCTED FOR COHORT 1, 2 & 3.

FIGURE 7: Screenshot of the Results of the Individual Sessions by Fraunhofer IPK

Backwards				
Name of the Pattern	Description of the Pattern	Examples	Term/Synonym - Source	Sustainability aspect
Inclusive Sourcing (Inclusion and empowerment of disadvantaged suppliers)	Sustainable design of the supply chain, focusing on the integration, support and aggregation of regional farmers or producers rather than solely on the quality of the product. These are qualified through agricultural and economic advice, access to inputs and loans to reliable suppliers, which goes hand in hand with an image boost. Relates to the BMC Element: Key Partners and Key Activities Partners and Key Activities Search for Partners in the region that produce sustainable packaging.	Algeria, Interface, Jain Irrigation Systems, Novelis , Salala Rubber, Sylva Foods, Walmart, Woolworth South Africa	Inclusive Sourcing - Clinton und Whinston (2014); Smallholder Procurement - Jenkins et al. (2011)	social-economic
Knowledge as a Service (Knowledge-based services)	Informing, training and advising customers on the basis of industry-, problem- or target group-specific knowledge and experience. As a rule, this knowledge and experience is acquired through close cooperation with the target group or work in the respective industry. Relates to the BMC Element: Customer Relationships and potentially Value Proposition	Yester .	Expertise Broker - Zorn et al. (2014); Knowledge as a Service - Hurk et al. (2017)	Accumulating problem-specific know-how as a resource. This know-how is derived from affected persons' experiences and is used to educate, train, and help social target groups

FOR COHORT 1:

THE TEAM A COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT GET A RESPONSE. HENCE, THE TEAM A DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

THE TEAM B PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS AND FINALISED ITS BMC (08/01/2024 & 22/01/2024). FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE TEAM'S BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

RESULTS

THE TEAM C PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (16/01/2024 & 24/01/2024). AND FINALISED ITS BMC. FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE TEAM'S BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

THE TEAM D PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (15/01/2024 & 01/02/2024) AND FINALISED ITS BMC. FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE TEAM'S BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

FOR COHORT 2:

THE TEAM E PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS AND FINALISED ITS BMC (28/02/2024 & 04/03/2024). FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE TEAM'S BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

THE TEAM F PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS AND FINALISED ITS BMC (29/02/2024 & 14/03/2024). FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE TEAM'S BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

THE TEAM G PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS AND FINALISED ITS BMC (01/03/2024 & 07/03/2024). FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE TEAM'S BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

THE TEAM H PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS AND FINALISED ITS BMC (03/04/2024 & 11/04/2024). FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE TEAM'S BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

THE TEAM I COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE TEAM DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE TEAM, I DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

FOR COHORT 3:

THE TEAM J PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS AND FINALISED ITS BMC (18/06/2024 & 25/06/2024). FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE TEAM'S BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

THE TEAM K PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS AND FINALISED ITS BMC (18/06/2024 & 25/06/2024). FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE TEAM'S BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

THE TEAM L PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS AND FINALISED ITS BMC (25/06/2024 & 02/07/2024). FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE TEAM'S BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

THE TEAM M COMMUNICATED THAT THEIR BUSINESS HAD BEEN RESOLVED. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE TEAM DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE TEAM I DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

THE TEAM N PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS AND FINALISED ITS BMC (24/07/2024 & 29/07/2024). FURTHER, FITTING BUSINESS MODEL PATTERNS TO APPLY TO THE TEAM'S BUSINESS MODEL WERE DISCUSSED.

THE TEAM O PARTICIPATED IN THE FIRST SESSION AND INITIALLY FILLED OUT ITS BMC (10/07/2024). UNFORTUNATELY, THE TEAM COMMUNICATED DUE TO AN OVERLAP OF THE MENTORING PROGRAMME WITH THEIR CURRENT OCCUPATION, THEY WILL NOT BE ABLE TO CONTINUE WITH THE PROGRAMME.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

REFLECTION SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

A ONE-HOUR REFLECTION SESSION WAS OFFERED TO ALL MENTEES ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THIS SESSION FOCUSED ON PROVIDING FEEDBACK TO THE MENTEES AND MARKED THE END OF THIS MENTORING MODULE

GOAL

THE REFLECTION SESSION AIMS TO ENCOURAGE PARTICIPANTS TO PRACTISE SELF-ASSESSMENT AND REFLECTION, ENABLING THEM TO MONITOR THEIR PROGRESS, ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS, AND IDENTIFY AREAS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT.

CONTENT

IN THE REFLECTION SESSION, A GUIDED DISCUSSION BETWEEN THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEE TOOK PLACE. THE FOCUS WAS PUT ON REVIEWING THE BMC AND DEVELOPING ACTIONS TO IMPROVE THE TEAM IN THE FUTURE. THIS PROCESS WAS CONDUCTED FOR COHORT 1, 2 & 3.

FOR COHORT 1:

THE TEAM B PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 12/02/2024 AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT AND FITTING PATTERNS WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED.

THE TEAM C PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 14/02/2024 AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT AND FITTING PATTERNS WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED.

THE TEAM D PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 16/02/2024 AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT AND FITTING PATTERNS WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED.

FOR COHORT 2:

THE TEAM E PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 11/03/2024 AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT AND FITTING PATTERNS WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED.

THE TEAM F PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 21/03/2024 AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT AND FITTING PATTERNS WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED.

THE TEAM G PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 14/03/2024 AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT AND FITTING PATTERNS WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED.

RESULTS

THE TEAM H PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 03/04/2024 AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT AND FITTING PATTERNS WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED.

FOR COHORT 3:

THE TEAM J PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 02/07/2024 AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT AND FITTING PATTERNS WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED.

THE TEAM K PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 02/07/2024 AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT AND FITTING PATTERNS WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED.

THE TEAM L PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 09/07/2024 AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT AND FITTING PATTERNS WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED.

THE TEAM N PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 31/07/2024 AND THE OVERALL PROCESS OF THE BMC DEVELOPMENT AND FITTING PATTERNS WAS REVIEWED. FURTHER, THE OVERALL MENTORING PROCESS OF THE MODULE AND PROGRAMME WAS DISCUSSED AND FEEDBACK COLLECTED.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

4.2 LUISS - CRAFTING A UNIQUE AND COMPETITIVE VALUE PROPOSITION

TRAINING VIDEOS

STRUCTURE	<p>THE TRAINING VIDEOS SERVE AS THE INITIAL MENTORING ELEMENT, WITH EACH OF THE THREE VIDEOS LASTING ABOUT ONE HOUR, A TOTAL OF APPROXIMATELY THREE HOURS OF VIDEO MATERIAL IS PROVIDED. THE MENTORS PRE-RECORD THE VIDEOS, WHICH ARE THEN LINKED TO ON THE F6S PLATFORM</p>
GOAL	<p>THE TRAINING VIDEOS AIM TO INTRODUCE THE MENTEES INTO THE TOPIC OF THE MODULE AND PROVIDE THEM WITH A BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF THE ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF THE MODULE. THE FIRST VIDEO SERVES AS AN INTRODUCTORY SESSION TO THE TOPIC OF THE MENTORING MODULE. THE SECOND VIDEO DELVES DEEPER INTO THE MODULE'S TOPICS, WHILE THE FINAL VIDEO FOCUSES ON THE MOST COMPLEX ASPECTS COVERED IN THE MENTORING MODULE.</p>
CONTENT	<p>VIDEO 1: THE VIDEO EXPLORES PROBLEM VALIDATION, STRESSING ITS IMPORTANCE IN BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT. IT HIGHLIGHTS THE NEED TO UNDERSTAND AND VALIDATE THE PROBLEM STATEMENT BEFORE STARTING ANY ENTREPRENEURIAL OR PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT PROJECT</p> <p>VIDEO 2: THE VIDEO FOCUSES ON SOLUTION VALIDATION, EXPLAINING ITS SIGNIFICANCE, AND PROVIDING GUIDANCE ON HOW TO EXECUTE IT EFFECTIVELY. IT EMPHASISES WHY VERIFYING THE VIABILITY OF A SOLUTION IS CRUCIAL BEFORE MOVING FORWARD WITH ANY BUSINESS OR PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT ENDEAVOUR.</p> <p>VIDEO 3: THE VIDEO IS ABOUT CRAFTING A COMPELLING VALUE PROPOSITION, WHICH IS ESSENTIALLY A CLEAR STATEMENT THAT EXPLAINS THE BENEFITS OF YOUR PRODUCT OR SERVICE AND WHY IT'S VALUABLE TO CUSTOMERS. IT DIVES INTO WHY HAVING A STRONG VALUE PROPOSITION IS ESSENTIAL FOR ATTRACTING AND RETAINING CUSTOMERS IN TODAY'S COMPETITIVE MARKET.</p>
RESULTS	<p>FOR COHORT 1, 2 & 3 ALL THREE TRAINING VIDEOS HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTORING ORGANISATION AND HAVE BEEN CONSUMED BY THE MENTEES.</p> <p>TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 3H</p>

QUIZ

STRUCTURE	<p>ON THE F6S PLATFORM, A MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUIZ WAS IMPLEMENTED FOR EVERY MENTORING MODULE. THE AMOUNT OF QUESTIONS RANGED BETWEEN 24 AND 30. THE QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE THREE MENTORING VIDEOS. IT WAS ESTIMATED THAT THE COMPLETION OF ONE QUIZ TAKES ONE HOUR.</p>
GOAL	<p>THE QUIZ IS NON-MANDATORY BUT AIMS TO TEST THE MENTEES UNDERSTANDING OF MENTORING VIDEOS TO THEN FOCUS IN THE FOLLOWING MENTORING PROCESS ON AREAS WHERE THE PERFORMANCE IN THE QUIZ WAS LACKING.</p>
CONTENT	<p>THE QUIZ INCLUDES BOTH THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE CONTENT PRESENTED IN THE 3 VIDEOS OF THE MODULE. THE QUESTIONS ARE FORMED IN A WAY THAT MAKES IT EASY TO VERIFY WHETHER THE</p>

MENTEES HAVE INDEED WATCHED THE VIDEOS, AND TO IDENTIFY SPECIFIC AREAS ON WHICH THE TEAMS MAY NEED EXTRA CLARIFICATIONS.

FOR **COHORT 1** UNFORTUNATELY, NONE OF THE TEAMS COMPLETED THE QUIZ.

FOR **COHORT 2** THE QUIZ WAS COMPLETED BY TEAM E & G

FOR **COHORT 3** THE QUIZ WAS COMPLETED BY TEAM J, K & M.

RESULTS

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

WORKSHOP

STRUCTURE

THE WORKSHOP SESSION IS THE FIRST LIVE INTERACTION OF THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEES. THE SESSION IS HELD ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE WORKSHOP SESSION HAS A DURATION OF 2 HOURS AND IS OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES.

GOAL

IN THE WORKSHOP, THE DIFFERENT MENTEES CAN APPLY THE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS LEARNED IN THE TRAINING VIDEOS TO THEIR OWN BUSINESS ENDEAVOURS.

CONTENT

DURING THE WORKSHOP, A TOOL FOR PROBLEM VALIDATION WAS PRESENTED TO THE PARTICIPANTS OF **COHORT 1, 2 AND 3**. IT WAS DEMONSTRATED HOW THE TOOL FUNCTIONS, AND GUIDANCE WAS PROVIDED ON FILLING IN THE INITIAL HYPOTHESES TO BE TESTED IN THE MARKET. THE SESSION UTILISED THE SUPPORT OF THE **MENTI.COM** ONLINE PLATFORM.

THE WORKSHOP FOR **COHORT 1** HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE **22/11/2023**, TWO TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION.

RESULTS

THE WORKSHOP FOR **COHORT 2** HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE **16/02/2024**.

THE WORKSHOP FOR **COHORT 3** HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE **28/05/2024**, THREE TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

Q&A SESSION

STRUCTURE

THE Q&A SESSION WAS FACILITATED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE DURATION OF THE SESSION WAS 1 HOUR AND OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES TO ENTER AND ASK QUESTIONS ABOUT MENTORING RELATED TOPICS.

GOAL

THE Q&A SESSION AIMS TO PROVIDE THE MENTEES WITH AN OPPORTUNITY TO ASK QUESTIONS AND TO SOLVE DOUBTS RAISED FROM THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP.

CONTENT

THE WORK ON PROBLEM VALIDATION CARRIED OUT BY THE TEAMS OF **COHORT 1, 2 AND 3** DURING THE WORKSHOP SESSION WAS REVIEWED, AND ALL THEIR DOUBTS AND QUESTIONS WERE ADDRESSED. **NONE** OF THE TEAMS WERE ABLE TO CONCLUDE THE PROBLEM VALIDATION WITHIN THE FIRST SESSION, THEREFORE THE **Q&A** WAS FOCUSED ON

ADDRESSING QUESTIONS ON THE TOOL, DISCUSSING HOW TO IMPROVE THE INTERVIEWS AND HOW TO EVENTUALLY PIVOT

ALL TEAMS ACTIVELY ENGAGED IN THE Q&A SESSION AND ASKED QUESTIONS.

THE SESSION FOR **COHORT 1** HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 06/12/2023 WITH THE PARTICIPATION OF TWO TEAMS.

RESULTS

THE SESSION FOR **COHORT 2** HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 23/02/2024.

THE SESSION FOR **COHORT 3** HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 03/06/2024 WITH THE PARTICIPATION OF THREE TEAMS.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

TWO INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR EACH TEAM, EACH WITH A DURATION OF ONE HOUR, WERE OFFERED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR, LEADING TO A TOTAL OF TWO HOURS OF MENTORING PER TEAM. IN THESE SESSIONS ONLY, THE MENTORS AND ONE TEAM ARE PRESENT TO FOCUS ON THEIR SPECIFIC NEEDS AND ISSUES.

GOAL

THE INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS PROVIDE PERSONALISED GUIDANCE TO EACH TEAM, HELPING THEM OVERCOME SPECIFIC OBSTACLES ENCOUNTERED DURING CRITICAL PHASES OF THEIR COMPANIES. THIS ASSISTANCE AIDS IN DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR THE FUTURE.

CONTENT

IN THE INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR COHORT 1, 2 AND 3 THE PROBLEM VALIDATION PROCESS OF THE TEAMS WAS DISCUSSED.

FOR COHORT 1:

THE TEAM **A** COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT GET A RESPONSE. HENCE, TEAM **A** DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

RESULTS

THE TEAM **B** PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS **BMC (15/01/2024 & 22/01/2024)** AND BASED ON THE DISCUSSION OF THE PROBLEM VALIDATION PROCESS IT WAS DECIDED THAT THE TEAM WILL START ANOTHER ROUND OF PROBLEM VALIDATION WITH ANOTHER GROUP OF POTENTIAL CUSTOMERS.

THE TEAM **C** PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS **(10/01/2024 & 22/01/2024)** DURING WHICH THE PROBLEM VALIDATION, AND THE LACK OF ACCESS THE TEAM HAD TO THE INDUSTRY WERE DISCUSSED. FURTHER, ALTERNATIVE AVENUES TO CONTACT CUSTOMERS WERE SUGGESTED.

THE TEAM **D** COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE TEAM DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, TEAM **D** DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

FOR COHORT 2:

THE TEAM E PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (26/02/2024 & 04/03/2024). DURING THE SESSIONS, WE WORKED ON FINDING MANAGERS TO INTERVIEW, TO UNDERSTAND WHAT DISSATISFIED THEM ABOUT THE SOLUTIONS CURRENTLY AVAILABLE ON THE MARKET. HOWEVER, NO INTERVIEWS WERE ACTUALLY CARRIED OUT DURING THE MENTORING PROGRAMME.

THE TEAM F PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (26/02/2024 & 04/03/2024). TOGETHER WE REVIEWED THEIR PROBLEM VALIDATION CHART, AND COACHED THEM FOR INTERVIEWS.

THE TEAM G PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (29/02/2024 & 01/07/2024) ALBEIT WITH A LARGE TIME GAP BETWEEN THE TWO. TOGETHER WE REVIEWED THEIR PROBLEM VALIDATION CHART, AND COACHED THEM FOR INTERVIEWS.

THE TEAM H PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (22/04/2024 & 29/04/2024). THE TEAM EMBRACED THE PROBLEM VALIDATION TOOL AND FOLLOWED THE PROCESS VERY CAREFULLY. THEY CONDUCTED SEVERAL INTERVIEWS ON DIFFERENT CUSTOMER SEGMENTS. THEY HAD NOT COMPLETED THE VALIDATION BY THE TIME THE MENTORING PROGRAMME ENDED.

THE TEAM I PARTICIPATED IN ONLY ONE SESSION (26/02/2024) THEY HOWEVER MANAGED TO CONDUCT INTERVIEWS AND BASED ON THE RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS IN THE MENTORING SESSION, ULTIMATELY DECIDED WHICH PRODUCT NICHE TO FOCUS ON TO START THEIR BUSINESS. THEY THEN COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE TEAM DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THEY DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

FOR COHORT 3:

THE TEAM J PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (10/06/2024 & 20/06/2024). THEIR MAIN ISSUE CONCERNED THE IDENTIFICATION OF BOTH THE CUSTOMER SEGMENT AND THE REAL ISSUE THEY WERE FACING. DURING THE MENTORING PROCESS THEY MANAGED TO GAIN MORE PRECISION ON THEIR TARGET NICHE AND THEY STARTED ACQUIRING MORE CONTACTS FOR FURTHER INTERVIEW ROUNDS.

THE TEAM K PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (17/06/2024 & 24/06/2024). THE SESSIONS CONCENTRATED MOSTLY ON SUPPORTING THEM IN FINDING POTENTIAL INTERVIEWEES FOR THEIR B2B IDEA, TRYING TO FIND ALTERNATIVES TO VERY LARGE MULTINATIONAL COMPANIES THEY HAD IN MIND.

THE TEAM L PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (26/06/2024 & 17/07/2024). THEY FOCUSED ON A NEW PRODUCT THEY WANTED TO INTRODUCE INTO THE MARKET AND STARTED WITH SOME INTERVIEWS. WE DISCUSSED HOW THEY COULD FURTHER TAILOR THEIR QUESTIONS TO VALIDATE THE PROBLEM.

THE TEAM M COMMUNICATED THAT THEIR BUSINESS HAD BEEN RESOLVED. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE TEAM DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE TEAM DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

THE TEAM N PARTICIPATED IN ONE SESSION (16/07/2024). THEY HAD ALREADY CONDUCTED A PROBLEM VALIDATION WHEN THEY JOINED THE SESSION, THEREFORE WE FOCUSED ON VALIDATING THE OFFER SIDE OF THE PLATFORM, TO FIND WINNING POINTS TO SCALE THE ONBOARDING OF THE TEACHERS ON THE PLATFORM. THE VALIDATION WAS STILL ON-GOING WHEN THE PROGRAMME ENDED.

THE TEAM O PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (10/07/2024 & 17/07/2024). BASED ON THE INTERVIEWS THEY CARRIED OUT, THEY IDENTIFIED SEVERAL CUSTOMER SEGMENTS THAT COULD BE INTERESTING TO FURTHER INTERVIEW, AND THUS PROCEEDED WITH A FURTHER ROUND OF INTERVIEWS.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

REFLECTION SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

A ONE-HOUR REFLECTION SESSION WAS OFFERED TO ALL MENTEES ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THIS SESSION FOCUSED ON PROVIDING FEEDBACK TO THE MENTEES AND MARKED THE END OF THIS MENTORING MODULE

GOAL

THE REFLECTION SESSION AIMS TO ENCOURAGE PARTICIPANTS TO PRACTISE SELF-ASSESSMENT AND REFLECTION, ENABLING THEM TO MONITOR THEIR PROGRESS, ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS, AND IDENTIFY AREAS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT.

CONTENT

THE REFLECTION WAS HELD ON THE BASIS OF THE WORK PERFORMED ON THE PROBLEM VALIDATION TOOL. THE OVERALL INFORMATION GATHERED WAS ANALYSED AND STARTUPS WERE COACHED THROUGH THINKING ABOUT WHAT THE INFORMATION IMPLIED FOR THEIR BUSINESS.

FOR COHORT 1:

THE TEAM C PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 05/02/2024.

THE TEAM B PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 13/02/2024.

BOTH STARTUPS ULTIMATELY REORIENTED THEIR BUSINESS OFFERING AS A RESULT OF THE INFORMATION THEY GATHERED: TEAM C CHANGED THEIR TARGET MARKET AND TEAM B CHANGED THE PROBLEM THEY WOULD LIKE TO ADDRESS.

FOR COHORT 2:

THE TEAM E PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 20/03/2024.

THE TEAM F PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 13/03/2024.

THE TEAM G PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 01/07/2024.

THE TEAM H PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 06/05/2024.

RESULTS

ALL TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN A FINAL REFLECTION ON THEIR JOURNEY THROUGH THE PROBLEM VALIDATION, IDENTIFYING WHAT THE RESULTS MEANT FOR THEM. ALL TEAMS HAD THE NECESSITY OF PROCEEDING WITH FURTHER INTERVIEWS.

FOR COHORT 3:

THE TEAM J PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 27/06/2024.

THE TEAM K PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 01/07/2024.

THE TEAM L PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 24/07/2024.

THE TEAM N PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 23/07/2024.

THE TEAM O PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 24/07/2024.

ALL TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN A FINAL REFLECTION ON THEIR JOURNEY THROUGH THE PROBLEM VALIDATION, IDENTIFYING WHAT THE RESULTS MEANT FOR THEM. ALL TEAMS SAW THE NECESSITY OF PROCEEDING WITH FURTHER INTERVIEWS, HOWEVER L MANAGED TO HAVE A PRELIMINARY VALIDATION OF THE PROBLEM, AND O WAS ABLE TO PINPOINT SOME USER GROUPS WITH THE GREATEST NEEDS IN RELATION TO THEIR SOLUTION.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

4.3 FONDAZIONE E. AMALDI - YOUR IDEA PITCH: FROM TECH FEASIBILITY TO PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT

TRAINING VIDEOS

STRUCTURE

THE TRAINING VIDEOS SERVE AS THE INITIAL MENTORING ELEMENT, WITH EACH OF THE THREE VIDEOS LASTING ABOUT ONE HOUR, A TOTAL OF APPROXIMATELY THREE HOURS OF VIDEO MATERIAL IS PROVIDED. THE MENTORS PRE-RECORD THE VIDEOS, WHICH ARE THEN LINKED TO THE F6S PLATFORM

GOAL

THE TRAINING VIDEOS AIM TO INTRODUCE THE MENTEEES INTO THE TOPIC OF THE MODULE AND PROVIDE THEM WITH A BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF THE ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF THE MODULE. THE FIRST VIDEO SERVES AS AN INTRODUCTORY SESSION TO THE TOPIC OF THE MENTORING MODULE. THE SECOND VIDEO DELVES DEEPER INTO THE MODULE'S TOPICS, WHILE THE FINAL VIDEO FOCUSES ON THE MOST COMPLEX ASPECTS COVERED IN THE MENTORING MODULE.

VIDEO 1: THE VIDEO FOCUSES ON THE "TECHNOLOGICAL FEASIBILITY" AND HAS THE AIM TO PROVIDE STUDENTS OR ASPIRING ENTREPRENEURS A PRELIMINARY BUT COMPREHENSIVE UNDERSTANDING ABOUT HOW TO DESIGN AND PERFORM A TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY STUDY. PRACTICAL TIPS, EXPLANATION OF METHODOLOGIES, EXAMPLES AND THEORETICAL REFERENCES ARE PROVIDED.

FIGURE 8: Screenshot of the first training video by Fondazione E. Amaldi

CONTENT

VIDEO 2: THE VIDEO FOCUSES ON "YOUR IDEA PITCH: FROM TECH FEASIBILITY TO PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT". THE OBJECTIVE OF THE VIDEO IS TO PROVIDE PARTICIPANTS A PRELIMINARY BUT COMPREHENSIVE EXPLANATION ABOUT HOW PRACTICALLY PUT THEM IN THE RIGHT ATTITUDE TO SOLVE COMPLEX PROBLEMS BY MEANS SOME OF THE MOST COMMON TOOLS OF THE DESIGN THINKING APPROACH: THE "PLANNING", THE "PROTOTYPING", THE "TESTING" AND THE "THINKING" ACTIVITY.

FIGURE 9: Screenshot of the second training video by Fondazione E. Amaldi

PLANNING

Funded by the European Union

2) Set objectives and activities: a) WBS

The Work Breakdown Structure

WBS answers to the question: What do we have to do ?
Graphical representation of the activities needed to reach the goals.
It is built on the basis of the hierarchy of the goals (upside down tree, similar to an organisational chart)

Main goal: Title of the project

Sub-objectives: Sub-objective, Sub-objective, Sub-objective

Activities: Activity, Activity, Activity

Tasks: Task, Task

Legend:

- Main information, no operative procedures
- Project manager and Project team leader
- Single manager

ENTREPRENEDEU is a project funded by the European Union under GA 101100502.

VIDEO 3: THE VIDEO FOCUSES ON “THE PITCH” AS AN EFFECTIVE MEANS TO PRESENT THE IDEA TO AN AUDIENCE. THE VIDEO EXPLAINS WHAT A PITCH IS, EXPLAINS THE DIFFERENT TYPOLOGIES OF PITCHES, PROVIDES SOME PRACTICAL TIPS TO PREPARE AND PERFORM WRITTEN AS WELL AS ORAL PITCHES.

FIGURE 10: Screenshot of the third training video by Fondazione E. Amaldi

THE SALES PITCH

Funded by the European Union

The Personas (tools)

Personalise

- Who are you talking to ?
- Make sure the pitch interests the interlocutor
- You can adapt it based on the aspects that are most interesting to different interlocutors

Interviews

Use cases

- How is the product used, where and by whom?
- What happens before and after use?
- How does the user get informations?
- How does the purchasing process take place?
- Who influences the decision?

Name

Description of the person
Age, gender, Place of residence, marital status, hobby, qualification, job position, social context, way of thinking, ecc...

Advantages

- To what extent do current products make the customer satisfied?

Difficulties

- What causes negative customer feelings about current products?
- What are the customer's concerns?

Stories

1) USER PROFILE CANVAS

ENTREPRENEDEU is a project funded by the European Union under GA 101100502.

RESULTS

FOR COHORT **1, 2, & 3** ALL THREE TRAINING VIDEOS HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTORING ORGANISATION AND HAVE BEEN CONSUMED BY THE MENTEES.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 3H

QUIZ

STRUCTURE

ON THE F6S PLATFORM, A MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUIZ WAS IMPLEMENTED FOR EVERY MENTORING MODULE. THE AMOUNT OF QUESTIONS RANGED BETWEEN 24 AND 30. THE QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE THREE MENTORING VIDEOS. IT WAS ESTIMATED THAT THE COMPLETION OF ONE QUIZ TAKES ONE HOUR.

GOAL	THE QUIZ IS NON-MANDATORY BUT AIMS TO TEST THE MENTEES UNDERSTANDING OF MENTORING VIDEOS TO THEN FOCUS IN THE FOLLOWING MENTORING PROCESS ON AREAS WHERE THE PERFORMANCE IN THE QUIZ WAS LACKING.
CONTENT	THE QUIZ INCLUDES BOTH THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE CONTENT PRESENTED IN THE 3 VIDEOS OF THE MODULE. THE QUESTIONS ARE FORMED IN A WAY THAT MAKES IT EASY TO VERIFY WHETHER THE MENTEES HAVE INDEED WATCHED THE VIDEOS, AND TO IDENTIFY SPECIFIC AREAS ON WHICH THE TEAMS MAY NEED EXTRA CLARIFICATIONS.
RESULTS	UNFORTUNATELY, NONE OF THE TEAMS OF COHORT 1 COMPLETED THE QUIZ. FOR COHORT 2 THE QUIZ WAS COMPLETED BY TEAM G & H. FOR COHORT 3 THE QUIZ WAS COMPLETED BY TEAM J & K. TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

WORKSHOP

STRUCTURE	THE WORKSHOP SESSION IS THE FIRST LIVE INTERACTION OF THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEES. THE SESSION IS HELD ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE WORKSHOP SESSION HAS A DURATION OF 2 HOURS AND IS OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES.
GOAL	IN THE WORKSHOP, THE DIFFERENT MENTEES CAN APPLY THE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS LEARNED IN THE TRAINING VIDEOS TO THEIR OWN BUSINESS ENDEAVOURS.
CONTENT	THE WORKSHOP ON "IDEA PITCH AND PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT" WITH GUIDED EXERCISES AIMED TO TRANSLATE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS FROM VIDEO LECTURES INTO PRACTICAL SKILLS FOR EFFECTIVELY COMMUNICATING A BUSINESS IDEA AND DRAFTING A PRODUCT OR SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PLAN. IT PROVIDED PRACTICAL HINTS AND TIPS ON VARIOUS TYPES OF PITCHES FOR DIFFERENT SITUATIONS, ALONG WITH EXAMPLES ON INITIATING A PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT PLAN. THE WORKSHOP REFERRED TO THE 'DESIGN THINKING APPROACH' AND ADVISED ON TYPICAL TOPICS TO CONSIDER FOR DRAFTING AN EFFECTIVE AND COHESIVE TECHNOLOGY-BASED PRODUCT OR SERVICE DEVELOPMENT PLAN. ADDITIONALLY, TEMPLATES AND TOOLS WERE PROVIDED TO FACILITATE THE PROCESS. THIS PROCESS WAS CONDUCTED FOR COHORT 1, 2 & 3.
RESULTS	ALL THE TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP AND UNDERSTOOD ITS CONTENT. THE WORKSHOP FOR COHORT 1 HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 21/11/2023; THREE OUT OF FOUR COMPANIES WERE PRESENT IN THE LIVE WORKSHOP, WHILE ONE COMPANY COULD NOT ATTEND BUT ENJOYED THE RECORDED VIDEO OF THE WORKSHOP. THE WORKSHOP FOR COHORT 2 HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 14/02/2024; THREE OUT OF FOUR COMPANIES WERE PRESENT IN THE LIVE WORKSHOP, WHILE ONE COMPANY COULD NOT ATTEND BUT ENJOYED THE RECORDED VIDEO OF THE WORKSHOP. THE WORKSHOP FOR COHORT 3 HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 29/05/2024; THREE OUT OF FIVE COMPANIES WERE PRESENT IN THE LIVE WORKSHOP WHILE TWO COMPANIES DID NOT ATTEND BECAUSE THEY ENGAGED AFTER THE RENUNCIATION OF TWO STARTUPS, BUT THEY ENJOYED THE RECORDED VIDEO OF THE WORKSHOP. TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

Q&A SESSION

STRUCTURE

THE Q&A SESSION WAS FACILITATED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE DURATION OF THE SESSION WAS 1 HOUR AND OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES TO ENTER AND ASK QUESTIONS ABOUT MENTORING RELATED TOPICS.

GOAL

THE Q&A SESSION AIMS TO PROVIDE THE MENTEES WITH AN OPPORTUNITY TO ASK QUESTIONS AND TO SOLVE DOUBTS RAISED FROM THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP.

CONTENT

DURING THE SESSION, A QUICK SUMMARY OF THE MAIN TOPICS EXPLAINED IN THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP WAS PROVIDED. THIS WAS FOLLOWED UP BY ANSWERING QUESTIONS OF THE MENTEES RELATED TO GENERAL TOPICS, PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT AND PARTICULAR COMPANY IDEAS AND PLANS. THIS PROCESS WAS CONDUCTED FOR COHORT 1, 2 & 3.

RESULTS

THE Q&A SESSION FOR **COHORT 1** HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 12/12/2023; THREE OUT OF FOUR COMPANIES WERE PRESENT IN THE LIVE Q&A SESSION, WHILE ONE COMPANY COULD NOT ATTEND. THE SESSION FOR **COHORT 2** HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 21/02/2024; THREE OUT OF FOUR COMPANIES WERE PRESENT IN THE LIVE Q&A SESSION, WHILE ONE COMPANY COULD NOT ATTEND. THE SESSION FOR **COHORT 3** HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 05/06/2024; THREE OUT OF FIVE COMPANIES WERE PRESENT IN THE LIVE Q&A SESSION, WHILE TWO COMPANIES DID NOT ATTEND BECAUSE THEY ENGAGED AFTER THE RENUNCIATION OF TWO OF THE INITIALLY SELECTED TEAMS.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

TWO INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR EACH TEAM, EACH WITH A DURATION OF ONE HOUR, WERE OFFERED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR, LEADING TO A TOTAL OF TWO HOURS OF MENTORING PER TEAM. IN THESE SESSIONS ONLY, THE MENTORS AND ONE TEAM ARE PRESENT TO FOCUS ON THEIR SPECIFIC NEEDS AND ISSUES.

GOAL

THE INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS PROVIDE PERSONALISED GUIDANCE TO EACH TEAM, HELPING THEM OVERCOME SPECIFIC OBSTACLES ENCOUNTERED DURING CRITICAL PHASES OF THEIR COMPANIES. THIS ASSISTANCE AIDS IN DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR THE FUTURE.

CONTENT

THE INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR COHORT 1, 2 AND 3 CAN COVER A RANGE OF TOPICS, DEEPENING ON THE MENTEE'S NEEDS. THEY CAN FOCUS ON PRACTICAL ADVICE TO IMPROVE THE CLARITY IN PRESENTING YOUR IDEA, THE EXPLANATION OF METHODOLOGIES TO IMPROVE THE PLANNING AND TESTING PROCESS OF THE COMPANY PRODUCT OR SUPPORTING TO PREPARE THE TEAM IN FUTURE MEETINGS WITH POTENTIAL INVESTORS.

FOR COHORT 1:

RESULTS

THE TEAM A COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT GET A RESPONSE. HENCE, THE TEAM A DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

THE TEAM B PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (17/01/2024 AND 24/01/2024) DURING WHICH THE STARTUP REVIEWED ITS PRESENTATION WITH THE MENTOR, TRYING TO PROPOSE ALTERNATIVE WAYS TO CONSIDER THE IDENTIFIED STAKEHOLDERS (CUSTOMERS, USERS, COMPETITORS, ETC.). THE INDIVIDUAL SESSION HAS BEEN FOCUSED ON THE IN-DEPTH EXPLANATION OF SPECIFIC TOPICS OF THE "PITCH", IN PARTICULAR, WHICH KIND OF PITCH IS MORE SUITABLE IN CASE OF A PRESENTATION TO POTENTIAL INVESTORS AND TO POTENTIAL CUSTOMERS. THE MENTOR HAS SUGGESTED TIPS ABOUT HOW TO PREPARE AND PERFORM AN INVESTOR DECK, ESPECIALLY IN WRITTEN FORM, USING AN APPROPRIATE STRUCTURE. DIFFERENCES BETWEEN CUSTOMERS AND STAKEHOLDERS HAS BEEN EXPLAINED; A REVIEW ABOUT THE FINANCIAL FORECAST HAS BEEN REQUESTED AND SUGGESTIONS PROVIDED TO BETTER PRESENT FINANCIAL FORECASTS.

THE TEAM C PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (16/01/2024 AND 23/01/2024) DURING WHICH THE STARTUP REVIEWED ITS PRESENTATION WITH THE MENTOR, TRYING TO BETTER EXPLAIN THEIR BUSINESS PROPOSITION AND PRICING MODEL. THE TEAM ALSO TRIED TO BETTER IDENTIFY THE POTENTIAL CUSTOMERS AND INVESTORS. THE INDIVIDUAL SESSION HAS BEEN FOCUSED ON THE IN-DEPTH EXPLANATION OF SPECIFIC TOPICS OF THE "PITCH", IN PARTICULAR, HIGHLIGHTING DIFFERENCES BETWEEN SALES PITCH AND INVESTOR DECK, EXPLAINING STRATEGIES TO PERFORM AD HOC PRESENTATIONS OF THE IDEA BASED ON DIFFERENT KINDS OF AUDIENCES. A REVIEW OF THE PRESENTATION OF THE STARTUP HAS BEEN PERFORMED BY THE MENTOR, PROVIDING TIPS TO TRANSFORM IT INTO AN INVESTOR DECK, WORKING ESPECIALLY ON THE FINAL PART, NOT PROVIDED BY FINAL CONCLUSIONS AND REQUESTS.

THE TEAM D COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE TEAM DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE TEAM D DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

FOR COHORT 2:

THE TEAM E PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (29/02/2024 AND 08/03/2024) DURING WHICH THE STARTUP ASKED TO BE EXPLAINED ABOUT HOW TO ENGAGE CUSTOMERS, ASKING IN PARTICULAR WHAT ARE THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN USERS AND CUSTOMERS. FURTHER EXPLANATIONS HAVE BEEN ASKED AS FAR AS THE FUND RAISING PROCESS IS CONCERNED. IN PARTICULAR, DIFFERENCES BETWEEN CALL FOR TENDERS, PUBLIC GRANT AND SEED/VENTURE CAPITAL HAVE BEEN EXPLAINED TO FIND OUT THE APPROPRIATE FUNDING SCHEME FOR THE STARTUP, IN THE SHORT AND IN THE MEDIUM TERM, IDENTIFYING A RELEVANT TOPIC FOR A PITCH DOCUMENT. THE FUNDING LOGICS OF PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS AND VENTURE CAPITAL HAVE BEEN EXPLAINED TO FOCUS ON PRESENTATIONS. THE STARTUP HAS ALSO REFLECTED ABOUT THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN COMPETITORS AND POTENTIAL PARTNERS TO BETTER SET UP ITS BUSINESS PROPOSITION IN THE PRESENTATIONS. IT HAS ALSO EXPRESSED THE NEED TO RECEIVE SUPPORT TO BETTER PRESENT ITS FINANCIAL FORECASTS.

THE TEAM F PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (01/03/2024 AND 08/03/2024) DURING WHICH THE STARTUP ASKED TO RECEIVE AN EXPLANATION ABOUT SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF THE DIFFERENT KINDS OF BUSINESS MODELS USED IN THE PROVISION OF SOFTWARE PLATFORMS AND SERVICES. TIPS AND SUGGESTIONS HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTOR TO IMPROVE THE WRITTEN AND ORAL PITCH, EXPLAINING STRATEGIES TO PERFORM AD HOC PRESENTATIONS OF THE IDEA ACCORDING TO DIFFERENT KINDS OF AUDIENCES. A FOCUS ON HOW TO BETTER IDENTIFY AND PRESENT THE CUSTOMER BASE, THE PRICING MODELS, THE FINANCIAL FORECASTING (REVENUES AND CASH FLOWS) HAS BEEN MADE. THE STARTUP HAS REVIEWED ITS PRESENTATION WITH THE MENTOR, TRYING TO BETTER EXPLAIN ITS BUSINESS PROPOSITION AND BUSINESS MODEL. IT ALSO TRIED TO BETTER IDENTIFY THE POTENTIAL CUSTOMERS AND INVESTORS. THE STARTUP HAS ALSO EXERCISED ON A FINANCIAL FORECAST TEMPLATE.

THE TEAM G PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (04/03/2024 AND 11/03/2024) DURING WHICH THE INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS HAVE BEEN FOCUSED ON THE IN-DEPTH EXPLANATION OF THE DIFFERENT KINDS OF PITCHES, FOCUSING ON SALES PITCH. AN EXPLANATION OF CRITICALITIES RELATED TO THE TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY STUDY AND TECHNICAL PLAN HAS BEEN PERFORMED WITH REFERENCES TO RISK ANALYSIS AND TESTING PHASES. THE STARTUP HAS REVIEWED ITS PRESENTATION WITH THE MENTOR, TRYING TO BETTER EXPLAIN ITS BUSINESS PROPOSITION AND BUSINESS MODEL. IT

ALSO TRIED TO BETTER IDENTIFY THE POTENTIAL CUSTOMERS AND INVESTORS. THE STARTUP HAS FURTHERMORE EXERCISED ON A FINANCIAL FORECAST TEMPLATE.

THE TEAM H PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (10/04/2024 AND 16/04/2024) DURING WHICH THE STARTUP ASKED AN EXPLANATION RELATED TO THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN USERS AND CUSTOMERS AS WELL AS INDICATIONS ABOUT HOW TO BALANCE THE TECHNOLOGY ASSESSMENT WITH THE COMMERCIAL VIABILITY OF THE COMPANY'S SOLUTIONS WITHIN A FEASIBILITY STUDY. FURTHERMORE, THE MENTORING HOURS HAVE BEEN FOCUSED ON HOW TO APPROACH A BUSINESS USE CASE TO PROPERLY IDENTIFY THE MARKET AND TO TEST A PROTOTYPE TAILORED ON SPECIFIC USER NEEDS. FINALLY, THE MENTORING SESSIONS HAVE REMINDED THE TIPS OF THE VIDEO ABOUT PITCHING AND PROVIDED SUGGESTIONS ABOUT HOW TO ASSESS, IN A TECHNOLOGY PLAN OR PROJECT, ITS ECONOMIC AND FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY, TAKING INTO CONSIDERATION THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN OPERATIVE AND CAPITAL COSTS, DIRECT AND INDIRECT COSTS. THE STARTUP HAS REFLECTED ABOUT WHAT IT HAS ALREADY DONE AND IT CAN SIMPLY DO TO DEVELOP ITS PRODUCTS, BY ITSELF OR IN COLLABORATION WITH ITS TECHNICAL PARTNER (UNIVERSITY) AND WHAT IT SHOULD DO TO ASSESS THE MARKET IN A REAL BUSINESS CASE (IDENTIFIED IN THE OIL-REFINERY COMPANIES USING FUEL CELLS). THE COMPANY HAS ALSO REFLECTED WITH THE MENTOR ABOUT ITS INTERNAL COST STRUCTURE AND ITS DYNAMICS TO PASS FROM A TECHNOLOGICAL FEASIBILITY TO A MARKET PHASE.

THE TEAM I PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (27/02/2024 AND 05/03/2024) DURING WHICH THE MENTOR HAS PROVIDED A PRACTICAL EXPLANATION OF SPECIFIC METHODS TO PRESENT AND MARKET THE IDEA AND THE SERVICE USING "PITCH" TEMPLATES BUT, MOST OF ALL, BY MEANS THE IDENTIFICATION OF STRATEGIES TO INVOLVE THE USER IN A WIN-WIN SITUATION; IDENTIFICATION OF THE BENEFITS AND POTENTIAL RETURNS FOR THE CUSTOMERS HAVE BEEN DISCUSSED AS EXAMPLE TO STRENGTHEN THE COMMERCIAL STRATEGY. THE TEAM HAS REVIEWED ITS PRESENTATION WITH THE MENTOR, TRYING TO PROPOSE ALTERNATIVE WAYS TO MARKET ITS IDEA (B2B MEETINGS, EXPLOITATION OF DIGITAL FUNDS TO PURCHASE DIGITAL SERVICES, ETC.).

FOR COHORT 3:

THE TEAM J PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (19/06/2024 AND 26/06/2024) DURING WHICH THE TEAM AND THE MENTOR PAID ATTENTION TO THE TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY PLAN. THE TECHNICAL CHALLENGES ARE IN FACT RELEVANT TO DEMONSTRATE THE FEASIBILITY OF THE IDEA. THUS, THE FEASIBILITY PLAN HAS BEEN EXPLAINED WITH PARTICULAR REFERENCE TO THE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN PoC AND INDUSTRIALIZATION PROCESS. FURTHERMORE, TIPS ON HOW TO DESIGN AND PRESENT A TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY STUDY HAVE BEEN PROVIDED. A FOCUS, AS REQUESTED BY THE TEAM, HAS BEEN MADE ON A TEMPLATE TO PERFORM A TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY STUDY CONTAINING TECHNICAL, IMPLEMENTATION, MANAGERIAL, AND FINANCIAL SECTIONS.

THE TEAM K PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (19/06/2024 AND 26/06/2024) DURING WHICH THE TEAM HAS PRESENTED THE PROJECT IDEA FOCUSING ON THE TECHNICAL PROBLEMS (E.G. SCARCITY OF DATA TO IMPLEMENT A.I. MODULE); A TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY SHOULD BE MADE TO MOVE ON, AS WELL AS AN ASSESSMENT RELATED TO THE BUSINESS MODEL (A STAND-ALONE SOLUTION VERSUS A SOLUTION INTEGRATED WITH THE PROVISION OF MULTI-SOURCES IMAGES). THE TEAM HAS REFLECTED THAT COMPLEMENTARY SKILLS NEED TO BE ADDED (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE EXPERTS, BUSINESS DEVELOPERS, AGRONOMISTS). TIPS ON HOW AND WHERE TO IDENTIFY THOSE EXPERTS AND FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTOR. ANOTHER FOCUS HAS BEEN MADE ABOUT TECHNIQUE AND TEMPLATE TO PERFORM A TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY STUDY. AN EXAMPLE TAKEN FROM THE BEST PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS PRACTICES WAS PROPOSED AS A GUIDELINE TO FOLLOW IN ORDER TO WRITE A TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY STUDY PROPOSAL COMPLETED WITH IMPLEMENTATION AND MANAGERIAL TOPICS. THE COMPANY REFLECTED THAT IT HAS TO STRENGTHEN THE COLLABORATION WITH TECHNICAL PARTNERS (UNIVERSITIES, LABORATORIES) AND TO INVOLVE THEM AS A LARGE TEAM TO DIFFERENTIATE ITS SERVICES; THIS CAN BRING TO THE ALTERNATIVE "CONSULTING" BUSINESS MODEL THAT COULD FIT WITH ITS SELF-SUSTAINMENT NEEDS OF THE SHORT TERM. THE COMPANY ALSO REFLECTED THAT OTHER CRITICAL POINTS TO WORK ON ARE: TO COMPLETE THE TEAM, TO OFFER AD HOC CONSULTING SERVICES TO PILOT CUSTOMERS, TO ELABORATE ON A BUSINESS PLAN TO CLEARLY IDENTIFY INVESTMENTS AND

TIMELINE FOR A FAST DEVELOP IN THE SHORT AND MEDIUM TERM, TO IDENTIFY PROPER SOURCE OF FUNDING (PUBLIC AND EQUITY CROWDFUNDING) BEFORE TO ENGAGE WITH VENTURE CAPITALISTS.

THE TEAM L PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (27/06/2024 AND 04/07/2024) DURING WHICH THE TEAM PRESENTED THE COMPANY THAT HAS BEEN ON THE MARKET FOR ONE YEAR. THE MENTORING HAS BEEN FOCUSED ON THE POSSIBILITY TO DEFINE THE UPSELLING STRATEGIES (DIFFERENTIATION OF SERVICES, INCREASE THE QUALITY USING BIO-PRODUCTS, ETC.) TO SCALE-UP THE BUSINESS AND TO IDENTIFY THE POSSIBLE CRITICAL POINTS IN THE SHORT AND MEDIUM TERM. THE TEAM AGREED THAT A POSSIBLE CRITICAL POINT IS THE PREPARATION OF A BUSINESS PLAN WITH A CREDIBLE GROWTH STRATEGY, ASSESSING HOW MUCH THE COMPANY IS SELF-STANDING FROM A FINANCIAL POINT OF VIEW AND THE ASSESSMENT OF THE POTENTIAL INVESTMENT AND MONEY TO ASK AN EXTERNAL INVESTOR. A SPECIFIC FOCUS HAS BEEN PROVIDED ON HOW TO IMPROVE THE PRESENTATION ALREADY PREPARED BY THE COMPANY TO FIT WITH CUSTOMERS AND INVESTORS' EXPECTATIONS. TIPS ON HOW TO MODIFY, IN GENERAL, THE PRESENTATION HAVE BEEN FORMULATED. A MORE PRECISE MARKET EVALUATION HAS TO BE PERFORMED, AS WELL AS A MORE PRECISE CASH REQUEST. AN OVERVIEW ABOUT THE POSSIBLE ALTERNATIVE FUNDING SOURCES (E.G. CROWDFUNDING) HAS BEEN BRIEFLY PROVIDED, IN CONSIDERATION OF THE MATURITY OF THE BUSINESS CASE. THE COMPANY HAS TAKEN INTO CONSIDERATION THE SUGGESTION RECEIVED AND TRIED TO ELABORATE ON A NEW PRESENTATION / PITCH.

THE TEAM M COMMUNICATED THAT THEIR BUSINESS HAD BEEN RESOLVED. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE TEAM DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE TEAM I DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

THE TEAM N PARTICIPATED ON IN SESSIONS ON THE 11/07/2024 AND 18/07/2024 DURING WHICH THE TEAM (FORMED BY THE PROMOTER OF THE STARTUP, WITH A DEGREE IN COMPUTER SCIENCES AND A BUSINESS DEVELOPER) PRESENTED THE PROJECT, A WEB PLATFORM / APPLICATION CONCEIVED TO INNOVATE THE EDUCATIONAL SCENARIO IN BULGARIA. THE PLATFORM, CURRENTLY UNDER DEVELOPMENT, WILL PROVIDE INNOVATIVE CONTENTS FOR CHILDREN, TEACHERS, PARENTS, OTHER STAKEHOLDERS AND USERS OF THE BULGARIAN EDUCATION SYSTEM, TO INCREASE THE QUALITY OF THE INTERACTIONS AND OF THE LEARNING PROCESS DURING THE EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES AS WELL AS DURING EVENTS FOR CHILDREN. THE MISSION OF THE COMPANY IS TO BRIDGE THE GAP BETWEEN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM AND INDUSTRY AND THE VALUES OF THE PLATFORM ARE ACCESSIBILITY, INCLUSION, ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY. THE PLATFORM PROVIDES PROPRIETARY CONTENTS AND RESOURCES BASED ON GAMIFICATION, ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, ROBOTICS FOR CHILDREN, ETC. AND THIS DIFFERENTIATION MAKES THE PRODUCT CUSTOMIZABLE FOR A BROAD RANGE OF USERS. THE TEAM IS STILL WORKING ON THE BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS AND CURRENTLY IT HAS IDENTIFIED DIFFERENT POSSIBLE BUSINESS MODELS (EVENTS AS A SERVICE, LICENSING, B2B CONTRACTS ETC.). THE BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS HAS BEEN PRESENTED AND THE MENTOR HAS PROVIDED SEVERAL TIPS ON HOW TO CORRECT IT AND TO IMPROVE. FURTHERMORE, DURING THE MEETINGS THE TEAM HAS RECOGNIZED SOME CRITICALITIES AND THE IMPORTANCE TO WORK ON SOME ISSUES: THE DISTINCTION OF USERS FROM CUSTOMERS (NOT STILL CLEAR BECAUSE OF THE MULTIPURPOSE AIMS OF THE BUSINESS), THE NEED TO BE MORE FOCUSED ON BUSINESS MODEL AND MARKETING; THE PERFORMANCE OF A TECHNICAL PLAN; THE IMPROVEMENT OF KNOWLEDGE AND EXPERTISE ABOUT FUNDING AND PITCHING; THE COMPLETION OF THE TEAM ENGAGING NEW PERSONS WITH COMPLEMENTARY SKILLS. PART OF THE MEETINGS HAS THEN BEEN DEDICATED TO HOW TO STRUCTURE A TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY PLAN, TO USE DIFFERENT KINDS OF PITCHES AND TO ASSESS AND QUANTIFY RESOURCES TO ASK INVESTORS AND TO CORRECT THE BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS.

THE TEAM O PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSIONS ON THE 11/07/2024 AND 18/07/2024 DURING WHICH THE TEAM PRESENTED THE IDEA TO DEVELOP AN APP FOR SMARTPHONES FOR RENTING OBJECTS IN THE SOFIA AREA. O IS AT THE VERY BEGINNING STAGE: A DEMO VERSION / PROTOTYPE OF THE APP DOES NOT STILL EXIST AND THE PROMOTER NEEDS TO UNDERSTAND IF THE IDEA IS FEASIBLE OR NOT. THE BUSINESS MODEL OF THE APP IS VERY SIMPLE AND ALREADY TESTED: PUT IN CONTACT THE OBJECTS' OWNER WITH PERSONS THAT NEED TO RENT THOSE OBJECTS. OTHER APPS EXIST, BUT THEY DON'T SEEM TO OPERATE IN BULGARIA. THE TEAM IS WORKING ON THE BUSINESS MODEL AND AT THE MOMENT AND IT HAS IDENTIFIED THE LIST OF ISSUES THAT SHE HAS TO BE FACED TO DESIGN AND BRING THE

IDEA TO A PROTOTYPE LEVEL: USER INTERFACE, BACK-END, DATA SECURITY, LEGAL FRAMEWORK ABOUT INFORMATION/GUARANTEES FOR USERS (CODE OF CONDUCTS, GUARANTEES TO MAINTAIN THE STATUS OF THE OBJECT DURING THE RENTING, ETC.), COMMUNICATION AND MARKETING, ETC. THE MEETING HAS BEEN FOCUSED ON THE SELECTION OF PRIORITIES TO ASSESS THE BUSINESS: A FEASIBILITY STUDY HAS BEEN IDENTIFIED AS ONE OF THE MAIN TASKS TO BE PERFORMED BY THE ENTREPRENEUR TO ASSESS THE SEVERAL ISSUES, TECHNICAL BUT ALSO MANAGERIAL ONES. TIPS ABOUT HOW TO INITIATE A FEASIBILITY STUDY AND TOPICS TO CONSIDER HAVE BEEN PROVIDED.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

REFLECTION SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

A ONE-HOUR REFLECTION SESSION WAS OFFERED TO ALL MENTEES ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THIS SESSION FOCUSED ON PROVIDING FEEDBACK TO THE MENTEES AND MARKED THE END OF THIS MENTORING MODULE

GOAL

THE REFLECTION SESSION AIMS TO ENCOURAGE PARTICIPANTS TO PRACTISE SELF-ASSESSMENT AND REFLECTION, ENABLING THEM TO MONITOR THEIR PROGRESS, ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS, AND IDENTIFY AREAS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT.

CONTENT

A REVIEW OF THE OVERALL MENTORING PATH HAS BEEN MADE, FOCUSING ON THE MAIN CRITICAL POINT ON THE BASE OF THE STARTUP SENSIBILITY. FUTURE PLANS HAVE ALSO BEEN ANALYSED. THIS PROCESS WAS CONDUCTED FOR COHORT 1, 2 & 3.

FOR COHORT 1:

RESULTS

TEAM B PARTICIPATED IN THE REFLECTION SESSION (21/02/2024). A REVIEW OF THE OVERALL MENTORING PATH HAS BEEN MADE, FOCUSING ON THE MAIN CRITICAL POINT ON THE BASE OF THE STARTUP SENSIBILITY: IN PARTICULAR, THE FINANCIAL FORECAST OF THE COMPANY AND METHODOLOGIES TO CALCULATE THE VALUE OF ENTERPRISES, IDENTIFIED AS MAIN WEAKNESS POINTS BY THE STARTUP. FUTURE PLANS HAVE ALSO BEEN PLANNED, WITH A DISCUSSION OF THE POTENTIAL FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE BACKWARDS STRATEGIES AND SERVICES, AT EUROPEAN AS WELL AS NATIONAL LEVEL. THE STARTUP HAS PROACTIVELY INTERACTED OPENLY SHARING CRITICAL POINTS AND NEEDS TO OVERCOME SOME MANAGERIAL ISSUES (E.G. CAPACITY TO PERFORM AND PRESENT FINANCIAL FORECASTS AND TO IDENTIFY FINANCIAL RESOURCES TO COVER INVESTMENTS AND COSTS).

TEAM C PARTICIPATED IN THE REFLECTION SESSION (19/02/2024). A REVIEW OF THE OVERALL MENTORING PATH HAS BEEN MADE, FOCUSING ON THE FINANCIAL FORECAST OF THE COMPANY AND METHODOLOGIES TO ENGAGE CUSTOMERS AND STAKEHOLDERS. THE SESSION HAS ALSO BEEN FOCUSED ON THE ASSESSMENT OF THE ORGANISATIONAL STRUCTURE OF THE TEAM, WHICH SEEMED LACKING ALL THE NECESSARY EXPERTISE TO LAUNCH THE SERVICE ON THE MARKET. THE STARTUP HAS INTERACTED WITH THE MENTOR, REFLECTING ABOUT THE MAIN CRITICAL ISSUE OF THE COMPANY: THE LACK OF A TEAM WITH ALL THE NEEDED SKILLS AND EXPERTISE (MARKETING) TO

IMPLEMENT THE PROJECT IDEA. THE STARTUP HAS AGREED ON THE NEED TO WORK ON THIS POINT BEFORE PERFORMING FURTHER COMMERCIAL ACTIVITIES.

FOR COHORT 2:

TEAM E PARTICIPATED IN THE REFLECTION SESSION (19/03/2024). A REVIEW OF THE OVERALL MENTORING PATH HAS BEEN MADE, FOCUSING ON THE MAIN CRITICAL POINT ON THE BASE OF THE STARTUP SENSIBILITY: THE TECHNOLOGICAL FEASIBILITY PLAN; A SUMMARY ABOUT BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT AND PITCHING TIPS HAS BEEN MADE. THE REFLECTION SESSION HAS BEEN FOCUSED ON THE MOST INTERESTING TOPICS FOR THE COMPANY (HOW TO PERFORM A TECH FEASIBILITY STUDY, THE IMPORTANCE OF SOME MANAGEMENT TOOLS TO CONTROL THE FEASIBILITY STUDY). A REFLECTION ABOUT THE INCREASED AWARENESS AND FUTURE PLANS HAS BEEN MADE. THE STARTUP HAS THOUGHT ABOUT THE MOST IMPORTANT TOPICS OF THE MENTORING PROGRAMME AND THE SPECIFIC NEEDS, UNDERSTANDING THE INTERNAL GAP OF THE TEAM EXPERTISE IS IMPACTING THE FUTURE PLANS. THE COMPANY HAS BECOME MORE AWARE TO IMPROVE MANAGEMENT (E.G. MANAGE THE SUB-CONTRACTING PROCESSES) AND MARKETING EXPERTISE TO PROCEED TOWARDS A MORE COMPREHENSIVE STRATEGY TO SUCCEED (IMPROVE MARKETING CAPACITY, BUSINESS PLANNING AND ASSESS FINANCIAL FORECASTING). THE COMPANY REFLECTED ON THE IMPORTANCE OF THE TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY PLAN VIDEO TO UNDERSTAND THE AIM OF THIS PHASE ALSO IN PREPARATION OF THE FUTURE DEVELOPMENT PLANS.

TEAM F PARTICIPATED IN THE REFLECTION SESSION (15/03/2024). A REVIEW OF THE OVERALL MENTORING PATH HAS BEEN MADE, FOCUSING ON THE COMMUNICATION SKILLS THAT STILL HAVE TO BE IMPROVED INSIDE THE TEAM, WHILE THE ASSESSMENT OF THE TECHNICAL TOPICS ARE QUITE WELL COVERED BY THE TEAM. IMPROVEMENT ABOUT COMMUNICATION IN THE MARKETING, PARTNERSHIPS, AND BUSINESS MODELLING STRATEGY HAS BEEN IDENTIFIED. THE STARTUP HAS REFLECTED ON THE INTERNAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS, IDENTIFYING THE HIGHEST VALUE OF THE MENTORING PROGRAMME ON THIS PARTICULAR POINT, DUE TO THE BACKGROUND OF THE FOUNDERS. FURTHER ADVICE ON HOW TO COMMUNICATE THE PRESENCE OF EVENTUAL PARTNERS TO BOOST THE MARKETING OF THE PRODUCTS HAS BEEN ASKED TO THE MENTOR.

TEAM G PARTICIPATED IN THE REFLECTION SESSION (28/03/2024). A REVIEW OF THE OVERALL MENTORING PATH HAS BEEN MADE, FOCUSING ON THE FINANCIAL FORECAST OF THE COMPANY AND METHODOLOGIES TO BETTER CALCULATE PROFIT AND LOSS AND CASH FLOW. THE SESSION HAS ALSO BEEN FOCUSED ON DIFFERENCES BETWEEN THE KIND OF COSTS TO CONSIDER TO ESTIMATE THE COST OF A PRODUCT. THE STARTUP HAS INTERACTED WITH THE MENTOR, REFLECTING ABOUT THE MAIN CRITICAL COST COMPONENT OF A PRODUCT AND HOW TO IDENTIFY THE PROPER PRODUCTS FOR THE DIFFERENT KINDS OF CUSTOMERS. FURTHERMORE, THE STARTUP HAS INTERACTED WITH THE MENTOR IDENTIFYING DIFFERENT KIND OF COSTS FOR ITS PRODUCT AND HOW TO PRESENT THEM IN A FINANCIAL FORECAST TOOL.

TEAM H PARTICIPATED IN THE REFLECTION SESSION (23/04/2024). A REVIEW OF THE OVERALL MENTORING MEETINGS HAS BEEN MADE, FOCUSING ON THE TECH FEASIBILITY TOPIC, THAT IS AT THE MOMENT THE MOST CRITICAL POINT FOR THE COMPANY, DUE TO THE KIND OF PRODUCT TO BE DEVELOPED (FUEL CELLS) THAT SEEMS TO HAVE SOME TECHNICAL CONSTRAINTS UNDER EVALUATION. FURTHER REVIEW ABOUT COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES HAVE BEEN MADE. THE STARTUP HAS PROACTIVELY INTERACTED OPENLY SHARING CRITICAL POINTS BY THE TECHNOLOGICAL POINT OF VIEW: PROBABLY IT WILL ASSESS IF A DIVERSIFIED APPROACH WILL BE APPROPRIATE, TARGETING ON SELLING THE SW COMPONENTS INSTEAD OF THE HW ONE (FUEL CELL) AFTER A PROPER TECHNICAL AND ECONOMIC ASSESSMENT. THE COMPANY WILL TRY TO PERFORM A PROPER TESTING PHASE INVOLVING NOT ONLY UNIVERSITY TEAM MEMBERS BUT ALSO FINAL USERS. THE COMPANY HAS ALREADY STARTED-UP TO EXERCISE ABOVE PRESENTATIONS TO IMPROVE COMMUNICATION AND ITS STRATEGY.

TEAM I UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT PARTICIPATE IN THE REFLECTION SESSION (SCHEDULED ON 27/03/2024) . NEVERTHELESS, EVEN IN THE ABSENCE OF THIS LAST SESSION THROUGH THE PREVIOUS TWO INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS, THEY STILL MANAGED TO DEFINE A FINAL PITCH PRESENTATION.

For COHORT 3:

TEAM J PARTICIPATED IN THE REFLECTION SESSION (02/07/2024). A REVIEW OF THE OVERALL MENTORING MEETINGS HAS BEEN MADE, FOCUSING IN PARTICULAR ON THE TECH FEASIBILITY TOPIC, THE MOST CRITICAL ISSUE FOR THE TEAM AT THE MOMENT. ANOTHER IMPORTANT REFLECTION HAS BEEN MADE ABOUT METHODOLOGIES TO MANAGE THE PROCESS TO DEVELOP THE PRODUCT, TAKING INTO CONSIDERATION REQUESTS OF A FULL ENGAGEMENT THE TEAM RECEIVED BY POTENTIAL PARTNERS. THE TEAM HAS PROACTIVELY INTERACTED WITH THE MENTOR ABOUT PROS (EXPERIENCE, POSITIVE PRELIMINARY FEEDBACK FROM POTENTIAL CUSTOMERS AND INVESTORS) AND CONS (LIMITED ENGAGEMENT, TEAM NOT COMPLETED). AN ASSESSMENT OF THE FUNDING SOURCES HAS BEEN MADE TO SUSTAIN THE SHORT TIME ACTIVITIES, AND AN OVERVIEW OF OTHER POTENTIAL FUNDING SOURCES HAS BEEN SUGGESTED BY THE MENTOR. THE TEAM ALSO REFLECTED ABOUT CONCEIVING AN ALTERNATIVE BUSINESS MODEL TO BALANCE TO SUCCEED AND PROACTIVE WAYS TO INVOLVE CUSTOMERS.

TEAM K PARTICIPATED IN THE REFLECTION SESSION (03/07/2024). A REVIEW OF THE OVERALL MENTORING MEETINGS HAS BEEN MADE, FOCUSING ON THE TECH FEASIBILITY TOPIC AS AN URGENT TASK TO BE PERFORMED. A REFLECTION ON STRENGTHS AND WEAKNESSES HAS BEEN MADE: THERE IS POSITIVE FEEDBACK ABOUT THE PRODUCTS, WHILE THERE ALSO IS A TEAM SKILL GAP THAT REMAINS CRITICAL. ANOTHER IMPORTANT REFLECTION HAS DEALT WITH THE POSSIBLE WAY TO UPGRADE THE SERVICES, USING ADDITIONAL DATA SOURCES (E.G. SATELLITE IMAGES) THAT CAN BRING MORE VALUE ADDED AND BROADEN THE OPPORTUNITY TO TARGET NEW CUSTOMERS AND GET FINANCING SOURCES. FUNDING WAS IDENTIFIED AS A CRITICAL POINT, AND AN OVERVIEW ABOUT PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SOURCES (ESPECIALLY CROWDFUNDING) HAS BEEN FACILITATED BY THE MENTOR TO FIX SOME POINTS TO IDENTIFY FUTURE PLANS. THE COMPANY HAS TAKEN INTO CONSIDERATION TO PROCEED WITH THE FOLLOWING ACTIVITIES: A) TO COMPLETE ITS TECH FEASIBILITY ASSESSMENT; B) TO COMPLETE THE TEAM WITH SPECIFIC EXPERTISE (AGRONOMIST, ENGINEER, A.I. EXPERT); C) TO EXPLORE THE PUBLIC FUNDING OPPORTUNITY AS WELL AS NATIONAL (EQUITY) CROWDFUNDING PLATFORMS TO SUSTAIN ITS BUSINESS; D) TO IMPROVE THE COMMUNICATION MATERIALS ACCORDING TO THE NEW BUSINESS STRATEGY OF THE COMPANY.

TEAM L PARTICIPATED IN THE REFLECTION SESSION (11/07/2024). THE REFLECTION SESSION HAS STARTED WITH A REVIEW OF THE MAIN ISSUES FACED IN THE INDIVIDUAL MEETINGS, STRESSING THE IDENTIFICATION OF THE STRENGTHS AND THE AREAS OF IMPROVEMENT OF THE TEAM. POSITIVE POINTS HAVE BEEN IDENTIFIED IN THE INVOLVEMENT AND PASSION OF THE TEAM, THE TRACK RECORD AND THE DEFINITION OF CLEAR OBJECTIVES FOR THE BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT OF THE COMPANY. RELEVANT IMPROVEMENTS HAVE TO BE REFERRED TO PITCHING AND BUSINESS PLANNING. THE MENTEE HAS IDENTIFIED THAT SHE NEEDS TO IMPROVE HER COMMUNICATION SKILLS AND TO PRACTISE ON TECHNIQUES TO PERFORM BETTER PITCHES AND MORE PRECISE BUSINESS PLANS. SHE ACQUIRED BASIC KNOWLEDGE ABOUT HOW TO IMPROVE THE PITCH OF THE COMPANY (IN PARTICULAR PRESENTING A MORE FOCUSED MARKET ANALYSIS) AND SHE ALSO ASSESSED AS POSITIVE THE CONCEPTS EXPLAINED BY THE MENTOR DEALING WITH BUSINESS PLANNING. SHE HAS CLEARLY UNDERSTOOD BASIC DIFFERENCES BETWEEN CASH FLOWS, PROFIT AND LOSS, INVESTMENTS AND COSTS AND SHE WILL WORK ON THAT POINT TO IMPROVE PRESENTATIONS AND FINANCIAL FORECASTS. IN TERMS OF FUTURE PLAN, THE MENTEE HAS UNDERSTOOD SHE HAS TO GO INTO DETAILS OF THESE ISSUES TO BETTER CONTROL THOSE ISSUES, FROM THE MOMENT SHE CONFIRMED SHE WANTS TO DEDICATE HER EFFORTS TO STRATEGY AND THE DEVELOPMENT.

TEAM N PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 01/08/2024. THE REFLECTION SESSION HAS STARTED WITH A REVIEW OF THE MAIN TOPICS DISCUSSED IN THE INDIVIDUAL MEETINGS AND THEIR RELEVANCE FOR THE BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT OF THE COMPANY. IN PARTICULAR, THE TEAM AND THE MENTOR HAVE RECOGNISED THAT STRENGTHS ARE THE DEEP INVOLVEMENT OF THE TEAM, THE COMPLEMENTARY SKILLS THAT THE TEAM HAVE, THE CLEAR IDEA OF THE PRODUCT TO OFFER; THERE ARE POINTS STILL TO IMPROVE AS A BETTER DEFINITION OF THE MARKET SEGMENT, THE PREPARATION OF A MORE EFFECTIVE PITCH AND THE DRAFTING OF A PRELIMINARY BUSINESS PLAN TO USE FOR INTERNAL TASKS AS WELL AS TO PRESENT TO EXTERNAL PERSONS. THE TEAM HAS, HOWEVER, CERTAINLY IMPROVED ITS SKILLS ABOUT COMMUNICATION AND PITCHING. IT HAS UNDERSTOOD THE IMPORTANCE TO LINK THE DIFFERENT TASKS OF THE JOB (TECHNICAL AND ECONOMIC) TO EFFECTIVELY ASSESS THE FINANCIAL PROJECTIONS. NEGOTIATION SKILLS

NEED ALSO TO BE IMPROVED, AT THE MOMENT THE TEAM SEEMS STILL DEPENDING ON EXTERNAL EXPERTISE TO OPERATE THE BUSINESS. A NEW / IMPROVED VERSION OF THE TECHNICAL AND THE BUSINESS PLAN WILL HELP THE TEAM IN FINDING THE BALANCED ASSET OF INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL RESOURCES FOR THE SUCCESS OF THE COMPANY IN THIS START-UP PHASE.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

4.4 EBAN - INVESTMENT PITCH AND QUANTIFYING YOUR FUNDING NEEDS

TRAINING VIDEOS

STRUCTURE

THE TRAINING VIDEOS SERVE AS THE INITIAL MENTORING ELEMENT, WITH EACH OF THE THREE VIDEOS LASTING ABOUT ONE HOUR, A TOTAL OF APPROXIMATELY THREE HOURS OF VIDEO MATERIAL WAS PROVIDED. THE MENTORS PRE-RECORD THE VIDEOS, WHICH ARE THEN LINKED TO ON THE F6S PLATFORM WITH THEIR RESPECTIVE POWERPOINT PRESENTATIONS.

GOAL

THE TRAINING VIDEOS AIMED TO INTRODUCE THE MENTEES INTO THE TOPIC OF THE MODULE AND PROVIDE THEM WITH A STRONG BASE FOR UNDERSTANDING THE ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF INVESTMENT PITCH AND QUANTIFYING THEIR FUNDING NEEDS. THE FIRST VIDEO PRESENTED THE CORE PRINCIPLES AND SKILLS TO DELIVER A COMPELLING INVESTMENT PITCH, PROVIDING THE APPROPRIATE STRUCTURE AND COMPONENTS TO CRAFT THE PITCH ACCORDING TO THE DIFFERENT FUNDING SOURCES. THE SECOND VIDEO PRESENTED AND DESCRIBED THE DIFFERENT FUNDING SOURCES AVAILABLE FOR STARTUPS, WHILE THE FINAL VIDEO FOCUSED ON THE FINANCIAL FORECASTING AND THE QUANTIFYING OF THEIR NEEDS.

CONTENT

VIDEO 1: THE VIDEO DIVED INTO THE ART OF INVESTMENT PITCHING. BY THE END OF THE WEBINARS, PARTICIPANTS SHOULD HAVE ACQUIRED A SOLID UNDERSTANDING OF WHAT IS AN INVESTMENT PITCH, HOW THEY ARE OFTEN STRUCTURED AND WHAT EACH PHASE CONSISTS OF. THE VIDEO LESSON ALSO TACKLES THE IMPORTANCE OF THE SOFT SKILL OF STORYTELLING AND THE NEED TO TAILOR THE INVESTMENT PITCH ACCORDING TO THE DIFFERENT AUDIENCES.

FIGURE 11: Screenshot of the First training video by EBAN

VIDEO 2: IN THIS VIDEO, THE MENTOR COVERED IN DETAIL THE DIFFERENT FUNDING SOURCES. THE WEBINAR ALSO COVERED WHAT WOULD BE THE MOST ADEQUATE EQUITY PERCENTAGES TO GIVE AWAY DURING EACH PHASE AND OTHER RELEVANT TIPS FOR ENTREPRENEURS. BY THE END OF THE WEBINARS, PARTICIPANTS SHOULD BE ABLE TO UNDERSTAND THE DIFFERENT STAGES A STARTUP WILL BE IN AND WHAT WOULD BE THEIR RESPECTIVE IDEAL SOURCE OF FUNDING TO GUARANTEE THEIR FINANCIAL SUSTAINABILITY.

FIGURE 12: Screenshot of the second training video by EBAN

VIDEO 3: IN THIS VIDEO, THE MENTOR COVERED FINANCIAL FORECASTING AND QUANTIFYING NEEDS. IT IS ESSENTIAL TO UNDERSTAND THESE TOPICS SINCE THEY WOULD ULTIMATELY HELP THE PARTICIPANTS UNDERSTAND THE FINANCIAL REQUIREMENTS OF THEIR BUSINESS, INCLUDING HOW MUCH CAPITAL THEY WOULD EVENTUALLY NEED TO RAISE AND HOW IT WILL BE USED. THE WEBINAR THEREFORE DIVED INTO THE FINANCIAL PROJECTIONS, MARKET SIZE AND MARKET SHARE TARGETS, KEY FINANCIAL METRICS AND KPIS, EXIT STRATEGIES AND OTHER ESSENTIAL POINTS.

FIGURE 13: Screenshot of the third training video by EBAN

RESULTS

FOR **COHORT 1, 2, & 3** ALL THREE VIDEOS HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTORING ORGANISATION AND HAVE BEEN CONSUMED BY THE MENTEES.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 3H

Quiz

STRUCTURE

ON THE F6S PLATFORM, A MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUIZ WAS IMPLEMENTED FOR EVERY MENTORING MODULE. THE NUMBER OF QUESTIONS AMOUNTED TO 30. THE QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE THREE MENTORING VIDEOS. IT WAS ESTIMATED THAT THE COMPLETION OF ONE QUIZ WOULD TAKE AN AVERAGE OF ONE HOUR.

GOAL

THE QUIZ IS NON-MANDATORY, IT AIMS TO TEST THE MENTEES UNDERSTANDING OF MENTORING VIDEOS TO THEN FOCUS IN THE FOLLOWING MENTORING PROCESS ON AREAS WHERE THE PERFORMANCE IN THE QUIZ WAS LACKING. THIS ALSO PROVIDED THE OPPORTUNITY OF THE MENTEE TO ASK QUESTIONS ABOUT THOSE QUESTIONS DURING THE WORKSHOPS AND Q&A SESSIONS.

CONTENT

THE QUIZ SHARED BY EBAN INCLUDES QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE CONTENT PRESENTED IN THE 3 VIDEOS OF THE MODULE. EACH VIDEO HAS 8 DEDICATED QUESTIONS WITH 4 POSSIBLE ANSWERS EACH. THE GOAL IS TO ASSESS THE LEVEL OF UNDERSTANDING WITH QUESTIONS THAT WERE BASED ON WHAT WAS PRESENTED ON THE SLIDES - OFFERING THE OPPORTUNITY FOR THE PARTICIPANTS TO GET BACK TO THE PRESENTATION TO MAKE SURE THEY DID NOT MISS ANY OF THE IMPORTANT INFORMATION WORTH REMEMBERING.

RESULTS

UNFORTUNATELY, NONE OF THE TEAMS OF **COHORT 1** COMPLETED THE QUIZ.

FOR **COHORT 2** THE QUIZ WAS COMPLETED BY E WHO HAD 75% OF CORRECT ANSWERS AND G WHO HAD 54.2% OF CORRECT ANSWERS.

For **COHORT 3** THE QUIZ WAS COMPLETED BY TEAMS J 75% CORRECT & K 62.5% CORRECT.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

WORKSHOP

STRUCTURE

THE WORKSHOP SESSION WAS THE FIRST LIVE INTERACTION OF THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEES. THE SESSION WAS HELD ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE WORKSHOP SESSION HAD A DURATION OF 2 HOURS AND WAS OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES.

GOAL

IN THE WORKSHOP, THE DIFFERENT MENTEES WERE ENCOURAGED TO APPLY THE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS LEARNED IN THE TRAINING VIDEOS TO THEIR OWN BUSINESS PLANS. THE GOAL OF THE SESSION IS TO FACILITATE PEER LEARNING THROUGH THE EXCHANGES BETWEEN ALL PARTICIPANTS. THE WORKSHOP AIM WAS TO TRAIN THE PARTICIPANTS TO DEVELOP AND REFINE THEIR ELEVATOR PITCH TO THEN HAVE THE TOOLS TO FURTHER DEVELOP THEIR INVESTOR PITCH.

CONTENT

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

THE MENTOR ALSO COVERED ALL THE KEY POINTS PRESENTED DURING THE VIDEOS LESSON, MAKING SURE THAT THE PARTICIPANTS WERE UP TO DATE AND WERE ABLE TO PROCEED WITH THE PREPARATION OF A FIRST DRAFT OF THEIR PITCH. FOCUSING ON HOW TO EFFECTIVELY DELIVER A PITCH, ENGAGING PARTICIPANTS, REQUESTING THEM TO ATTEMPT COVERING EACH POINT AND ENCOURAGING QUESTION EXCHANGES.

RESULTS

FOR **COHORT 1**, TWO TEAMS JOINED THE WORKSHOP CONDUCTED ON THE 28/11/2023, TEAM B AND C. THE TWO PARTICIPANTS ENGAGED WITH THE MENTORS AND PRACTISED THEIR ELEVATOR PITCH, AS WELL AS REVIEWING THE CORE FUNDAMENTALS FOR DELIVERING A PITCH TO INVESTORS. THE SESSION WAS CONCLUDED WITH A REQUEST TO THE MENTEES TO PREPARE A FIRST DRAFT OF THEIR INVESTOR PITCH.

FOR **COHORT 2**, ONLY ONE TEAM JOINED THE WORKSHOP CONDUCTED ON THE 16/02/2024, TEAM E. THE MENTEE PRACTISED HER ELEVATOR PITCH, AS WELL AS REVIEWING THE CORE FUNDAMENTALS FOR DELIVERING A PITCH TO INVESTORS. THE SESSION WAS CONCLUDED WITH A REQUEST TO THE MENTEES TO PREPARE A FIRST DRAFT OF THEIR INVESTOR PITCH.

FOR **COHORT 3**, ONLY ONE TEAM JOINED THE WORKSHOP CONDUCTED ON THE 30/05/2024, TEAM J. THE MENTEE PRACTISED HER ELEVATOR PITCH, AS WELL AS REVIEWING THE CORE FUNDAMENTALS FOR DELIVERING A PITCH TO INVESTORS, THE TEAM ALREADY HAD A FIRST DRAFT SO THE MENTOR TOOK THE OPPORTUNITY TO COMMENT AND PROVIDE RECOMMENDATIONS TO THE MENTEE. THE SESSION WAS CONCLUDED WITH A REQUEST TO ALL THE MENTEES (WHO DID NOT PARTICIPATE BUT WOULD WATCH THE RECORDING) TO PREPARE A FIRST DRAFT OF THEIR INVESTOR PITCH.

ALL THE 3 WORKSHOP SESSIONS WERE RECORDED TO ENABLE ENTREPRENEURS WHO MISSED THE SESSION TO WATCH IT.

FIGURE 14: Screenshot of the Webinar video by EBAN

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

Q&A SESSION

STRUCTURE

THE Q&A SESSION WAS FACILITATED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE DURATION OF THE SESSION WAS 1 HOUR AND OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES TO ENTER AND ASK QUESTIONS ABOUT MENTORING RELATED TOPICS.

GOAL

THE Q&A SESSION AIMS TO PROVIDE THE MENTEES WITH AN OPPORTUNITY TO ASK QUESTIONS AND TO SOLVE DOUBTS RAISED FROM THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP.

THE MENTOR ADDRESSED ALL PRESSING QUESTIONS THAT AROSE DURING THE WEBINARS AND THE WORKSHOP, AND GUIDED PARTICIPANTS INTO HOW TO REFINE THEIR OBJECTIVES AND PITCH TO PRESENT TO INVESTORS.

CONTENT

FOR **COHORT 1, 2 AND 3**, PARTICIPANTS HAVE THE CHANCE TO EXPLAIN PRESSING ISSUES OR ASK QUESTIONS REGARDING THE BEFORE PROVIDED CONTENT. THE AIM WAS TO INCREASE THEIR UNDERSTANDING AND PREPARE THEM FOR THE UPCOMING SESSIONS.

ONLY THREE TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION (A, C, AND B) AND ALL OF THEM PARTICIPATED AND ASKED QUESTIONS.

RESULTS

FOR **COHORT 1**, THREE TEAMS JOINED THE Q&A SESSION CONDUCTED ON THE 16/01/2023, NAMELY D, C AND B. THE SESSION REVIEWED THE QUESTIONS OF THE ATTENDEES, AND PROVIDED SOME INSIGHTS INTO THE INVESTMENT GATHERING PROCESS.

FOR **COHORT 2**, ONLY ONE TEAM JOINED THE Q&A SESSION CONDUCTED ON THE 22/02/2024, TEAM F. THE SESSION REVIEWED THE QUESTIONS OF THE ATTENDEE, AND PROVIDED SOME INSIGHTS INTO THE INVESTMENT GATHERING PROCESS.

FOR **COHORT 3**, UNFORTUNATELY NONE OF THE TEAMS PARTICIPATED IN THE Q&A SESSION THAT WAS SUPPOSED TO BE CONDUCTED ON THE 06/06/2024. INSTEAD, EBAN PROPOSED TO HAVE FREE

ADDITIONAL SESSIONS TO TWO MENTEES TO RECEIVE FURTHER FEEDBACK FOR THEIR INVESTMENT PITCHES, ONE BOOKED A SESSION FOR THE 11/09/2024.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

TWO INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR EACH TEAM, EACH WITH A DURATION OF ONE HOUR, WERE OFFERED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH WERE CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR, LEADING TO A TOTAL OF TWO HOURS OF MENTORING PER TEAM. IN THESE SESSIONS ONLY, THE MENTORS AND ONE TEAM ARE PRESENT TO FOCUS ON THEIR SPECIFIC NEEDS AND CHALLENGES.

GOAL

THE INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS PROVIDED PERSONALISED GUIDANCE TO EACH TEAM, HELPING THEM DEVELOP AND REFINE THEIR OWN PITCH TO DELIVER TO INVESTORS. THIS ASSISTANCE ENSURED THAT EACH TEAM WOULD RECEIVE PERSONALISED INPUT AND RECOMMENDATIONS ON THEIR PITCH, MAKING SURE THAT ALL THE RELEVANT SECTIONS WERE INCLUDED IN THE PITCH DECK, AS WELL AS THAT THE FORMAT OF DELIVERY WAS THE MOST APPROPRIATE ONE.

CONTENT

IN THE INDIVIDUAL SESSION, THE PITCH DECK OF EACH STARTUP WAS REVIEWED AND ASSESSED. THE SESSIONS BEGAN WITH A THOROUGH REVIEW OF THE STARTUP'S PRESENTATION USED FOR THE HACKATHON. MENTORS AND MENTEES EXAMINED EACH COMPONENT OF THE PRESENTATION, FROM THE PROBLEM TO THE BUSINESS MODEL AND MARKET OPPORTUNITY. THEN THE MENTOR BUILT ON TOP OF THE PRESENTATION, PROVIDING RECOMMENDATIONS ON WHO TO DEVELOP IT INTO A BETTER PITCH. THE MENTOR PROVIDED TARGETED ADVICE ON HOW TO IMPROVE CERTAIN ASPECTS OF THE PRESENTATION, ENSURING THAT BY THE END OF THE TWO SESSIONS, EACH TEAM HAD A COMPLETED PITCH DECK READY TO BE DELIVERED IN FRONT OF INVESTORS. THE FIRST STEP WAS TO IDENTIFY THE PROBLEM THE STARTUP WAS AIMING TO RESOLVE, THIS WAS AN ESSENTIAL ASPECT FOR GRABBING THE AUDIENCE'S INTEREST SINCE IT WOULD LAY THE FOUNDATION FOR THE NEXT SECTIONS. IT IS IMPORTANT TO HIGHLIGHT THE PROJECT IN A CLEAR WAY SO THAT THE INVESTORS UNDERSTAND THE LOGIC BEHIND THE IDEA, THAT IS WHERE THE IMPORTANCE TO SHARE THE PROBLEM IN THE BEST WAY POSSIBLE COMES IN. THEN WOULD COME THE SOLUTION, THE INVESTOR WOULD RECEIVE GUIDANCE ON HOW TO BEST HIGHLIGHT THE SOLUTION TO ATTRACT THE INVESTOR'S INTEREST. THE ENTREPRENEURS HAD SOME RECOMMENDATIONS ON HOW TO BEST EXPLAIN THE MARKET OPPORTUNITY, HIGHLIGHTING THE POTENTIAL GROWTH OF THEIR BUSINESS. THE MENTOR PROVIDED RECOMMENDATIONS ON THE GRAPHS FOR THE COMPETITION, AS WELL AS FOR THE BUSINESS MODEL AND SALE STRATEGIES. A LOT OF WORK WAS DEDICATED TO EXPLAINING THE EXPECTATION OF THE INVESTORS WHEN IT CAME TO TRACTION, MILESTONES, THE TEAM AND THE ASK. THIS PROCESS WAS CONDUCTED FOR COHORT 1, 2 & 3.

RESULTS
FOR COHORT 1:

THE TEAM A COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT GET A RESPONSE. HENCE, THE TEAM A DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

THE TEAM B PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (13/02/2024 & 19/02/2024) AND DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR DEVELOPED A PITCH AND ORGANISED PITCH DRY RUNS TO ENSURE THE READINESS OF THE ENTREPRENEUR. THE MENTOR ALSO ANSWERED ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS ON DIFFERENT TOPICS SUCH AS PITCHING COMPETITION, DILUTION, THE EVENTS HAPPENING IN EUROPE, AND OTHER ADVICE.

THE TEAM C PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (01/02/2024 & 14/02/2024) AND DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR DEVELOPED A PITCH AND ORGANISED PITCH DRY RUNS TO ENSURE THE READINESS OF THE ENTREPRENEUR. THE MENTOR ALSO ANSWERED ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS ON DIFFERENT TOPICS SUCH AS PITCHING COMPETITION, DILUTION, THE EVENTS HAPPENING IN EUROPE, AND OTHER ADVICE.

THE TEAM D COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT GET A RESPONSE. HENCE, THE TEAM "AS YOU LIKE" DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

FOR COHORT 2:

THE TEAM E PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (01/03/2024 & 05/03/2024) AND DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR DEVELOPED A PITCH AND ORGANISED PITCH DRY RUNS TO ENSURE THE READINESS OF THE ENTREPRENEUR. THE MENTOR ALSO ANSWERED ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS ON DIFFERENT TOPICS SUCH AS PITCHING COMPETITION, DILUTION, THE EVENTS HAPPENING IN EUROPE, AND OTHER ADVICE.

THE TEAM F PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (26/02/2024 & 04/03/2024) AND DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR DEVELOPED A PITCH AND ORGANISED PITCH DRY RUNS TO ENSURE THE READINESS OF THE ENTREPRENEUR. THE MENTOR ALSO ANSWERED ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS ON DIFFERENT TOPICS SUCH AS PITCHING COMPETITION, DILUTION, THE EVENTS HAPPENING IN EUROPE, AND OTHER ADVICE.

THE TEAM G PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (05/03/2024 & 08/03/2024) AND DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR DEVELOPED A PITCH AND ORGANISED PITCH DRY RUNS TO ENSURE THE READINESS OF THE ENTREPRENEUR. THE MENTOR ALSO ANSWERED ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS ON DIFFERENT TOPICS SUCH AS PITCHING COMPETITION, DILUTION, THE EVENTS HAPPENING IN EUROPE, AND OTHER ADVICE.

THE TEAM H PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (12/04/2024 & 17/04/2024) AND DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR DEVELOPED A PITCH AND ORGANISED PITCH DRY RUNS TO ENSURE THE READINESS OF THE ENTREPRENEUR. THE MENTOR ALSO ANSWERED ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS ON DIFFERENT TOPICS SUCH AS PITCHING COMPETITION, DILUTION, THE EVENTS HAPPENING IN EUROPE, AND OTHER ADVICE.

THE TEAM I PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (05/04/2024 & 17/04/2024) AND DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR DEVELOPED A PITCH AND ORGANISED PITCH DRY RUNS TO ENSURE THE READINESS OF THE ENTREPRENEUR. THE MENTOR ALSO ANSWERED ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS ON DIFFERENT TOPICS SUCH AS PITCHING COMPETITION, DILUTION, THE EVENTS HAPPENING IN EUROPE, AND OTHER ADVICE.

FOR COHORT 3:

THE TEAM J PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (13/06/2024 & 20/06/2024) AND DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR DEVELOPED A PITCH AND ORGANISED PITCH DRY RUNS TO ENSURE THE READINESS OF THE

ENTREPRENEUR. THE MENTOR ALSO ANSWERED ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS ON DIFFERENT TOPICS SUCH AS PITCHING COMPETITION, DILUTION, THE EVENTS HAPPENING IN EUROPE, AND OTHER ADVICE.

THE TEAM K PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (20/06/2024 & 27/06/2024) AND DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR DEVELOPED A PITCH AND ORGANISED PITCH DRY RUNS TO ENSURE THE READINESS OF THE ENTREPRENEUR. THE MENTOR ALSO ANSWERED ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS ON DIFFERENT TOPICS SUCH AS PITCHING COMPETITION, DILUTION, THE EVENTS HAPPENING IN EUROPE, AND OTHER ADVICE.

THE TEAM L PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (28/06/2024 & 31/07/2024) AND DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR DEVELOPED A PITCH AND ORGANISED PITCH DRY RUNS TO ENSURE THE READINESS OF THE ENTREPRENEUR. THE MENTOR ALSO ANSWERED ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS ON DIFFERENT TOPICS SUCH AS PITCHING COMPETITION, DILUTION, THE EVENTS HAPPENING IN EUROPE, AND OTHER ADVICE.

THE TEAM M COMMUNICATED THAT THEIR BUSINESS HAD BEEN RESOLVED. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE TEAM DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE TEAM DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

THE TEAM N WAS NOT ABLE TO ATTEND THE SESSION PRE-AGREE WITH THE MENTOR, THE MENTOR AND THE ENTREPRENEUR HAVE ARRANGED THE MEETING TIMES ON THE 04/09/2024 & 09/09/2024.

THE TEAM O PARTICIPATED IN THE FIRST SESSION (15/07/2024) AND DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR DEVELOPED A PITCH AND ORGANISED PITCH DRY RUNS TO ENSURE THE READINESS OF THE ENTREPRENEUR. UNFORTUNATELY, THE TEAM COMMUNICATED DUE TO AN OVERLAP OF THE MENTORING PROGRAMME WITH THEIR CURRENT OCCUPATION, THEY WILL NOT BE ABLE TO CONTINUE WITH THE PROGRAMME.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

REFLECTION SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

A ONE-HOUR REFLECTION SESSION WAS OFFERED TO ALL MENTEES ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THIS SESSION FOCUSED ON SHARING THE FEEDBACK BETWEEN THE MENTEES AND THE ENTREPRENEUR, MARKING THE END OF THIS MENTORING MODULE.

GOAL

THE REFLECTION SESSION AIMED TO ENCOURAGE PARTICIPANTS TO PRACTISE SELF-ASSESSMENT AND REFLECTION, ENABLING THEM TO MONITOR THEIR PROGRESS, ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS, AND IDENTIFY AREAS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT. THIS SESSION ALSO OFFERED THE OPPORTUNITY TO THE MENTEE TO HAVE A FINAL REVIEW OF THEIR PITCH, AS WELL AS SHARE THEIR THOUGHTS ABOUT THE PROGRAMME. THE MENTOR ENCOURAGED CONSTRUCTIVE FEEDBACK IN BOTH WAYS, TO APPLY THE RECEIVED FEEDBACK IN THE NEXT COHORT'S MENTORING.

CONTENT

IN THE REFLECTION SESSION, A GUIDED DISCUSSION BETWEEN THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEE TOOK PLACE. THE FOCUS WAS PUT ON REVIEWING THE PITCH DECK AND FUTURE STEPS FOR THE STARTUPS. EBAN OFFERED THE OPPORTUNITY TO THE TEAMS TO ASK THEIR FINAL QUESTIONS CONCERNING THE COURSE AND TO HAVE A FINAL PITCH DRY RUN TO CONSOLIDATE THE LESSONS LEARNED DURING THE FIRST HALF OF THE SESSION. EBAN HAS ALSO PRESENTED THE INITIATIVES AND THEIR ANNUAL EVENTS EBAN IS CURRENTLY ORGANISED AND INVOLVED IN, WHICH COULD PROVIDE ADDITIONAL SUPPORT TO THE TEAMS, (SUCH AS HORIZON PROJECTS, AND ITS CONGRESS & SUMMIT). THE PARTICIPANT REQUESTED WHETHER THEY COULD REACH OUT TO EBAN IN CASE THEY HAD ANY ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS, OR MATERIAL TO BE REVIEWED, AND EBAN GLADLY ACCEPTED AND ENCOURAGED THE ENTREPRENEUR TO

NOT HESITATE TO REACH OUT EVEN ONCE THE PROJECT WAS OVER. THEN, EBAN ENCOURAGED THE PARTICIPANTS TO SHARE THEIR THOUGHTS ABOUT THE SESSION AND PRACTISE SELF-ASSESSMENT TO ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS. THIS PROCESS WAS CONDUCTED FOR COHORT 1, 2 & 3.

FOR COHORT 1:

THE TEAM B PARTICIPATED IN THEIR SESSION ON THE 19/03/2024. THE FINAL PITCH DRY RUN WAS ORGANISED, VERY POSITIVE WAS GATHERED FROM THE MENTEE, THEY DID NOT HAVE MANY COMMENTS REGARDING HOW TO IMPROVE THE SESSIONS.

THE TEAM C PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 11/03/2024. THE FINAL PITCH DRY RUN WAS ORGANISED, VERY POSITIVE WAS GATHERED FROM THE MENTEE, THEY DID NOT HAVE MANY COMMENTS REGARDING HOW TO IMPROVE THE SESSIONS.

FOR COHORT 2:

THE TEAM E PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 15/03/2024. THE FINAL PITCH DRY RUN WAS ORGANISED, VERY POSITIVE WAS GATHERED FROM THE MENTEE, THEY DID NOT HAVE MANY COMMENTS REGARDING HOW TO IMPROVE THE SESSIONS. REFLECTED IN THE POSITIVE FEEDBACK GATHERED BY FRAUNHOFER.

THE TEAM F PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 12/03/2024. THE FINAL PITCH DRY RUN WAS ORGANISED, VERY POSITIVE WAS GATHERED FROM THE MENTEE, THEY DID NOT HAVE MANY COMMENTS REGARDING HOW TO IMPROVE THE SESSIONS. REFLECTED IN THE POSITIVE FEEDBACK GATHERED BY FRAUNHOFER.

THE TEAM G PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 13/03/2024. THE FINAL PITCH DRY RUN WAS ORGANISED, VERY POSITIVE WAS GATHERED FROM THE MENTEE, THEY DID NOT HAVE MANY COMMENTS REGARDING HOW TO IMPROVE THE SESSIONS. REFLECTED IN THE POSITIVE FEEDBACK GATHERED BY FRAUNHOFER.

THE TEAM H PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 25/04/2024. THE FINAL PITCH DRY RUN WAS ORGANISED, VERY POSITIVE WAS GATHERED FROM THE MENTEE, THEY DID NOT HAVE MANY COMMENTS REGARDING HOW TO IMPROVE THE SESSIONS. REFLECTED IN THE POSITIVE FEEDBACK GATHERED BY FRAUNHOFER.

RESULTS

FOR COHORT 3:

THE TEAM J PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 27/06/2024. THE FINAL PITCH DRY RUN WAS ORGANISED, VERY POSITIVE WAS GATHERED FROM THE MENTEE, THEY DID NOT HAVE MANY COMMENTS REGARDING HOW TO IMPROVE THE SESSIONS. REFLECTED IN THE POSITIVE FEEDBACK GATHERED BY FRAUNHOFER.

THE TEAM K PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION ON THE 10/07/2024. THE FINAL PITCH DRY RUN WAS ORGANISED, VERY POSITIVE WAS GATHERED FROM THE MENTEE, THEY DID NOT HAVE MANY COMMENTS REGARDING HOW TO IMPROVE THE SESSIONS. REFLECTED IN THE POSITIVE FEEDBACK GATHERED BY FRAUNHOFER.

THE TEAM L WILL PARTICIPATE IN THE SESSION ON THE 17/09/2024.

THE TEAM N WILL PARTICIPATE IN THE SESSION ON THE 12/09/2024.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

4.5 CORALLIA - ENTREPRENEURIAL BUSINESS PLANNING

TRAINING VIDEOS (WEBINARS)

STRUCTURE

THE TRAINING VIDEOS SERVE AS THE INITIAL MENTORING ELEMENT, WITH EACH OF THE THREE VIDEOS LASTING ABOUT ONE HOUR, A TOTAL OF APPROXIMATELY THREE HOURS OF VIDEO MATERIAL IS PROVIDED. THE MENTORS PRE-RECORD THE VIDEOS, WHICH ARE THEN LINKED TO ON THE F6S PLATFORM.

GOAL

THE TRAINING VIDEOS AIM TO INTRODUCE THE MENTEES INTO THE TOPIC OF THE MODULE AND PROVIDE THEM WITH A BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF THE ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF THE MODULE. THE FIRST VIDEO SERVES AS AN INTRODUCTORY SESSION TO THE TOPIC OF THE MENTORING MODULE. THE SECOND VIDEO DELVES DEEPER INTO THE MODULE'S TOPICS, WHILE THE FINAL VIDEO FOCUSES ON THE MOST COMPLEX ASPECTS COVERED IN THE MENTORING MODULE

CONTENT

VIDEO 1: THE VIDEO INTRODUCES PARTICIPANTS TO THE FUNDAMENTAL PRINCIPLES OF BUSINESS PLANNING. IT AIMS FOR VIEWERS TO GRASP THE SIGNIFICANCE OF A BUSINESS PLAN, COMPREHEND ITS ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS, AND GAIN INSIGHTS INTO INITIATING THE DRAFTING PROCESS FOR THEIR STARTUP. DETAILED INFORMATION AND SUGGESTIONS REGARDING THE MANDATORY SECTIONS OF A BUSINESS PLAN, SUCH AS THE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY, COMPANY DESCRIPTION, MARKET ANALYSIS, ORGANISATION AND MANAGEMENT, SERVICE OR PRODUCT LINE, MARKETING AND SALES, AND FINANCIAL PROJECTIONS, ARE PROVIDED. THE ADVICE GIVEN IS GROUNDED IN BEST PRACTICES FOR WRITING A BUSINESS PLAN.

Figure 15: Screenshot of the first training video by Corallia

VIDEO 2: THE VIDEO AIMS TO GUIDE PARTICIPANTS ON CONDUCTING A COMPREHENSIVE MARKET ANALYSIS AND DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE BUSINESS STRATEGIES. IT IS INTENDED THAT, BY THE END OF THE WEBINARS, PARTICIPANTS WILL BE ABLE TO CONDUCT A MARKET ANALYSIS, ENCOMPASSING A COMPETITIVE ANALYSIS AND CUSTOMER

SEGMENTATION, AND TO FORMULATE A SUITABLE BUSINESS STRATEGY. THE WEBINAR CENTRES ON EMPHASISING THE IMPORTANCE OF UNDERSTANDING THE MARKET LANDSCAPE, WHICH INCLUDES IDENTIFYING COMPETITORS, COMPREHENDING CUSTOMER SEGMENTS, AND RECOGNIZING MARKET TRENDS.

Figure 16: Screenshot of the second training video by Corallia

VIDEO 3: THE VIDEO AIMS TO EQUIP PARTICIPANTS WITH THE KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS REQUIRED TO EFFECTIVELY PLAN THE FINANCIAL ASPECTS OF THEIR BUSINESS. IT IS INTENDED THAT, BY THE END OF THE WEBINAR, PARTICIPANTS WILL BE CAPABLE OF CREATING BUDGETS, FINANCIAL FORECASTS, AND A PLAN FOR FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT FOR THEIR TEAMS. THE VIDEO COVERS THE FUNDAMENTALS OF FINANCIAL PLANNING, INCLUDING BUDGETING, CASH FLOW MANAGEMENT, FINANCIAL FORECASTING, AND UNDERSTANDING KEY FINANCIAL STATEMENTS.

Figure 17: Screenshot of the third training video by Corallia

RESULTS

FOR **COHORT 1, 2, & 3** ALL THREE TRAINING VIDEOS HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTORING ORGANISATION AND HAVE BEEN VIEWED BY THE MENTEES.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 3H

QUIZ

STRUCTURE

ON THE F6S PLATFORM, A MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUIZ WAS IMPLEMENTED FOR EVERY MENTORING MODULE. THE AMOUNT OF QUESTIONS RANGED BETWEEN 24 AND 30. THE QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE THREE MENTORING VIDEOS. IT WAS ESTIMATED THAT THE COMPLETION OF ONE QUIZ TAKES ONE HOUR.

GOAL

THE QUIZ IS NON-MANDATORY BUT AIMS TO TEST THE MENTEES UNDERSTANDING OF MENTORING VIDEOS TO THEN FOCUS IN THE FOLLOWING MENTORING PROCESS ON AREAS WHERE THE PERFORMANCE IN THE QUIZ WAS LACKING.

CONTENT

THE QUIZ INCLUDES BOTH THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE CONTENT PRESENTED IN THE 3 VIDEOS OF THE MODULE. THE QUESTIONS ARE FORMED IN A WAY THAT MAKES IT EASY TO VERIFY WHETHER THE MENTEES HAVE INDEED WATCHED THE VIDEOS, AND TO IDENTIFY SPECIFIC AREAS ON WHICH THE TEAMS MAY NEED EXTRA CLARIFICATIONS.

UNFORTUNATELY, NONE OF THE TEAMS OF **COHORT 1** COMPLETED THE QUIZ.

RESULTS

FOR **COHORT 2** THE QUIZ WAS COMPLETED BY THE TEAM G.

FOR **COHORT 3** THE QUIZ WAS COMPLETED BY TEAMS J & K.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

WORKSHOP

STRUCTURE

THE WORKSHOP SESSION IS THE FIRST LIVE INTERACTION OF THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEES. THE SESSION IS HELD ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE WORKSHOP SESSION HAS A DURATION OF 2 HOURS AND IS OPEN TO ALL MENTEES.

GOAL

IN THE WORKSHOP, THE DIFFERENT MENTEES CAN APPLY THE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS LEARNT IN THE TRAINING VIDEOS TO THEIR OWN BUSINESS ENDEAVOURS.

CONTENT

THE PRIMARY AIM OF THIS WORKSHOP WAS TO ENABLE PARTICIPANTS TO APPLY THE CONCEPTS LEARNT DURING THE WEBINARS TO DRAFT THEIR BUSINESS PLANS. BY THE END OF THE WORKSHOP, EACH TEAM IDENTIFIED A PRELIMINARY OUTLINE OF THEIR BUSINESS PLAN AND UNDERSTOOD THE AREAS THEY NEED TO DEVELOP FURTHER. AT THE BEGINNING OF THE WORKSHOP, THE PARTICIPANTS PRESENTED THEIR IDEAS AND WITH THE HELP OF THE MENTOR, THEY IDENTIFIED THE TYPE OF THEIR BUSINESS MODEL AND THEIR MARKET SEGMENT. THE BUSINESS PLAN ANALYSIS THAT FOLLOWED FOR EACH COMPONENT OF THE BUSINESS PLAN WAS BASED ON EXAMPLES THAT FIT EXACTLY THE IDEAS AND MARKETS OF THE PARTICIPANTS, AND AS SUCH, THE PRESENTATION OF THE BUSINESS PLAN STRUCTURE WAS TAILORED TO THE INDIVIDUAL NEEDS OF THE TEAMS.

ALL FOUR TEAMS OF **COHORT 1** PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP AND UNDERSTOOD ITS CONTENT. ALL **COHORT 2** TEAMS (EXCLUDING THE TEAM I) PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP. FINALLY, TWO TEAMS OF **COHORT 3** (J AND K) PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP.

RESULTS

THE WORKSHOP FOR **COHORT 1** WAS CONDUCTED ON THE 29/11/2023.

THE WORKSHOP FOR **COHORT 2** WAS CONDUCTED ON THE 14/02/2024.

THE WORKSHOP FOR **COHORT 3** WAS CONDUCTED ON THE 21/06/2024.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

Q&A SESSION

STRUCTURE

THE Q&A SESSION WAS FACILITATED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE DURATION OF THE SESSION WAS 1 HOUR AND OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES TO ENTER AND ASK QUESTIONS ABOUT MENTORING RELATED TOPICS.

GOAL

THE Q&A SESSION AIMS TO PROVIDE THE MENTEES WITH AN OPPORTUNITY TO ASK QUESTIONS AND TO SOLVE DOUBTS RAISED FROM THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP.

CONTENT

DURING THIS SESSION, THE MENTOR ADDRESSED ALL QUESTIONS AND ISSUES THAT AROSE DURING THE WEBINARS AND THE WORKSHOP, AND PROVIDED PARTICIPANTS WITH THE CLARIFICATION AND GUIDANCE NEEDED TO REFINE THEIR OWN BUSINESS PLANS. MOREOVER, THE TIME-PLAN AND METHODOLOGY TO BE FOLLOWED DURING THE UPCOMING INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS WAS ALSO PRESENTED.

RESULTS

IN **COHORTS 1 AND 2**, ALL TEAMS ACTIVELY ENGAGED IN THE Q&A SESSION AND ASKED QUESTIONS. IN **COHORT 3**, THERE WAS NO TIME AVAILABLE FOR A Q&A SESSION, AND AS SUCH, THE TEAMS WERE OFFERED THE OPTION TO

SHARE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN AND QUESTIONS AND RECEIVE FEEDBACK FROM THE MENTOR ASYNCHRONOUSLY. THE MENTOR ALSO OFFERED AN OPTION FOR EACH ONE OF THE TEAMS TO GET AN EXTRA HOUR OF INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSION AT A TIME OF THEIR CONVENIENCE.

THE SESSION FOR **COHORT 1** WAS CONDUCTED ON THE 15/12/2023.

THE SESSION FOR **COHORT 2** WAS CONDUCTED ON THE 23/02/2024.

FOR **COHORT 3** A Q&A SESSION HAS BEEN OFFERED ON THE 07/06/2024 BUTT WAS NOT ATTENDED BY THE TEAMS.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

TWO INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR EACH TEAM, EACH WITH A DURATION OF ONE HOUR, WERE OFFERED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR, LEADING TO A TOTAL OF TWO HOURS OF MENTORING PER TEAM. IN THESE SESSIONS, ONLY THE MENTORS AND ONE TEAM WERE PRESENT TO FOCUS ON THEIR SPECIFIC NEEDS AND ISSUES.

GOAL

THE INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS PROVIDED PERSONALISED GUIDANCE TO EACH TEAM, HELPING THEM OVERCOME SPECIFIC OBSTACLES ENCOUNTERED DURING CRITICAL PHASES OF THEIR COMPANIES. THIS ASSISTANCE AIDS IN DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR THE FUTURE.

CONTENT

IN THE INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS, THE TEAMS HAD THE CHANCE TO CONTINUE WORKING ON THEIR BUSINESS PLAN AND CLARIFY PRESSING ISSUES.

FOR COHORT 1:

TEAM A COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT GET A RESPONSE. HENCE, TEAM A DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

TEAM B PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (15/01/2024 & 29/01/2024) AND WORKED ON ALL SECTIONS OF THE BUSINESS PLAN PROVIDED BY CORALLIA. DISCUSSIONS FOCUSED ON FEEDBACK AND COMMENTS RELATED TO THE PRODUCED OUTCOME.

RESULTS

TEAM C PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (08/01/2024 & 22/01/2024) AND WORKED ON ALL SECTIONS OF THE BUSINESS PLAN PROVIDED BY CORALLIA. DISCUSSIONS FOCUSED ON FEEDBACK AND COMMENTS RELATED TO THE PRODUCED OUTCOME.

TEAM D COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE TEAM DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, TEAM D DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

FOR COHORT 2:

TEAM E PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (11/03/2024 & 15/03/2024) AND WORKED ON ALL SECTIONS OF THE BUSINESS PLAN PROVIDED BY CORALLIA. DISCUSSIONS FOCUSED ON FEEDBACK AND COMMENTS RELATED TO THE PRODUCED OUTCOME.

TEAM F PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (01/03/2024 & 15/03/2024) AND WORKED ON ALL SECTIONS OF THE BUSINESS PLAN PROVIDED BY CORALLIA. DISCUSSIONS FOCUSED ON FEEDBACK AND COMMENTS RELATED TO THE PRODUCED OUTCOME.

TEAM G PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (22/03/2024 & 01/04/2024) AND WORKED ON ALL SECTIONS OF THE BUSINESS PLAN PROVIDED BY CORALLIA. DISCUSSIONS FOCUSED ON FEEDBACK AND COMMENTS RELATED TO THE PRODUCED OUTCOME.

TEAM H PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (03/04/2024 & 19/04/2024) AND WORKED ON ALL SECTIONS OF THE BUSINESS PLAN PROVIDED BY CORALLIA. DISCUSSIONS FOCUSED ON FEEDBACK AND COMMENTS RELATED TO THE PRODUCED OUTCOME.

TEAM I PARTICIPATED IN ONE SESSION (02/04/2024) AND WORKED ON SOME OF THE SECTIONS OF THE BUSINESS PLAN PROVIDED BY CORALLIA (MAINLY THE ONES RELATED TO MARKET AND COMPETITION ANALYSIS). DISCUSSIONS FOCUSED ON FEEDBACK AND COMMENTS RELATED TO THE PRODUCED OUTCOME.

FOR COHORT 3:

TEAM J PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (05/07/2024 & 12/07/2024) AND WORKED ON ALL SECTIONS OF THE BUSINESS PLAN PROVIDED BY CORALLIA. DISCUSSIONS FOCUSED ON FEEDBACK AND COMMENTS RELATED TO THE PRODUCED OUTCOME.

TEAM K DID NOT MANAGE TO FIND A TIME AVAILABLE FOR THE PROVIDED SESSIONS. HOWEVER, THE TEAM WERE OFFERED THE OPTION TO SHARE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN AND QUESTIONS AND RECEIVE FEEDBACK FROM THE MENTOR ASYNCHRONOUSLY. THE MENTOR ALSO OFFERED AN OPTION FOR THE TEAM TO GET AN EXTRA HOUR OF INDIVIDUAL MENTORING AT A TIME OF THEIR CONVENIENCE, EVEN AFTER THE CONCLUSION OF THE PROJECT.

TEAM L PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (01/07/2024 & 15/07/2024) AND WORKED ON ALL SECTIONS OF THE BUSINESS PLAN PROVIDED BY CORALLIA. DISCUSSIONS FOCUSED ON FEEDBACK AND COMMENTS RELATED TO THE PRODUCED OUTCOME.

THE TEAM M COMMUNICATED THAT THEIR BUSINESS HAD BEEN RESOLVED. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE TEAM DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE TEAM I DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

TEAM N PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (12/07/2024 & 19/07/2024) AND WORKED ON ALL SECTIONS OF THE BUSINESS PLAN PROVIDED BY CORALLIA. DISCUSSIONS FOCUSED ON FEEDBACK AND COMMENTS RELATED TO THE PRODUCED OUTCOME.

TEAM O PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (12/07/2024 & 26/07/2024) AND WORKED ON ALL SECTIONS OF THE BUSINESS PLAN PROVIDED BY CORALLIA. DISCUSSIONS FOCUSED ON FEEDBACK AND COMMENTS RELATED TO THE PRODUCED OUTCOME.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

REFLECTION SESSIONS

STRUCTURE	<p>A ONE-HOUR REFLECTION SESSION WAS OFFERED TO ALL MENTEES ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THIS SESSION FOCUSED ON PROVIDING FEEDBACK TO THE MENTEES AND MARKED THE END OF THIS MENTORING MODULE.</p>
GOAL	<p>THE REFLECTION SESSION AIMED TO ENCOURAGE PARTICIPANTS TO PRACTISE SELF-ASSESSMENT AND REFLECTION, ENABLING THEM TO MONITOR THEIR PROGRESS, ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS, AND IDENTIFY AREAS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT.</p>
CONTENT	<p>IN THE REFLECTION SESSION, A GUIDED DISCUSSION BETWEEN THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEE TOOK PLACE. THE FOCUS WAS PUT ON REVIEWING THE BUSINESS PLAN AND DEVELOPING ACTIONS TO IMPROVE THE TEAM IN THE FUTURE.</p> <p>FOR COHORT 1:</p> <p>TEAM B PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION (19/02/2024) AND THE FINALISED RESULT OF THE TEAM WAS EVALUATED AND THE LAST FEEDBACK WAS PROVIDED. A PLAN WAS SET FOR THE PRIORITISED FUTURE STEPS THAT THE TEAM SHOULD FOLLOW TO ACTIVATE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN.</p> <p>TEAM C PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION (12/02/2024) AND THE FINALISED RESULT OF THE TEAM WAS EVALUATED AND THE LAST FEEDBACK WAS PROVIDED. A PLAN WAS SET FOR THE PRIORITISED FUTURE STEPS THAT THE TEAM SHOULD FOLLOW TO ACTIVATE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN.</p> <p>FOR COHORT 2:</p> <p>TEAM E PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION (22/03/2024) AND THE FINALISED RESULT OF THE TEAM WAS EVALUATED AND THE LAST FEEDBACK WAS PROVIDED. A PLAN WAS SET FOR THE PRIORITISED FUTURE STEPS THAT THE TEAM SHOULD FOLLOW TO ACTIVATE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN.</p> <p>TEAM F PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION (22/03/2024) AND THE FINALISED RESULT OF THE TEAM WAS EVALUATED AND THE LAST FEEDBACK WAS PROVIDED. A PLAN WAS SET FOR THE PRIORITISED FUTURE STEPS THAT THE TEAM SHOULD FOLLOW TO ACTIVATE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN.</p> <p>TEAM G PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION (23/04/2024) AND THE FINALISED RESULT OF THE TEAM WAS EVALUATED AND THE LAST FEEDBACK WAS PROVIDED. A PLAN WAS SET FOR THE PRIORITISED FUTURE STEPS THAT THE TEAM SHOULD FOLLOW TO ACTIVATE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN.</p> <p>TEAM H PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION (26/04/2024) AND THE FINALISED RESULT OF THE TEAM WAS EVALUATED AND THE LAST FEEDBACK WAS PROVIDED. A PLAN WAS SET FOR THE PRIORITISED FUTURE STEPS THAT THE TEAM SHOULD FOLLOW TO ACTIVATE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN.</p> <p>FOR COHORT 3:</p> <p>TEAM J PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION (18/07/2024) AND THE FINALISED RESULT OF THE TEAM WAS EVALUATED AND THE LAST FEEDBACK WAS PROVIDED. A PLAN WAS SET FOR THE PRIORITISED FUTURE STEPS THAT THE TEAM SHOULD FOLLOW TO ACTIVATE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN.</p> <p>TEAM K DID NOT MANAGE TO FIND A TIME AVAILABLE FOR THE PROVIDED SESSION. HOWEVER, THE TEAM WERE OFFERED THE OPTION TO SHARE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN AND QUESTIONS AND RECEIVE FEEDBACK FROM THE MENTOR ASYNCHRONOUSLY. THE MENTOR ALSO OFFERED AN OPTION FOR THE TEAM TO GET AN EXTRA HOUR OF INDIVIDUAL MENTORING AT A TIME OF THEIR CONVENIENCE, EVEN AFTER THE CONCLUSION OF THE PROJECT.</p> <p>TEAM L PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION (16/07/2024) AND THE FINALISED RESULT OF THE TEAM WAS EVALUATED AND THE LAST FEEDBACK WAS PROVIDED. A PLAN WAS SET FOR THE PRIORITISED FUTURE STEPS THAT THE TEAM SHOULD FOLLOW TO ACTIVATE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN.</p>
RESULTS	

THE TEAM N PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION (26/07/2024) AND THE FINALISED RESULT OF THE TEAM WAS EVALUATED AND THE LAST FEEDBACK WAS PROVIDED. A PLAN WAS SET FOR THE PRIORITISED FUTURE STEPS THAT THE TEAM SHOULD FOLLOW TO ACTIVATE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN.

TEAM O DID NOT MANAGE TO FIND A TIME AVAILABLE FOR THE PROVIDED SESSION. HOWEVER, THE TEAM WERE OFFERED THE OPTION TO SHARE THEIR BUSINESS PLAN AND QUESTIONS AND RECEIVE FEEDBACK FROM THE MENTOR ASYNCHRONOUSLY. THE MENTOR ALSO OFFERED AN OPTION FOR THE TEAM TO GET AN EXTRA HOUR OF INDIVIDUAL MENTORING AT A TIME OF THEIR CONVENIENCE, EVEN AFTER THE CONCLUSION OF THE PROJECT.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

4.6 CLEANTECH BULGARIA – ACCESS TO FINANCE AND RELATED FUNDING

TRAINING VIDEOS

STRUCTURE

THE TRAINING VIDEOS SERVE AS THE INITIAL MENTORING ELEMENT, WITH EACH OF THE THREE VIDEOS LASTING ABOUT ONE HOUR, A TOTAL OF APPROXIMATELY THREE HOURS OF VIDEO MATERIAL IS PROVIDED. THE MENTORS PRE-RECORD THE VIDEOS, WHICH ARE THEN LINKED TO ON THE F6S PLATFORM.

GOAL

THE TRAINING VIDEOS AIM TO INTRODUCE THE MENTEES INTO THE TOPIC OF THE MODULE AND PROVIDE THEM WITH A BASIC UNDERSTANDING OF THE ESSENTIAL COMPONENTS OF THE MODULE. THE FIRST VIDEO SERVES AS AN INTRODUCTORY SESSION TO THE TOPIC OF THE MENTORING MODULE. THE SECOND VIDEO DELVES DEEPER INTO THE MODULE'S TOPICS, WHILE THE FINAL VIDEO FOCUSES ON THE MOST COMPLEX ASPECTS COVERED IN THE MENTORING MODULE.

CONTENT

VIDEO 1: IN THIS INTRODUCTORY VIDEO, PARTICIPANTS EMBARK ON A JOURNEY TO GAIN A PROFOUND UNDERSTANDING OF THE MULTIFACETED FUNDING LANDSCAPE AVAILABLE FOR STARTUPS. DELVING INTO VARIOUS FINANCING OPTIONS, INCLUDING CROWDFUNDING, GRANTS, LOANS, ANGEL INVESTMENTS, VENTURE CAPITAL, AND BOOTSTRAPPING, THE VIDEO METICULOUSLY EXPLORES THE IMPLICATIONS, ADVANTAGES, AND DRAWBACKS OF EACH FUNDING AVENUE. THE ULTIMATE OBJECTIVE IS TO EQUIP THE ENTREPRENEURS WITH THE KNOWLEDGE NEEDED TO IDENTIFY AND DIFFERENTIATE FUNDING OPTIONS TAILORED TO DIFFERENT STAGES OF THEIR STARTUP'S LIFECYCLE. THIS FOUNDATIONAL KNOWLEDGE SETS THE STAGE FOR THEIR VENTURE INTO THE DYNAMIC REALM OF STARTUP FUNDING.

VIDEO 2: THIS VIDEO GUIDES THE PARTICIPANTS THROUGH THE PROCESS OF ACCURATELY ASSESSING THE FINANCIAL NEEDS OF THEIR STARTUPS. OVER THE COURSE OF THE SESSION, PARTICIPANTS DELVE INTO KEY ASPECTS OF FINANCIAL PLANNING ESSENTIAL FOR STARTUP SUSTAINABILITY. THE VIDEO COVERS THE DEVELOPMENT OF A ROBUST FINANCIAL MODEL, FORECASTING REVENUE AND EXPENSES, AND DETERMINING CRITICAL CASH FLOW NEEDS. BY PROVIDING PRACTICAL TIPS ON CREATING REALISTIC AND CONVINCING FINANCIAL PROJECTIONS, PARTICIPANTS GAIN THE SKILLS NECESSARY TO NAVIGATE THE FINANCIAL INTRICACIES OF THEIR VENTURES. THE OVERARCHING GOAL IS TO EMPOWER PARTICIPANTS TO DEVELOP A COMPREHENSIVE UNDERSTANDING OF THEIR STARTUP'S FINANCIAL REQUIREMENTS, A PIVOTAL STEP TOWARD SECURING THE NECESSARY FUNDING FOR GROWTH.

VIDEO 3: THIS VIDEO ALLOWS PARTICIPANTS TO EMBARK ON A JOURNEY TO MASTER THE ART OF PRESENTING AN IMPACTFUL INVESTMENT PITCH. THEY ARE INTRODUCED TO THE SKILLS NEEDED TO ARTICULATE A UNIQUE SELLING PROPOSITION, PERSUASIVELY CONVEY FINANCIAL NEEDS, AND EFFECTIVELY COMMUNICATE GROWTH POTENTIAL. THE

VIDEO UNFOLDS WITH AN EXPLORATION OF INVESTOR EXPECTATIONS, PROVIDING VALUABLE INSIGHTS INTO THE MINDSET OF INVESTORS AND THE KEY ELEMENTS THAT ATTRACT THEM. IT THEN TRANSITIONS INTO THE ART OF CRAFTING AN ENGAGING NARRATIVE, HIGHLIGHTING THE IMPORTANCE OF STORYTELLING IN A PITCH AND THE FUNDAMENTAL STRUCTURE OF A COMPELLING PRESENTATION. THIS VIDEO SERVES AS AN INVALUABLE RESOURCE FOR ANYONE SEEKING TO REFINE THEIR PITCH-PERFECT SKILLS AND NAVIGATE THE CHALLENGING TERRAIN OF STARTUP FUNDRAISING WITH CONFIDENCE.

FOR **COHORT 1, 2, & 3** ALL THREE TRAINING VIDEOS HAVE BEEN PROVIDED BY THE MENTORING ORGANISATION AND HAVE BEEN CONSUMED BY THE MENTEES.

RESULTS

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 3H

Quiz

STRUCTURE

ON THE F6S PLATFORM, A MULTIPLE-CHOICE QUIZ WAS IMPLEMENTED FOR EVERY MENTORING MODULE. THE AMOUNT OF QUESTIONS RANGED BETWEEN 24 AND 30. THE QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE THREE MENTORING VIDEOS. IT WAS ESTIMATED THAT THE COMPLETION OF ONE QUIZ TAKES ONE HOUR.

GOAL

THE QUIZ IS NON-MANDATORY BUT AIMS TO TEST THE MENTEES UNDERSTANDING OF MENTORING VIDEOS TO THEN FOCUS IN THE FOLLOWING MENTORING PROCESS ON AREAS WHERE THE PERFORMANCE IN THE QUIZ WAS LACKING.

CONTENT

THE QUIZ INCLUDES BOTH THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL QUESTIONS RELATED TO THE CONTENT PRESENTED IN THE 3 VIDEOS OF THE MODULE. THE QUESTIONS ARE FORMED IN A WAY THAT MAKES IT EASY TO VERIFY WHETHER THE MENTEES HAVE INDEED WATCHED THE VIDEOS, AND TO IDENTIFY SPECIFIC AREAS ON WHICH THE TEAMS MAY NEED EXTRA CLARIFICATIONS.

UNFORTUNATELY, NONE OF THE TEAMS OF **COHORT 1** COMPLETED THE QUIZ.

RESULTS

FOR **COHORT 2** THE QUIZ WAS COMPLETED BY TEAM G.

FOR **COHORT 3** THE QUIZ WAS COMPLETED BY TEAM J, K & M.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

WORKSHOP

STRUCTURE

THE WORKSHOP SESSION IS THE FIRST LIVE INTERACTION OF THE MENTOR AND THE MENTEES. THE SESSION IS HELD ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE WORKSHOP SESSION HAS A DURATION OF 2 HOURS AND IS OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES.

GOAL

IN THE WORKSHOP, THE DIFFERENT MENTEES CAN APPLY THE THEORETICAL CONCEPTS LEARNED IN THE TRAINING VIDEOS TO THEIR OWN BUSINESS ENDEAVOURS.

CONTENT	<p>THE WORKSHOP FOCUSED ON PROVIDING THE MENTEES WITH AN IN-DEPTH UNDERSTANDING OF FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES AT THEIR CURRENT DEVELOPMENT LEVEL.</p> <p>ALL FOUR TEAMS OF COHORT 1 PARTICIPATED IN THE WORKSHOP AND UNDERSTOOD ITS CONTENT.</p> <p>FOR COHORT 2 REPRESENTATIVES FROM 3 TEAMS (G; E; F) TOOK PART IN THE SESSION.</p> <p>FOR COHORT 3 ONLY TEAM K PARTICIPATED LIVE IN THE WORKSHOP AND THE REST OF THE TEAMS WERE PROVIDED WITH A RECORDING .</p>
RESULTS	<p>THE WORKSHOP FOR COHORT 1 HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 23/11/2023.</p> <p>THE WORKSHOP FOR COHORT 2 HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 12/02/2024.</p> <p>THE WORKSHOP FOR COHORT 3 HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 31/05/2024.</p> <p>TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H</p>

Q&A SESSION

STRUCTURE	<p>THE Q&A SESSION WAS FACILITATED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THE DURATION OF THE SESSION WAS 1 HOUR AND OPEN FOR ALL MENTEES TO ENTER AND ASK QUESTIONS ABOUT MENTORING RELATED TOPICS.</p>
GOAL	<p>THE Q&A SESSION AIMS TO PROVIDE THE MENTEES WITH AN OPPORTUNITY TO ASK QUESTIONS AND TO SOLVE DOUBTS RAISED FROM THE PREVIOUS TRAINING VIDEOS AND WORKSHOP.</p>
CONTENT	<p>FOR COHORT 1 THE Q&A WAS SPLIT TO TWO SESSIONS FOR THE CONVENIENCE OF THE PARTICIPATING TEAMS. THERE GENERAL TOPICS WERE DISCUSSED.</p> <p>ONLY THE TEAMS B AND C PARTICIPATED IN THE Q&A SESSION. THEY INFORMED THE MENTOR THAT DUE TO EXTERNAL CIRCUMSTANCES THEY WERE NOT ABLE TO KEEP UP WITH THE CONTENT OF THE MENTORING MODULE AND WOULD LIKE TO POSTPONE THE UPCOMING INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS BY A BIT. THIS POINT OF VIEW WAS SHARED BY CLEANTECH, AND IT WAS DECIDED TO RESCHEDULE THE UPCOMING INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS.</p> <p>FOR COHORT 2 ONLY A REPRESENTATIVE FROM THE F TEAM PARTICIPATED IN THE SESSION.</p>
RESULTS	<p>FOR COHORT 3 NO TEAMS JOINED THE DEDICATED SESSION.</p> <p>THE SESSIONS FOR COHORT 1 HAVE BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 15/12/2023.</p> <p>THE SESSION FOR COHORT 2 HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 19/02/2024.</p> <p>THE SESSION FOR COHORT 3 HAS BEEN CONDUCTED ON THE 07/06/2024.</p> <p>TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H</p>

INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

TWO INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS FOR EACH TEAM, EACH WITH A DURATION OF ONE HOUR, WERE OFFERED ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR, LEADING TO A TOTAL OF TWO HOURS OF MENTORING PER TEAM. IN THESE SESSIONS ONLY, THE MENTORS AND ONE TEAM ARE PRESENT TO FOCUS ON THEIR SPECIFIC NEEDS AND ISSUES.

GOAL

THE INDIVIDUAL MENTORING SESSIONS PROVIDE PERSONALISED GUIDANCE TO EACH TEAM, HELPING THEM OVERCOME SPECIFIC OBSTACLES ENCOUNTERED DURING CRITICAL PHASES OF THEIR COMPANIES. THIS ASSISTANCE AIDS IN DEVELOPING EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR THE FUTURE.

CONTENT

DURING THE INDIVIDUAL SESSION, THE MENTOR ADDRESSES SPECIFIC NEEDS OF THE MENTEE RELATED TO THE MODULE. THIS CAN RANGE FROM IDENTIFYING SUITABLE FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES TO APPROACHING POTENTIAL INVESTORS.

FOR COHORT 1:

THE TEAM A COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY DID NOT GET A RESPONSE. HENCE, THE TEAM A DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

THE TEAM B PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS BMC (13/02/2024 & 20/02/2024). THROUGHOUT THE DURATION OF THE SESSIONS, SUITABLE OPPORTUNITIES FOR FUNDING (SUCH AS GRANTS, INVESTMENTS, AND PARTICIPATION IN OTHER PROGRAMMES) WERE EXPLORED. FURTHER, THE MENTEES THEIR MAIN INTEREST WAS ON INVESTORS, SO PLATFORMS WITH ADDITIONAL LEARNING RESOURCES AND MASTERCLASSES ON THE INVESTOR'S MINDSET AND APPROACH WERE EXPLORED

THE TEAM C PARTICIPATED IN BOTH SESSIONS (09/02/2024 & 16/02/2024). THE MENTEE EXPRESSED A MAIN INTEREST IN OPPORTUNITIES FOR OBTAINING FUNDING. AS A RESULT, THE SESSIONS WERE FOCUSED ON EXPLORING PLATFORMS (SUCH AS F6S AND LOCAL OPPORTUNITIES) AND PROGRAMMES (INCLUDING HORIZON EUROPE, EIT, EIC, AND LOCAL OPPORTUNITIES). MULTIPLE PROGRAMMES FOR THE CONTINUATION OF THE MOMENTUM THEY OBTAINED DURING THEIR PARTICIPATION IN THE ENTREPRENEDEDU PROGRAMMES WERE IDENTIFIED. GOALS WERE SET, AND C AIMED TO APPLY TO AT LEAST ONE NEW PROGRAMME FOR ADDITIONAL COACHING AND FUNDING OF THEIR PROJECT

RESULTS

THE TEAM D COMMUNICATED THAT THEY HAD ISSUES TO ATTEND THE MENTORING SESSIONS. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE TEAM DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE TEAM D DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

FOR COHORT 2:

THE TEAM E COMPLETED BOTH OF THEIR INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS THAT TOOK PLACE ON THE 27/02/2024 AND 05/03/2024. AT THE BEGINNING, THEY SHARED THAT THE TEAM IS CURRENTLY NOT FULLY DEDICATED TO WORKING ON THE IDEA AND DECIDED TO PUT IT ON PAUSE. SOME OF THE TEAM MEMBERS HAVE BEEN INTERESTED MORE ON THE RESEARCH PART AND WERE NOT WILLING TO INVEST TIME IN THE BUSINESS SIDE. THERE WAS ONE TEAM MEMBER CONTRIBUTING ON HER OWN, SO WE DISCUSSED OPPORTUNITIES FOR SUPPORT (FINDING NEW TEAM MEMBERS, PARTICIPATING IN LOCAL AND INTERNATIONAL PROGRAMMES, FINDING FUNDING IN THE FORM OF GRANTS

ETC.) DURING OUR SECOND SESSION WE FOCUSED ON EXPLORING MORE IN DETAIL FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES OFFERED BY ESA, EIC, EIT AND THE HORIZON EUROPE PROGRAMME. ADDITIONALLY, WE DISCUSSED LOCAL OPPORTUNITIES AND THE NETWORK OF NATIONAL CONTACT POINTS IN GREECE THAT CAN BE OF FURTHER HELP WHEN APPLYING FOR EU FUNDING.

THE TEAM F PARTICIPATED IN BOTH OF THEIR INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS THAT TOOK PLACE ON THE 27/02/2024 AND 05/03/2024. WE STARTED THE FIRST SESSION BY EXPLORING THEIR CURRENT LEVEL OF DEVELOPMENT (PLANNING TO START ON THE PROGRAMMING OF THE PRODUCT) AND THE TEAM INFORMED US THAT THEY WILL BE PARTICIPATING IN AN INCUBATOR WHICH WILL PROVIDE SUPPORT AND FUNDING. AFTER ANSWERING A COUPLE OF QUESTIONS, WE AGREED THAT OUR FIRST SESSION WILL BE SHORTER, AS THE TEAM DID NOT FEEL PREPARED FOR THE SESSION, AND WE HAVE TRANSFERRED THE REMAINING TIME FOR THE 2ND INDIVIDUAL SESSION. TWO TEAM MEMBERS JOINED THE SECOND SESSION AND CONTRIBUTED TO THE DISCUSSION. THEY SHARED THEIR CURRENT LEVEL OF IDEA DEVELOPMENT, AND WE FURTHER DISCUSSED SUITABLE OPPORTUNITIES FOR OPEN PROGRAMMES AND GRANTS. ADDITIONALLY, WE EXPLORED MORE THE TOPIC OF BUSINESS ANGELS AND LOANS, AS THOSE SEEM TO BE THE PREFERRED FUNDING OPTIONS BY THE TEAM. ADDITIONALLY, THE TEAM HAS ASKED QUESTIONS ON THEIR TARGETED MARKET THAT WE FURTHER DISCUSSED AND BACKED UP WITH SOME ALREADY EXISTING RESEARCH DATA THAT CAN HELP THEM DEFINE THE MARKET BETTER.

THE TEAM G HAVE PARTICIPATED IN BOTH OF THEIR INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS THAT TOOK PLACE ON 06/03/2024 AND 14.03.2024. THE TEAM SHARED UPDATES ON THE PROJECT AS THEY WERE WORKING ON THE PROTOTYPE. WE DISCUSSED INITIAL OPPORTUNITIES UNDER THE FORM OF GRANTS AND SUPPORT FROM THE UNIVERSITY. THE TEAM SHARED THAT THEY LACK BUSINESS SKILLS, SO WE DISCUSSED OPPORTUNITIES ON ATTRACTING NEW TEAM MEMBERS WITH EXPERTISE ON THAT. DURING THE SESSION, WE DISCUSSED IN MORE DETAIL THE NEXT IDENTIFIED STEPS BY THE TEAM IN TERMS OF THEIR FUNDING NEEDS. THE MENTOR GUIDED THE TEAM ON THEIR RESEARCH ON RESOURCES, EIC OPPORTUNITIES AND THE EIT JUMPSTARTER PROGRAMME. THE TEAM HAD THE CHANCE TO GO THROUGH THE APPLICATION FORM WITH THE MENTOR IN ORDER TO GET A GOOD GRASP OF WHAT IS NEEDED FOR THEM TO APPLY.

THE TEAM H PARTICIPATED IN BOTH INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS THAT TOOK PLACE ON THE 04/04/2024 AND 15.04.2024. IN THE FIRST SESSION, THE TEAM EXPLORED FURTHER THEIR GOALS OF SOFTWARE OPTIMISATION AND HARDWARE EXPANSION. AS THEY WERE STILL FIGURING OUT THEIR DESIRED BUSINESS MODEL, THE MENTOR SUPPORTED THEM TO FURTHER EXPLORE THE OPPORTUNITIES FOR BOOTSTRAPPING, GRANTS AND LOAN PROGRAMME FOR SMEs IN GREECE. DURING THE SECOND SESSION, THE TEAM ALREADY HAD IDENTIFIED SOME INVESTORS AND POTENTIAL SPONSORS, SO WE DISCUSSED THEIR APPROACH TO THAT MATTER. ADDITIONALLY, FOCUS WAS PUT ON THE ESPA PROGRAMME ON STRENGTHENING THE ESTABLISHMENT AND OPERATION FOR NEW SMEs WHICH WAS OF INTEREST TO THE TEAM.

THE TEAM I DECIDED TO NOT PARTICIPATE IN THE SESSIONS.

FOR COHORT 3:

THE TEAM J PARTICIPATED IN BOTH OF THEIR INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS THAT TOOK PLACE ON THE 17/06/2024 AND 01/07/2024. AS THE TEAM HAS PARTICIPATED IN MORE PROGRAMMES FOR SUPPORT, SINCE THEIR PARTICIPATION IN THE HACKATHON, THEY FIRST SHARED THEIR UPDATES ON THE STATUS OF DEVELOPMENT AS WELL AS THE NEW GOALS OF THE COMPANY. TOGETHER WITH THE MENTOR, THEY EXPLORED SUITABLE FUNDING SOURCES AND PARTNERSHIPS THAT CAN CONTRIBUTE TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF THEIR BUSINESS.

THE TEAM K PARTICIPATED IN BOTH OF THEIR INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS THAT TOOK PLACE ON THE 19/06/2024 AND 26/06/2024. THE TEAM SHARED MORE ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF THEIR IDEA SINCE THE HACKATHON, AS WELL AS ABOUT THEIR CURRENT GOALS AND OBJECTIVES. TOGETHER WITH THE MENTOR, THEY EXPLORED FUTURE OPPORTUNITIES FOR PROGRAMMES TO PARTICIPATE IN, NETWORKS TO EXPLORE FOR BETTER KNOWLEDGE ON

POTENTIAL PARTNERS AND VISIBILITY FOR THEIR PROJECT, AND FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES THAT ARE RELEVANT FOR THEIR CURRENT LEVEL OF DEVELOPMENT.

THE TEAM **L** PARTICIPATED IN BOTH OF THEIR INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS THAT TOOK PLACE ON THE 26/06/2024 AND 02/07/2024. AS AN ACTIVE BUSINESS, THE TEAM HAD VERY SPECIFIC QUESTIONS AND DESIRES FOR TOPICS TO BE DISCUSSED, THAT THE MENTOR COVERED DURING THE SESSIONS. THROUGHOUT THE SESSIONS A BIGGER FOCUS WAS PLACED ON GRANTS, INVESTORS, BUSINESS ANGELS, PUBLIC FUNDS AND FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES FOR MARKETING DEVELOPMENT.

THE TEAM **M** COMMUNICATED THAT THEIR BUSINESS HAD BEEN RESOLVED. THE MENTORING PARTNERS TRIED TO ENGAGE WITH THEM TO FIND A SOLUTION, BUT UNFORTUNATELY THE TEAM DECIDED TO NOT COMPLETE THIS MENTORING MODULE. HENCE, THE TEAM **I** DID NOT COMPLETE ANY INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS AND DID NOT CONTINUE WITH THIS MODULE FROM THIS POINT FORWARD.

THE TEAM **N** PARTICIPATED IN BOTH OF THEIR INDIVIDUAL SESSIONS THAT TOOK PLACE ON THE 12/07/2024 AND 19/07/2024. THE TEAM, TOGETHER WITH THE MENTOR, EXPLORED FURTHER THEIR FUNDING NEEDS AND THEIR MOST SUITING FUNDING SOURCES. ADDITIONALLY, POTENTIAL PARTNERSHIPS WERE DISCUSSED THAT CAN CONTRIBUTE TO THE CURRENT LEVEL OF DEVELOPMENT. DURING THE SECOND MEETING, THE TEAM SHOWED INTEREST IN OBTAINING MORE INFORMATION ABOUT SOME SPECIFIC FUNDING SOURCES THAT THE MENTOR FOCUSED ON DURING THE SESSION.

THE TEAM **O** PARTICIPATED ONLY IN THEIR FIRST INDIVIDUAL SESSION ON THE 12/07/2024. THEY ELABORATED FURTHER ON THEIR IDEA AND BUSINESS PLAN. AFTER THAT, GUIDED BY THE MENTOR, THEY EXPLORED THE MOST SUITABLE FUNDING SOURCES FOR THEIR BUSINESS. THEIR SECOND MEETING WAS SCHEDULED FOR THE 26/07/2024, BUT A DAY EARLIER THE TEAM DECIDED TO DROP OUT OF THE PROGRAMME.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 2H

REFLECTION SESSIONS

STRUCTURE

A ONE-HOUR REFLECTION SESSION WAS OFFERED TO ALL MENTEES ON AN ONLINE MEETING PLATFORM WHICH IS CHOSEN BY THE MENTOR. THIS SESSION FOCUSED ON PROVIDING FEEDBACK TO THE MENTEES AND MARKED THE END OF THIS MENTORING MODULE

GOAL

THE REFLECTION SESSION AIMS TO ENCOURAGE PARTICIPANTS TO PRACTISE SELF-ASSESSMENT AND REFLECTION, ENABLING THEM TO MONITOR THEIR PROGRESS, ACKNOWLEDGE THEIR ACHIEVEMENTS, AND IDENTIFY AREAS FOR FUTURE DEVELOPMENT.

CONTENT

FOR ALL 3 COHORTS, THE SESSION SERVED AS A DISCUSSION GROUND FOR ALL REMAINING QUESTIONS FROM THE MENTEE ABOUT FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES AND REFLECTION ON THE EXPERIENCE THROUGHOUT THE PROGRAMME.

For Cohort 1:

RESULTS

THE REFLECTION SESSION OF TEAM **B** TOOK PLACE ON THE 27/02/2024 AND OF TEAM **C** ON THE 01/03/2024. FEEDBACK ON THE INVOLVEMENT OF THE TEAM AS WELL AS ON THE PERFORMANCE AND GUIDANCE FROM THE MENTOR WAS EXCHANGED. THE TEAMS SHARED THAT THEY FOUND THE PROGRAMME VERY USEFUL AND THE MENTORS WERE VERY WELL PREPARED AND PROVIDED RELEVANT INFORMATION. BOTH TEAMS EXPRESSED WILLINGNESS TO SHARE THEIR TESTIMONIALS DURING THE INFO WEBINAR ORGANISED FOR THE 3RD HACKTHEBUSINESS EVENT IN ORDER TO MOTIVATE NEW STUDENTS TO TAKE THIS JOURNEY.

FOR COHORT 2:

THE TEAM E TOOK PART IN THEIR REFLECTION SESSION ON THE 12/03/2024 AND REFLECTED ON THEIR OVERALL EXPERIENCE FROM THE MODULE, AS WELL AS THEIR PLAN FOR THE NEXT YEAR ON OBTAINING FUNDING.

THE TEAM F TOOK PART IN THEIR REFLECTION SESSION ON THE 11/03/2024 AND REFLECTED ON THEIR OVERALL EXPERIENCE FROM THE MODULE, AS WELL AS THEIR PLAN FOR THE NEXT YEAR ON OBTAINING FUNDING.

THE TEAM G TOOK PART IN THEIR REFLECTION SESSION ON THE 21/03/2024 AND REFLECTED ON THEIR OVERALL EXPERIENCE FROM THE MODULE, AS WELL AS THEIR PLAN FOR THE NEXT YEAR ON OBTAINING FUNDING.

THE TEAM H TOOK PART IN THEIR REFLECTION SESSION ON THE 19/04/2024 AND REFLECTED ON THEIR OVERALL EXPERIENCE FROM THE MODULE, AS WELL AS THEIR PLAN FOR THE NEXT YEAR ON OBTAINING FUNDING.

THE TEAM I DECIDED TO NOT PARTICIPATE IN THE SESSIONS.

FOR COHORT 3:

THE TEAM J TOOK PART IN THEIR REFLECTION SESSION ON THE 05/07/2024 AND REFLECTED ON THEIR OVERALL EXPERIENCE FROM THE MODULE, AS WELL AS THEIR PLAN FOR THE NEXT YEAR ON OBTAINING FUNDING.

THE TEAM K TOOK PART IN THEIR REFLECTION SESSION ON THE 03/07/2024 AND REFLECTED ON THEIR OVERALL EXPERIENCE FROM THE MODULE, AS WELL AS THEIR PLAN FOR THE NEXT YEAR ON OBTAINING FUNDING.

THE TEAM L TOOK PART IN THEIR REFLECTION SESSION ON THE 16/07/2024 AND REFLECTED ON THEIR OVERALL EXPERIENCE FROM THE MODULE, AS WELL AS THEIR PLAN FOR THE NEXT YEAR ON OBTAINING FUNDING.

THE TEAM N TOOK PART IN THEIR REFLECTION SESSION ON THE 26/07/2024 AND REFLECTED ON THEIR OVERALL EXPERIENCE FROM THE MODULE, AS WELL AS THEIR PLAN FOR THE NEXT YEAR ON OBTAINING FUNDING.

THE TEAM O DECIDED TO NOT PARTICIPATE IN THEIR REFLECTION SESSION.

TOTAL DELIVERED MENTORING HOURS PER TEAM: 1H

4.7 FEEDBACK OF THE MENTEES

As part of the project's commitment to continuous improvement and to ensure the programme's alignment with the evolving needs of entrepreneurs, a comprehensive feedback collection process has been embarked upon the completion of the first cohort. This chapter is dedicated to presenting the insights garnered from this feedback, which is instrumental in refining and enhancing the programme for subsequent cohorts.

The feedback collected from the participants serves as a cornerstone for the understanding of the programme's impact, effectiveness, and areas requiring enhancement. Through a designed feedback guideline, the participants' experiences, challenges faced, and the learning outcomes achieved throughout their mentoring journey has been collected. The feedback guideline was structured to explore various dimensions of the programme, including the skills and knowledge they acquired, their progress and goal setting, their interaction with the mentorship community, and their overall satisfaction with the programme organisation.

This chapter aims to elucidate the methodology behind the feedback collection, summarise the key findings, and outline the measures that have been implemented or could be applied in future iterations of the programme to improve it.

4.7.1 METHODOLOGY FOR FEEDBACK COLLECTION

The feedback collection for the ENTREPRENEDEDU mentoring programme's first cohort was conducted with a qualitative approach to collect the participants' experiences. This process was designed and executed by two researchers from Fraunhofer, the partner responsible for the development and coordination of the mentoring programme. It was gathered through guided online video calls. This approach allowed for a more dynamic and interactive exchange of information, providing clearer insights into the participants' experiences, perceptions, and suggestions for improvement. The methodology was structured around a semi-structured feedback guideline, exploring the following eight sections:

Section 1 - Reflection on the Mentoring Journey: Participants were asked to articulate their start-up's initial vision and how their objectives evolved, providing insights into the mentoring programme's transformative impact. The guiding questions were:

- *Describe the initial vision and objectives for your start-up/team. How have these evolved over the course of the programme?*
- *Reflect on the inception of your future business. What were the key assumptions, and how have they been validated or revised?*

Section 2 - Overcoming Obstacles and Developing Skills: This section delved into the significant obstacles participants faced and the skills they developed, highlighting the programme's role in equipping them with necessary entrepreneurial competencies. The guiding questions were:

- *Identify the most significant challenges you faced while developing your start-up/team. How did you overcome these obstacles?*
- *Reflect on the skills and knowledge you have developed during the mentoring programme. Which of these do you consider most valuable for your future growth?*
- *How did the mentoring sessions and interactions with peers contribute to your journey? Provide examples of insights gained or changes implemented as a result.*

Section 3 - Business Model Evaluation: Participants evaluated their developed business model's effectiveness, discussing strengths, areas for improvement, and their competitive positioning in the market. The guiding questions were:

- *Assess the effectiveness of your developed business model. What are its strengths, and where does it need improvement?*

- *How does your business address the needs of your target market? Discuss any feedback received from potential customers or stakeholders and how it has shaped your approach.*
- *Considering the competitive landscape, how does your start-up/team differentiate itself? Is there a unique value proposition or innovation that sets you apart?*

Section 4 - Progress and Future Goals: Reflecting on their growth and future aspirations, participants were asked to share the success metrics they use, their goals, and how the programme has prepared them for upcoming entrepreneurial challenges. The guiding questions were:

- *How do you measure the success and impact of your start-up/team? Discuss any metrics or indicators you use to track progress.*
- *What are the short-term and long-term goals for your start-up/team? Outline the steps you plan to take to achieve these goals.*
- *Reflecting on the ENTREPRENEDU programme, how has it prepared you for the next stages of your entrepreneurial journey? Identify any gaps or additional support you may need moving forward.*

Section 5 - Learning from the Community: Insights were gathered on the advice and knowledge exchanged within the community, analysing the programme's collaborative learning environment. The guiding questions were:

- *Share a key learning or piece of advice you received from another participant or mentor that has impacted your start-up/team strategy.*
- *How do you envision contributing to the ENTREPRENEDU community and the wider entrepreneurial ecosystem in the future?*

Section 6 - Overall Satisfaction with the Mentoring Programme and Modules: The section sought participants' overall impressions of the programme and specific modules, gathering detailed feedback on what was most valuable and identifying areas for enhancement. The guiding questions were:

- *How satisfied are you with the overall ENTREPRENEDU mentoring programme?*
- *For each of the following modules, please rate your satisfaction on a scale of 1 to 5 (1 is not satisfied at all and 5 is extremely satisfied) and provide specific feedback on what you found valuable and areas for improvement.*
- *What aspects of the programme did you find most valuable? Please explain.*
- *Were there any areas of the programme you feel could be improved? Please provide specific suggestions.*

Section 7 - Technical and Organisational Feedback: Participants were asked about the technical and organisational aspects of the programme, such as the technical implementation in the platform as well as the scheduling process. The guiding questions were:

- *How well did the mentoring modules integrate with one another to provide a cohesive learning experience?*
- *How do you assess the technical implementation of the ENTREPRENEDU mentoring programme?*
- *How easy was it for you to schedule appointments with your mentors?*
- *Are there any additional topics or areas you wish were covered in the mentoring programme?*

Section 8 - Closing thoughts: The participants were asked if there are any other thoughts or reflections they would like to share that have not been covered by the previous questions. The guiding question was:

- *Are there any other thoughts or reflections you would like to share that have not been covered in this questionnaire?*

The feedback sessions were scheduled and conducted in February 2024, immediately following the conclusion of the first cohort, in conjunction with the reflection sessions of the module business model development led by Fraunhofer IPK. Each team was invited to a one-on-one online video call, which allowed for a personal and in-depth exploration of their experiences. The sessions were not only aimed at gathering structured feedback, but also at understanding the subtleties of each participant's entrepreneurial journey within the programme. Further, for Cohort 2 and 3 a feedback survey was developed that was shared with the participants after they finished the mentoring programme. The layout of this survey can be found in the appendix. The qualitative data collected through these sessions were then analysed by the researchers to identify common themes, insights, and areas of improvement. This analysis was instrumental in developing targeted recommendations for enhancing the ENTREPRENEDU mentoring programme for future cohorts and iterations.

4.7.2 PRESENTATION OF FEEDBACK RESULTS COHORT 1

This chapter details the feedback across key areas of the programme, encapsulating the entrepreneurial journey's essence as experienced by the participants of Cohort 1.

Section 1 - Reflection on the Mentoring Journey

Participants reported a development of their business ideas and models, highlighting the programme's effectiveness in steering their ideas towards greater feasibility and concrete business planning. The mentoring journey was described as transformative, with mentors playing a crucial role in challenging assumptions, offering guidance, and enabling the teams to refine their visions into more concrete businesses. This evolution was not just about the ideas themselves, but also about participants' mindsets towards a more strategic, market-oriented approach.

Section 2 - Overcoming Obstacles and Developing Skills

The feedback highlighted a variety of challenges faced by the teams, ranging from concerns about scalability to the complexities of integrating the learned modules into their strategic business planning effectively. The programme played an important role in enabling participants to surmount these hurdles by providing focused support to cultivate essential skills such as problem validation, value proposition creation, and proficient pitch delivery. These competencies were indispensable not only for the immediate refinement of their business ideas but also for growth in a competitive market environment. Nonetheless, one team, which was at the nascent stage of idea development upon entering the programme, expressed that it was challenging to grasp the interplay among the different modules and the sequence in which to apply them. They found it difficult to discern which video lesson to prioritize and how to systematically incorporate all the videos from the different modules in the correct sequence.

Section 3 - Business Model Evaluation

The teams identified specific needs for further improvement in their revenue streams, market awareness, and competitive differentiation. Through the mentoring process, value propositions were clarified and strengthened, enabling the teams to better position themselves in the market. The iterative feedback and validation process within the programme were highlighted as instrumental in refining these business model components, demonstrating the value of continuous mentorship and peer review.

Section 4 - Progress and Future Goals

Participants expressed appreciation for the programme's effectiveness in assisting them with establishing actionable short-term and long-term goals, as well as metrics for gauging their success. The feedback highlighted the critical nature of setting clear, measurable objectives and affirmed the programme's capability in readying teams for subsequent phases of their entrepreneurial journey. Nonetheless, the feedback also pinpointed gaps, particularly in the need for additional support in actualizing these plans, signalling a requirement for enhanced mentorship or resources in specific domains. Within this framework, one team identified a need for further assistance in securing grants or funding to realize their business idea. Additional expertise in specific areas, such as technological feasibility, was deemed beneficial to fortify confidence in certain aspects of their business model. Moreover, there was a recognized necessity for guidance in forming a robust team, including strategies related to human resources.

Section 5 - Learning from the Community

The invaluable role of mentors was consistently highlighted in the feedback, with their insights, advice, and support significantly enhancing the learning experience. This exchange cultivated a collaborative learning environment that participants greatly appreciated. When considering peer-to-peer learning, the feedback presented a dichotomy. While some participants were highly satisfied with the opportunity to engage with other teams and expressed a desire for more structured interaction opportunities, others noted that, due to diverse business backgrounds, their engagement was more fruitful with mentors than with

peers. Additionally, one team suggested spacing out the sessions for the various modules over a longer period. This approach would not extend the programme's overall duration but would allow for a more distributed and in-depth exploration of each module, offering participants additional time to absorb, implement, and reflect on the learnings between sessions.

Section 6 - Overall Satisfaction with the Mentoring Programme and Modules

The overall satisfaction with the ENTREPRENEDU mentoring programme, as reported by the participating teams, reflects a high level of satisfaction across the various modules, with most ratings being very satisfied (5 out of 5). A summary of the collective feedback and satisfaction ratings for each module is presented as follows:

Module 1: Business Model Development

Participants found significant value in the assistance provided to complete the business model canvas, highlighting the competence and availability of mentors. The guidance on effectively filling out the canvas was particularly appreciated, although there was feedback that the mentor's involvement sometimes made it challenging for participants to internalize the solutions independently.

Module 2: Crafting a Unique and Competitive Value Proposition

This module was highlighted as especially stimulating, with its interactive nature and practical tasks awakening a crucial understanding of value proposition among entrepreneurs. Participants suggested that idea validation, a core component of this module, would be more beneficial if placed at the very beginning of the programme.

Module 3: Your Idea Pitch: from Tech Feasibility to Product Development

The module was highly appreciated, highlighting the strong competence of the mentors, accompanied by a suggestion to separate the tech feasibility aspect from the idea pitch, as not all participants had a product already developed. It was proposed that the structuring of this module should consider the participants' readiness level more closely. Additionally, the recommendation to include technical guidance for product development was made to further enrich this module.

Module 4: Investment Pitch and Quantifying Your Funding Needs

The investment pitch module was very well-regarded, and participants highlighted especially the very precise and personalised feedback they received. However, it also highlighted a need for more foundational knowledge for some participants.

Module 5: Entrepreneurial Business Planning

The business planning module was praised for its interactivity and the extensive input provided. Participants appreciated the opportunity for discussions and the engaging approach of the module, which stimulated significant thought and reflection on their business planning.

Module 6: Access to Finance and Related Funding

Feedback for this module underscored its straightforward and concrete approach to addressing finance and funding, with adaptations made to fit the situation of the participants. The practical focus of this module was particularly valued.

Section 7: Technical and Organisational Feedback

Teams acknowledged the mentoring modules' role in providing a cohesive learning experience, though they suggested improvements for better integration. The sequence of modules, particularly the placement of problem validation early in the programme, was noted as an area for improvement. Feedback indicated that an early focus on problem validation could lead to more meaningful shifts in business ideas, suggesting a need for clearer guidance on how different modules interact and complement each other.

The technical aspect of the programme was generally well-received, with the platform described as satisfactory and the process for accessing materials like videos being straightforward.

Scheduling appointments emerged as a significant challenge, primarily due to the use of multiple emails and channels, which led to confusion and scheduling difficulties. The feedback strongly suggests the need for a unified scheduling process to streamline communication and make it easier for participants to manage their interactions with mentors, especially considering the constraints of participants' work schedules.

While not all teams specified unaddressed areas, there was a clear call for the inclusion of topics related to HR Management and Leadership. Specifically, guidance on hiring and managing a team was identified as a critical area for additional content, underscoring the need for entrepreneurial leadership skills alongside the programme's existing focus areas.

4.7.3 PRESENTATION OF FEEDBACK RESULTS COHORT 2

The feedback from Cohort 2 of the ENTREPRENUEDU Mentoring Programme highlights a strong appreciation for the programme's comprehensive and well-structured modules, with teams expressing high levels of satisfaction. Teams consistently rated the overall experience highly, with many expressing extreme satisfaction. The feedback indicates that the programme successfully provided valuable insights and practical knowledge across various modules. Module 1: Business Model Development, led by Fraunhofer IPK, was particularly well-received, with teams appreciating the expert guidance and the depth of information provided. Modules focusing on idea pitching, investment pitch, and entrepreneurial business planning were also rated highly, reflecting the programme's strength in these areas.

Overall, Cohort 2 awarded the programme an outstanding rating of 4.7 out of 5. One team highlighted the value of the workshops and practical projects, which allowed them to apply theoretical knowledge with the support of professional feedback. This hands-on approach was seen as extremely beneficial, especially for those with technical backgrounds who were looking to expand their understanding of the financial aspects of a startup. In closing, teams reflected positively on their experience, noting the effective integration of the modules and

the ease of navigating the programme. The mentoring programme was highly valued for its practical insights and professional support.

While the overall feedback was overwhelmingly positive, participants did suggest several areas for improvement to further enhance the learning experience. Teams recommended extending the deadlines for video assignments to allow participants more time to prepare and refine their presentations, ensuring they can fully benefit from the feedback provided during the individual meetings. Some participants expressed a desire for additional sessions within certain modules, such as the Value Proposition module, to cover more ground and provide a deeper understanding of the topics discussed in the Value Proposition module. To better accommodate the busy schedules of university students and working professionals, respondents suggested reducing the density of the general lessons. This adjustment would make the content more manageable and allow participants to engage with the material more effectively.

There was also a suggestion to make some content available for later review. This flexibility would enable participants to revisit and digest the information at their own pace, enhancing their learning experience. Additionally, ensuring that all planned sessions are conducted as scheduled was highlighted as an area for improvement. Participants felt that missing sessions, such as the third session in the Value Proposition module, detracted from the overall learning experience.

Overall, the feedback from Cohort 2 underscores the programme's success in delivering valuable entrepreneurial education and mentorship. The suggestions for improvement reflect the participants' engagement and commitment to making the programme even more effective and beneficial for future cohorts.

4.7.4 PRESENTATION OF FEEDBACK RESULTS COHORT 3

The feedback from Cohort 3 of the ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring Programme reflects a high level of satisfaction with the programme's structure and delivery, mirroring the positive reception seen in previous cohorts. Participants consistently rated the modules highly, with many expressing that the programme provided them with valuable insights and practical knowledge essential for entrepreneurial success. Module 1: Business Model Development, led by Fraunhofer IPK, received high praise, with participants noting the expert guidance and comprehensive content as major strengths. This module was consistently rated as "Extremely Satisfied" by multiple respondents. Module 2: Crafting a Unique and Competitive Value Proposition, led by LUISS, was also well-received, with high satisfaction ratings. Participants appreciated the depth of information, though some suggested a need for additional focus to prevent overlap with other modules. Module 3: Your Idea Pitch: from Tech Feasibility to Product Development, led by FEA, garnered positive feedback, with most teams finding the content practical and beneficial for refining their pitches. Module 4: Investment Pitch and Quantifying Your Funding Needs, led by EBAN, was highlighted for its effectiveness in

preparing teams for funding pitches, though there were suggestions for more detailed coverage. Modules 5 and 6, Entrepreneurial Business Planning by Corallia and Access to Finance and Related Funding by Cleantech Bulgaria, received uniformly high ratings, with participants noting the practical value and the clarity of the instruction provided.

Overall, Cohort 3 participants rated the overall programme highly, with most expressing extreme satisfaction. The programme's systematic approach and the lean startup methodology were particularly valued, as they provided a structured framework for developing their startups. While the feedback was overwhelmingly positive, several areas for improvement were suggested. Participants recommended extending the programme duration to allow more time for absorbing the material and applying the knowledge effectively. Some feedback indicated a desire for better integration of modules to reduce content overlap and enhance the learning flow. Additionally, a few participants found scheduling appointments challenging due to platform limitations and suggested more flexible arrangements to better accommodate their schedules.

The technical implementation of the programme was praised for its user-friendly interface and responsive support, which facilitated a smooth learning experience. Participants suggested incorporating additional topics such as brainstorming sessions to further enhance the programme's comprehensiveness. In conclusion, Cohort 3's feedback underscores the ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring Programme's success in delivering valuable entrepreneurial training while also providing actionable suggestions for future improvements.

4.7.5 SUMMARY OF IMPLEMENTED MEASURES AND IMPROVEMENTS

This chapter details the feedback across key areas of the programme, encapsulating the entrepreneurial journey's essence as experienced by the participants. Hereby, the feedback from all three Cohorts is presented in table 2. The first column illustrates from which Cohorts the feedback as received. Further, table 2 highlights actions that have been derived from the feedback. Implementing these measures and addressing the areas for improvement, will lead to an improvement in engaging participants, fostering collaboration, and achieving positive outcomes for all stakeholders involved.

TABLE 2: Summary of Improvements for the ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring Programme

COHORT	ENHANCEMENTS TO THE MENTORING JOURNEY	STATUS OF MEASURES	
1 & 3	STRUCTURED INTEGRATION OF MODULES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DEVELOP CLEARER GUIDELINES ON THE SEQUENCE AND INTERPLAY OF DIFFERENT MODULES TO AID PARTICIPANTS IN EFFECTIVELY INCORPORATING LEARNED CONCEPTS INTO THEIR BUSINESS PLANNING. PRIORITISE PROBLEM VALIDATION AT THE PROGRAMME'S OUTSET TO ENCOURAGE IMMEDIATE AND IMPACTFUL IDEATIONAL SHIFTS. 	<p>DUE TO THE PROGRAMME, TAKING PART ONLINE AND THE EXECUTION OF DIFFERENT MODULES SIMULTANEOUSLY, IT IS NOT POSSIBLE TO READJUST THE STRUCTURE DURING THIS PROJECT. HOWEVER, FUTURE</p>

			ITERATIONS COULD APPLY THIS SUGGESTION.
1	INCREASED MENTOR ENGAGEMENT IN IDEA DEVELOPMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FOSTER A BALANCE BETWEEN MENTOR INVOLVEMENT AND PARTICIPANT AUTONOMY IN THE BUSINESS MODEL DEVELOPMENT PROCESS TO ENSURE PARTICIPANTS INTERNALISE SOLUTIONS INDEPENDENTLY WHILE BENEFITING FROM EXPERT GUIDANCE. 	THE SUGGESTED MEASURE HAS BEEN IMPLEMENTED
SKILL DEVELOPMENT AND BUSINESS EVALUATION			
1	MODULAR READINESS ADAPTATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TAILOR MODULES SUCH AS "YOUR IDEA PITCH: FROM TECH FEASIBILITY TO PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT" TO PARTICIPANTS' READINESS LEVELS, PARTICULARLY DISTINGUISHING BETWEEN THOSE WITH AND WITHOUT DEVELOPED PRODUCTS. INCORPORATE TECHNICAL GUIDANCE FOR PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT AS AN INTEGRAL COMPONENT OF RELEVANT MODULES. 	THE SUGGESTED MEASURE HAS BEEN IMPLEMENTED
1	FOUNDATION KNOWLEDGE ENHANCEMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IN MODULES LIKE THE "INVESTMENT PITCH AND QUANTIFYING YOUR FUNDING NEEDS" INCORPORATE MORE FOUNDATIONAL KNOWLEDGE CONTENT TO ENSURE ALL PARTICIPANTS, REGARDLESS OF THEIR STARTING POINT, CAN FULLY ENGAGE WITH AND BENEFIT FROM THE SESSIONS. 	THE SUGGESTED MEASURE HAS BEEN IMPLEMENTED
PROGRAMME STRUCTURE AND DELIVERY			
1, 2 & 3	EXTENDED MODULE DURATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WITHOUT PROLONGING THE PROGRAMME'S OVERALL DURATION, EXTEND THE SPACING BETWEEN SESSIONS, IF POSSIBLE, TO ALLOW DEEPER ABSORPTION AND REFLECTION OF THE CONTENT. THIS PACING WOULD ENABLE PARTICIPANTS TO APPLY LEARNINGS MORE EFFECTIVELY BETWEEN SESSIONS. 	WHENEVER IT WAS POSSIBLE, THE TIME BETWEEN THE DIFFERENT SESSIONS HAS BEEN EXPANDED. HOWEVER, DUE TO TIME CONSTRAINTS ON THE MENTORS SIDE AND THE PROJECTS DEADLINES THIS WAS NOT ALWAYS POSSIBLE
2 & 3	ADDITIONAL SESSIONS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FOR SOME MODULES SUCH AS THE "VALUE PROPOSITION MODULE" ADDITIONAL SESSIONS WOULD BE BENEFICIAL TO THE VALUE PROPOSITION MODULE. FURTHER, BRAINSTORMING SESSIONS CAN 	DUE TO THE INITIAL OUTSET OF THE CURRICULUM AND PROJECT, IT WAS

		<p>BE IMPLEMENTED TO FURTHER ENHANCE THE PROGRAMME'S COMPREHENSIVENESS.</p>	<p>NOT POSSIBLE TO GENERALLY ADD A SPECIFIC SESSION TO A MODULE. HOWEVER, THE TEAMS WERE OFFERED ADDITIONAL SESSIONS AFTER THE INITIAL COMPLETION OF THE PROGRAMME.</p>
2	CONTENT AVAILABILITY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RECORDING SESSIONS SUCH AS THE WORKSHOP AND MAKING IT AVAILABLE FOR THE PARTICIPANTS ENABLES THEM TO REVISIT AND DIGEST THE INFORMATION AT THEIR OWN PACE, ENHANCING THEIR LEARNING EXPERIENCE. 	<p>THE SUGGESTED MEASURE HAS BEEN IMPLEMENTED</p>
1 & 3	UNIFIED SCHEDULING SYSTEM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> IMPLEMENT A STREAMLINED, UNIFIED SCHEDULING PROCESS TO REDUCE CONFUSION AND ENHANCE THE EASE OF ARRANGING MENTORSHIP APPOINTMENTS, ACCOMMODATING THE DIVERSE SCHEDULES OF PARTICIPANTS. 	<p>THE SUGGESTED MEASURE HAS BEEN IMPLEMENTED</p>
CURRICULAR EXPANSION			
1	INCLUSION OF LEADERSHIP AND HR MANAGEMENT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> EXPAND THE CURRICULUM TO INCLUDE MODULES ON HR MANAGEMENT AND LEADERSHIP, PROVIDING VITAL SKILLS IN TEAM FORMATION AND MANAGEMENT, CRUCIAL FOR THE GROWTH AND SCALABILITY OF START-UP VENTURES. 	<p>THE SUGGESTED MEASURE HAS BEEN DEVELOPED AND CAN BE EXPLORED IN DELIVERABLE 4.4. MENTORING MODULES – FINAL RELEASE FUTURE ITERATIONS OF THE PROGRAMME COULD APPLY THE NEW MODULE.</p>
TECHNICAL AND ORGANISATIONAL FEEDBACK IMPLEMENTATION			
1	PLATFORM AND ACCESS IMPROVEMENTS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> WHILE THE TECHNICAL PLATFORM WAS GENERALLY SATISFACTORY, EXPLORE OPPORTUNITIES TO ENHANCE USER INTERACTION AND EASE OF ACCESSING MATERIALS, ENSURING A SEAMLESS LEARNING EXPERIENCE. 	<p>THE SUGGESTED MEASURE HAS BEEN IMPLEMENTED</p>

5 RESULTS OF THE MENTORING PROGRAMME

The high scalability of the mentoring programme should ensure sustainable outcomes for the 12 finalists. By the end of the programme, the participants were expected to achieve one or more of the following four key milestones. They should define tailored business models and develop comprehensive business plans at the European level, enabling effective pitches to potential investors and partners. Additionally, participants are expected to apply for various regional initiatives and European financial support instruments, such as the ERDF, EIC Pilot, Start Up Europe, and Invest Horizon. Creating impactful pitch presentations and identifying investor events to engage with private stakeholders is another key objective. Finally, participants should identify and enrol in further acceleration programmes at regional, national, and European levels to support the continued development and commercialization of their innovative ideas. Achieving these milestones will demonstrate the programme's effectiveness in fostering sustainable growth and impactful contributions to the European innovation ecosystem.

The programme's structured guidance has enabled participants to achieve the following outcomes:

Definition of a tailored business model and elaboration of a business plan at European level

Partner Facilitators: IPK & Luiss (Business Models) and Corallia (Business Plans).

This objective involved helping start-ups define customised business models and develop comprehensive business plans tailored for European markets, which can be used for pitching to investors and seeking partners. The business models included key components of the Business Model Canvas: customer segments, value propositions, channels, customer relationships, revenue streams, key resources, key activities, key partnerships, and cost structure. The business plans included executive summary, team/company presentation, product/service description, market analysis, competition analysis, business model, activities schedule, and financial projections, positioning the teams for successful expansion. This has been achieved for the following teams:

Cohort 1:

- Business Models: B, C, D
- Business Plans: B, C

Cohort 2:

- Business Models: E, F, G, H
- Business Plans: E, F, G, H

Cohort 3:

- Business Models: J, K, L, N, O
- Business Plans: J, L, N

Application to one or more Regional initiatives and/or European financial support instruments

Partner Facilitators: EBAN & Cleantech.

This objective supported teams in applying to one or more regional initiatives (e.g., ERDF, clusters, network) and/or European financial support instruments (e.g., EIC Pilot, Start Up Europe, Invest Horizon). The startups were presented with the different European Financial instruments they could leverage for the development of their projects as well as EU projects that could support them (for instance Women TechEU). Whilst none of the startups applied to them during the course of the mentoring programme, EBAN offered each team the possibility to reach out to the mentor in case they would need any assistance for future applications. EBAN also offered similar support for any applications to pitching events and other similar types of competitions. The mentor from EBAN offered this opportunity to all the participants of the Mentoring Programme:

- Cohort 1: B, C
- Cohort 2: E, F, G, H,
- Cohort 3: J, K, L, N

Definition of a pitch presentation and identification of investors events

Partner Facilitators: FEA & Cleantech.

This objective involved helping teams develop compelling pitch presentations and identify key investor events to participate in and/or attract private stakeholders. Facilitated by FEA and Cleantech, this effort equipped the teams to effectively engage with potential investors and stakeholders. The definition of a pitch presentation has been achieved for the following teams:

- Cohort 1: B, C
- Cohort 2: E, F, G, H, I
- Cohort 3: K, J, L, N, O

For all these teams a series of investor events have been identified (e.g. [Rome Startup Week](#), [Spring of Innovation](#), [8th Cassini Hackathon](#), [We Make Future](#), etc.). Specific communications are planned to be sent once the registration to the pitch competitions will be launched online.

Identification and enrolment in further acceleration programmes

Partner Facilitator: Cleantech.

This objective supported teams in identifying and enrolling in additional acceleration programmes at regional, national, and European levels to continue the deployment and commercialization of their ideas. This has been achieved for the following teams:

- Cohort 1: C (EIT Jumpstarter)
- Cohort 2: E (ESA BIC, EIT Jumpstarter), F (EIT Jumpstarter), G (ESA BIC; Acceleration program organized by Athens University of Economics and Business)
- Cohort 3: J (AgriVenture Start; Sofia Tech Park SEE program), K (Business Academy for Startup Entrepreneurs (BASE); EIT Food Seedbed Incubator), N (EIT Jumpstarter)

Final Results

- 12 teams defined their business model during the mentoring programme.
- 9 teams developed a business plan at the European level
- 10 teams applied to one or more Regional initiatives and/or European financial support instruments
- 12 teams defined a pitch presentation and identified investor events
- 7 teams identified and enrolled in further acceleration programmes at regional, national or European level

6 CONCLUSION

This report details the creation, structure, execution, and outcomes of the ENTREPRENEDU Mentoring Programme, alongside actions derived from participant feedback. The programme, featuring six modules integrating e-learning and interactive mentorship, aimed to provide a comprehensive journey for entrepreneurial teams from ideation to execution. The execution involved three phases, with the first two focussing on methodical preparation and development, culminating in reflection sessions where feedback was collected and measures for improvement were identified. While participants expressed high satisfaction, suggestions for enhancement were outlined, including for example clearer module guidelines, time expansion between modules and an expanded curriculum content. The report also provides insights into completed mentoring of Cohort 1, 2 and 3. From the consortium perspective, a recurring issue was the commitment of teams to the programme. To combat this issue, certificates were promised to teams that completed the whole mentoring programme. Therefore, the following teams received certificates: Shades of Blue, Backwards, E, G, H, J, K, L and N. With the team F, there is still an ongoing conversation regarding the awarding of the certificate. These measures slightly increased the commitment of the participants. However, to reach a full commitment, other measures might be practical for future iterations of the programme. These can include setting up a contract over the mentoring programme,

providing other rewards than certificates for a completion of the programme, or having the mentoring sessions in person. Ultimately, this report contributes to the ongoing efforts of the ENTREPRENEDU Project to bridge innovation and educational disparities across the EU.

7 APPENDIX

Cohort 1

MENTORING PROGRAM SCHEDULE

GROUP SESSIONS

Workshop Sessions (2 hour each)

Partner	Preferred Option	Name(s) of participating Mentors
Fraunhofer IPK	13.02.2024, 14:00-16:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	16.02.2024, 14:00-16:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	14.02.2024, 14:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	16.02.2024, 10:00-12:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	14.02.2024, 09:00-11:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	12.02.2024, 12:00-14:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Q&A Sessions (1 hour each)

Partner	Preferred Option	Name(s) of participating Mentors
Fraunhofer IPK	04.12.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	23.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	21.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	22.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	23.02.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	19.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Team A

Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	Did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	Did not participate	Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	Did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	Did not participate	Jaak Ennuste
Corallia	Did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	Did not participate	Ina Todorova

Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	Did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	Did not participate	Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	Did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	Did not participate	Jaak Ennuste
Corallia	Did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	Did not participate	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Reflection Session
Fraunhofer IPK	Did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	Did not participate	Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	Did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	Did not participate	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	Did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	Did not participate	Ina Todorova

Team B
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	08.01.2024, 08:00-09:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	15.01.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	17.01.2024, 17:00-18:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	13.02.2024, 12:00-13:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	15.01.2024, 15:30-16:30 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	13.02.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Ina Todorova
Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	22.01.2024, 08:00-09:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	22.01.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	24.01.2024, 17:00-18:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	19.02.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	29.01.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	20.02.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Reflection Session
Fraunhofer IPK	12.02.2024, 08:00-09:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	13.02.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	21.02.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	19.03.2024, 10:30-11:30 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	19.02.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	27.02.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Team C
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	16.01.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	10.01.2024, 12:00-13:00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	16.01.2024, 17:00-18:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	01.02.2024, 15:30-16:30 CET	Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	08.01.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	09.02.2024, 11:00-12:00 CET	Ina Todorova
Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	24.01.2024, 08:00-09:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	22.01.2024, 12:00-13:00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	23.01.2024, 17:00-18:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	14.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	22.01.2024, 12:00-13:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	16.02.2024, 11:00-12:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Reflection Session
Fraunhofer IPK	14.02.2024, 08:00-09:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	05.02.2024, 12:00-13:00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	19.02.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	11.03.2024, 15:30-16:30 CET	Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	12.02.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	01.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Team D
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	15.01.2024, 08:00-09:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	Did not participate	Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	Did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	Did not participate	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	Did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	Did not participate	Ina Todorova
Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	01.02.2024, 08:00-09:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	Did not participate	Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	Did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	Did not participate	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	Did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	Did not participate	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Reflection Session
Fraunhofer IPK	16.02.2024, 08:00-09:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	Did not participate	Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	Did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	Did not participate	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	Did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	Did not participate	Ina Todorova

Cohort 2

MENTORING PROGRAM SCHEDULE

GROUP SESSIONS

Workshop Sessions (2 hour each)

Partner	Preferred Option	Name(s) of participating Mentors
Fraunhofer IPK	13.02.2024, 14:00-16:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	16.02.2024, 14:00-16:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	14.02.2024, 14:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	16.02.2024, 10:00-12:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	14.02.2024, 09:00-11:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	12.02.2024, 12:00-14:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Q&A Sessions (1 hour each)

Partner	Preferred Option	Name(s) of participating Mentors
Fraunhofer IPK	04.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	23.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	21.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	22.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	23.02.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	19.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Ina Todorova

TEAM E

Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	28.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	26.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	29.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	01.03.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	11.03.2024, 11:00-12:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	27.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Ina Todorova
Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	04.03.2024, 12:00-13:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	04.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	08.03.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	05.03.2024, 11:00-12:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	15.03.2024, 11:00-12:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	05.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session (1 hour each)

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	11.03.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	20.03.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Paola Belingheri
FEA	19.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	15.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	22.03.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	12.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Ina Todorova

TEAM F
Mentoring Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	29.02.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	26.02.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	01.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	26.02.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	01.03.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	27.02.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Ina Todorova
Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	14.03.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	04.03.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	08.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	04.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	15.03.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	05.03.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	21.03.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	13.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	15.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	12.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	22.03.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	11.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Ina Todorova

TEAM G
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	01.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	29.02.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	04.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	05.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	22.03.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	06.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Ina Todorova
Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	07.03.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	01.07.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	11.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	08.03.2024, 14:30-15:30 CET	Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	01.04.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	14.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	14.03.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	01.07.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	28.03.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	13.03.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	23.04.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	21.03.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Ina Todorova

TEAM H
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	03.04.2024, 17:30-18:30 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	22.04.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	10.04.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	12.04.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	03.04.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	04.04.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Ina Todorova

Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	11.04.2024, 17:30-18:30 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	29.04.2023, 11:30-12:30 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	16.04.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	17.04.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	19.04.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	15.04.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	03.04.2024, 17:30-18:30 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	06.05.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	23.04.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	25.04.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	26.04.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	19.04.2024, 11:30-12:30 CET	Ina Todorova

TEAM I
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	26.02.2024, 12:30-13:30 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	27.02.2024, 12:30-13:30 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	05.04.2024, 12:30-13:30 CET	Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	02.04.2024, 12:30-13:30 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	did not participate	Ina Todorova

Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	did not participate	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	05.03.2024, 12:30-13:30 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	17.04.2024, 12:30-13:30 CET	Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	did not participate	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	did not participate	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	did not participate	Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	did not participate	Ina Todorova

Cohort 3

MENTORING PROGRAM SCHEDULE

GROUP SESSIONS

Workshop Sessions (2 hour each)

Partner	Preferred Option	Name(s) of participating Mentors
Fraunhofer IPK	27.05.2024, 15:00-17:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	28.05.2024, 15:00-17:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	29.05.2024, 15:00-17:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	30.05.2024, 15:00-17:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	21.06.2024, 14:00-16:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	31.05.2024, 10:00-12:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Q&A Sessions (1 hour each)

Partner	Preferred Option	Name(s) of participating Mentors
Fraunhofer IPK	04.06.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	03.06.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	05.06.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	06.06.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	Teams did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	07.06.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Ina Todorova

TEAM J

Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	18.06.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	10.06.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	19.06.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	13.06.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	05.07.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	17.06.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	25.06.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	20.06.2024, 17:00-18:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	26.06.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	20.06.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	12.07.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	01.07.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	02.07.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	26.06.2024, 17:00-18:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	02.07.2024, 17:00-18:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	27.06.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	18.07.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	05.07.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Ina Todorova

TEAM K
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	18.06.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	17.06.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	19.06.2024, 11:00-12:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	20.06.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	19.06.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	25.06.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	24.06.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	26.06.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	27.06.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	26.06.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	02.07.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	01.07.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	03.07.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	10.07.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	03.07.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Ina Todorova

TEAM L
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	25.06.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	26.06.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	27.06.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	28.06.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	01.07.2024, 12:00-13:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	26.06.2024, 11:00-12:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	02.07.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	17.07.2024, 08:30-09:30 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	04.07.2024, 10:00-11:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	31.07.2024, 09:00-10:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	15.07.2024, 08:30-09:30 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	02.07.2024, 11:00-12:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	09.07.2024, 08:30-09:30 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	24.07.2024, 09:30-10:30 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	11.07.2024, 10:30-11:30 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	17.09.2024, Time to be determined	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	16.07.2024, 08:30-09:30 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	16.07.2024, 09:30-10:30 CET	Ina Todorova

TEAM M
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	business resolved	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	business resolved	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	business resolved	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	business resolved	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	business resolved	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	business resolved	Ina Todorova

Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	business resolved	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	business resolved	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	business resolved	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	business resolved	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	business resolved	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	business resolved	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	business resolved	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	business resolved	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	business resolved	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	business resolved	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	business resolved	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	business resolved	Ina Todorova

TEAM N
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	24.07.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	16.07.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	11.07.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	04.09.2024, Time to be determined	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	12.07.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	12.07.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	29.07.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	did not participate	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	18.07.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	09.09.2024, Time to be determined	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	19.07.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	19.07.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	31.07.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	23.07.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	01.08.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	12.09.2024, Time to be determined	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	26.07.2024, 13:00-14:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	26.07.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Ina Todorova

TEAM O
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	10.07.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	10.07.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	11.07.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	15.07.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	12.07.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	12.07.2024, 14:00-15:00 CET	Ina Todorova
Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	17.07.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	18.07.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	did not participate	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	26.07.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	did not participate	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	24.07.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	24.07.2024, 15:00-16:00 CET	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	25.07.2024, 16:00-17:00 CET	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	did not participate	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	did not participate	Ina Todorova

TEAM P
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	did not participate	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	did not participate	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	did not participate	Ina Todorova
Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	did not participate	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	did not participate	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	did not participate	Ina Todorova

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux
LUISS	did not participate	Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio
FEA	did not participate	Fabio Biscotti
EBAN	did not participate	Abel Fernandez; Jacopo Piccagli
Corallia	did not participate	Orfeas Voutyras
Cleantech BG	did not participate	Ina Todorova

TEAM Q
Mentoring Sessions

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio Fabio Biscotti Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli Orfeas Voutyras Ina Todorova
LUISS	did not participate	
FEA	did not participate	
EBAN	did not participate	
Corallia	did not participate	
Cleantech BG	did not participate	

Partner	Session 2	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 2
Fraunhofer IPK	did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio Fabio Biscotti Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli Orfeas Voutyras Ina Todorova
LUISS	did not participate	
FEA	did not participate	
EBAN	did not participate	
Corallia	did not participate	
Cleantech BG	did not participate	

Reflection Session

Partner	Session 1	Name(s) of participating Mentors Session 1
Fraunhofer IPK	did not participate	Henry Buxmann; Katrin Singer-Coudoux Paola Belingheri; Emanuele Viglierchio Fabio Biscotti Abel Ferndandez; Jacopo Piccagli Orfeas Voutyras Ina Todorova
LUISS	did not participate	
FEA	did not participate	
EBAN	did not participate	
Corallia	did not participate	
Cleantech BG	did not participate	